

Supplementary Information for “Beyond the Standard Model: A Framework for Structural Models and Mass Calculation Methods of Fundamental Particles and Their Broader Extensions”

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This PDF file includes:

- **S1:** The work encompasses the proposal, establishment, and application of the matter-charge hypothesis and the particle toroidal-orbit model. Employing this new framework, the structure of dozens of particles is discussed, providing their attribute calculation formulas, with all calculated attribute values in complete agreement with the measured values. The discussion also includes content on strong and weak interactions, as well as atomic nucleus structure.
- **S2:** The study of relativistic effects based on the particle toroidal-orbit model, including a new mechanism for mass and discussions on the relationship between energy and the quantity of matter-charges.
- **S3:** The principle analysis of electromagnetic interactions according to the matter-charge hypothesis, including direct derivations of the Coulomb force and Lorentz force formulas.
- **S4:** The relationship between the new framework and quantum mechanics, focusing on interpretations of matter waves, quantum numbers, and electron orbits within the new framework.
- **S5:** The fundamental mechanisms of universal gravitation and gravitational fields, distinguishing between general relativity and gravitational mechanisms.

These five sections can be regarded as a series of research papers, proposing the matter-charge hypothesis related to the essence of matter and the particle toroidal-orbit model concerning the authentic structure of particles. Moreover, these sections introduce the application of this holistic framework across various fields, serving also as a validation of the new framework in different domains.

The references in the Supplementary Information (SI) section overlap with those in the main text, but are reorganized in the order of their appearance in the SI.

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S1: The Proposal and Application of the New Framework in Particle Physics

1. Introduction

In the realm of particle physics, as well as within the broader scope of physical sciences, a traditional tenet has prevailed: particles are commonly accepted as the fundamental constituents of matter, and charge is attributed as an intrinsic characteristic of these entities. Challenging this long-standing viewpoint, our research introduces a revolutionary paradigm, postulating charge as a more primitive entity—termed “matter-charge.” In this framework, electromagnetic properties emerge from the interplay of matter-charges, and particles manifest as dynamic toroidal structures composed of this foundational substance. These novel concepts underpin our “matter-charge hypothesis” and “particle toroidal-orbit model,” which are explicated in detail herein.

This work heralds a significant departure from conventional understanding, holding the potential to reverberate across vast expanses of physical sciences. In this Supplementary Information, we also give a brief outline of the consistent and advantageous alterations engendered by this fresh perspective within the spheres of special relativity, quantum mechanics, electromagnetic dynamics, and gravitation. Nevertheless, the crux of our exposition is dedicated to elucidating this nascent particle architecture and delineating a unified schematic for the computation of particle attributes.

Envisioned within our theoretical construct, each particle is characterized by a unique and intuitive “toroidal-orbit” configuration that elegantly marries three fundamental aspects—mass, radius, and magnetic moment—into a harmonious triptych. Albeit this vantage diverges markedly from the Standard Model, it not only stands robustly self-consistent but also simplifies the calculation of said attributes. For instance, our model offers a straightforward technique,

far simpler than the solutions provided by the Standard Model [1], to compute the proton’s spin magnetic moment, expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mu_p}{\mu_N} &= \frac{E_p}{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times E_e} \times \sin(45^\circ) \times 4 \\ &+ \left(-\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}\right) \times \frac{4\pi+1}{16} \times \sin(45^\circ) + \frac{\frac{\alpha^2}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha}}} \quad (\text{S1.1}) \\ &= 2.79284734468, \end{aligned}$$

where μ_N denotes the nuclear magneton. This value is remarkably in line with the experimentally measured value of 2.79284734463 (82) μ_N [2], which underscores the precision of our model using only fundamental constants like the rest energies of protons and electrons, and the fine-structure constant [3].

With the particle’s toroidal-orbit structure established, its radius becomes inherently determinable. Below, we present the formula devised for the proton’s radius:

$$r_p = \frac{c\hbar}{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{4} \times E_e} = 0.8308444 \times 10^{-15} \text{m}. \quad (\text{S1.2})$$

The computed radius exhibits close concordance with empirical determinations of 0.831 (7) (12) $\times 10^{-15} \text{m}$ [4]. Such precise agreement with experimental values supports the validity of our model and offers promising predictions for other particles’ radii, which are explored further within the paper.

Likewise, upon fixing a particle’s specific toroidal-orbit structure, its mass is concurrently ascertained. In our innovative model, a particle’s mass originates from its rest energy and the toroidal-orbit structure, as elucidated in S2. This contrasts starkly with the mass-generation mechanism via the Higgs field posited by the Standard Model. The structural formula for protons, also applicable to calculating the rest energy, is demonstrated below:

$$\frac{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{4} - \frac{E_p}{E_e} \times \frac{1}{4}}{\left(\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{4}\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{4}}}. \quad (\text{S1.3})$$

The derived rest energy $E_p = 938.095 \text{MeV}$, shows only a minute variance from the accepted experimen-

tal mass of protons, 938.27208816MeV [2]. While minor discrepancies exist for certain particles, the trend of our computed values aligning closely with empirical measurements is compelling and indicative of the model's potential.

Notwithstanding the Standard Model's resounding success in elucidating diverse phenomena in particle physics, it encounters known limitations. It lacks a mechanism to incorporate gravity, fails to fully unravel the mystery of neutrino masses, and grapples with persistent experimental anomalies, such as the anomalous magnetic moment of the muon [5] and the mass of the W boson [6]. This compels us to venture into new theoretical territories to unfurl the deeper essence of particles.

The body of this paper unfolds the structural intricacies of multiple particles and computes their properties, showcasing near-perfect alignment with experimental data. Although further foundational physical mechanisms await exploration, the evidence suggests a universally applicable framework.

Therefore, the ensuing text commences with a rationale for the toroidal-orbit structures of particles and advances cogent arguments for the primacy of matter-charge. Subsequently, we define the stability criteria for these structures and the computational formulas at their disposal. In culmination, the paper delves into the methodology for discerning particle structures and deriving their properties. Along the way, the text includes discussions on strong and weak interactions, quarks, and neutrinos, laying the groundwork for pioneering insights in particle physics and a deeper comprehension of the constitution of matter.

Importantly, while our model diverges from the Standard Model, particularly in envisaging charge as a primary substance and particles as toroidal structures thereof, it is not an outright repudiation of the empirical triumphs the Standard Model has amassed. Rather, the models may coexist in various respects: for instance, quarks remain pivotal within both models, and our toroidal-orbit framework offers direct cal-

culative formulae for quark masses. By presenting an explicit spatial structure, our model might furnish the perceptive breakthrough that the Standard Model currently approaches with abstraction.

2. Inference of a novel particle model from the revised proton radius measurements

In 2010, a pivotal experiment known as the Proton Radius Puzzle was conducted by the Paul Scherrer Institute in Switzerland and Harvard University in the USA, which revealed that the proton's radius was approximately 4% smaller than the previously accepted value [7]. This significant discovery challenges the existing understanding of proton structure. By correlating the revised proton radius with its mass and spin magnetic moment, we propose a classical model for proton structure. This proposed model lays the foundation for our innovative particle toroidal-orbit model and matter-charge hypothesis.

a. The toroidal-orbits in protons

In the particle toroidal-orbit model, particles are conceptualized as having classical orbit-like structures that determine their properties—a relationship that is particularly pronounced in the case of protons.

The rest energy of a proton can be expressed as $E_p = 1.50327755 \times 10^{-10}$ J [2]. A photon possessing this energy correlates to a wavelength, $\lambda = \frac{ch}{E_p} = 1.32141 \times 10^{-15}$ m.

Envisioning the proton as a sphere with a radius of $r_p = 0.831 \times 10^{-15}$ m [4], we calculate its circumference, $C_p = 2\pi r_p = 5.22133 \times 10^{-15}$ m.

A remarkable parallelism presents itself when this circumference is juxtaposed with the wavelength of a photon carrying one-fourth of the proton's rest energy. For such a photon, $\lambda' = 4\lambda$, yielding a ratio $\frac{4\lambda}{C_p} = \frac{5.28564 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}}{5.22133 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}} = 1.0123$, a value astonishingly proximal to unity.

This observation suggests a non-coincidental underlying mechanism, which leads us to propose the following hypothesis:

If a toroidal-orbit, capable of confining photons or energy in a circulation path where the circumference is commensurate with the wavelength of the confined photons, would have a radius, for an energy capacity of $E_p \times \frac{1}{4}$, as $r' = \frac{\frac{ch}{E_p \times \frac{1}{4}}}{2\pi} = 0.8412357 \times 10^{-15}$ m. Though this is not the exact proton radius according to our model, it closely aligns with the values reported by the Particle Data Group (PDG) in 2023 [8].

A composite of four such toroidal-orbits could potentially convey the energy and radius characteristics of a proton. This leads to the fundamental inquiry: if the attributes of this structure mirror those of a proton, could it indeed represent the true structure of the proton? Moreover, could this model extend to depict other particles?

b. The energy and charge within the toroidal-orbit

Within the context of the particle toroidal-orbit model, we envision particles as entities composed of classical toroidal-orbits characterized by radii r . When we posit a charge q traveling along these orbits at the speed of light c , the magnetic moment of the orbit can be deduced using classical electromagnetic theory as follows:

$$m = I \times S = \left(q \times \frac{v}{2\pi r} \right) \times (\pi r^2) = \frac{1}{2} qcr. \quad (\text{S1.4})$$

It is crucial to note the inverse correlation between the radius r and the energy E . If the aforementioned charge q correlates with E , as implied by the equation, a constant magnetic moment is inferred.

For a toroidal-orbit with an energy E_e , equivalent to the rest energy of an electron, the radius is $r_e = \frac{\lambda}{2\pi} = \frac{\frac{ch}{E_e}}{2\pi} = \frac{\frac{ch}{m_e c^2}}{2\pi} = \frac{\hbar}{m_e c}$. An orbiting unit charge at velocity c within this toroidal-orbit yields an orbital magnetic moment of $m = \frac{1}{2} \times e \times c \times r_e = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{e}{m_e} \times \hbar = 1\mu_B$, equivalent to a Bohr magneton.

Given the measured magnetic moment of the electron is $-1.00115965218059(13)\mu_B$ [9], and acknowledging that this toroidal-orbit model exhibits the same energy and magnetic moment as the electron, it prompts the question: if r_e is indeed the actual radius of the electron, yet certain mechanisms (discussed later in the text) prevent us from observing it as we can the proton's radius, could this toroidal-orbit structure truly represent the underlying structure of the electron?

Further, if the energy of a toroidal-orbit is $E_X = E_e \times X$, its radius will be $r_X = r_e \times \frac{1}{X}$. Assuming the electric charge q_X rotating within the toroidal-orbit is proportional to the energy capacity E_X , then:

$$q_X = \frac{E_X}{E_e} \times e = X \times e, \quad (\text{S1.5})$$

and as a result, the magnetic moment produced by any such toroidal-orbit remains a constant μ_B .

Viewing protons as structures composed of concentric toroidal-orbits, with each orbit carrying energy $E_p \times \frac{1}{4}$, and organizing these orbits into two perpendicular groups as depicted in Fig. S1.1, results in a total magnetic moment of $1\mu_B \times \sin(45^\circ) \times 4 = 2.82842712\mu_B$. This number is close to the measured value of $2.79284734463(82)\mu_N$. The comparison reveals an intriguing correlation, although one value is expressed in Bohr magnetons and the other in nuclear magnetons, which involves a conversion factor related to the mass ratio of electron to proton $\frac{m_e}{m_p}$. If there exists a rationale whereby the orbital magnetic moments generated by the toroidal-orbits in protons are $\frac{E_p}{E_e}$ or $\frac{m_p}{m_e}$ times smaller than those generated in electron toroidal-orbits, then the toroidal-orbit structure posited here could coherently link the three key properties of particles—mass, radius, and magnetic moment—as will be demonstrated later in the text.

Note on magneton units: The nuclear magneton is the unit for magnetic moment in protons and is defined based on a proton with the electron's charge; it is less than the Bohr magneton by the mass ratio of the electron to the proton, $\frac{m_e}{m_p}$, approximately

Figure S1.1. The proposed toroidal-orbit structure of protons.

3. The matter-charge hypothesis

To explain the specific magnetic moments contributed by each toroidal-orbit within a proton, we postulate the existence of a total motion charge, denoted as $q_p = \frac{E_p}{E_e} \times e = 1836.15267343 \times e$, distributed across four toroidal-orbits. Yet, it is an incontrovertible fact that protons present a single unit of positive charge. To reconcile this, we posit that a compensating negative charge of equal magnitude is nestled within the proton to neutralize the otherwise overwhelming positive electric field.

Our model describes a proton as a tripartite entity: a positive charge q_p , an equal magnitude negative charge q_p , and a lone positive unit charge e . Notably, the first two are intimately linked to the proton's rest energy E_p . The positive charge q_p , circulating at light speed within the toroidal-orbit r_p , is the primary contributor to the proton's spin magnetic moment. The negative charge q_p and the unit charge e have orbit radii significantly smaller than r_p , leading to the emergence of two magnetic moments of substantially different scales. The cumulative effect of these moments is encapsulated in the overall magnetic moment of the proton, as delineated in Equation (S1.1).

This model has profound implications: if the proton is indeed composed of these three constitutive parts, the traditional role of charge as a mere property of particles is transcended. Charge becomes a primordial form of matter. In this lens, a proton is a structured assembly of toroidal-orbits of this matter,

which embodies electromagnetic properties and could be the foundational substance for electromagnetic interactions, as elucidated in S3. The energy within the toroidal-orbits is intimately connected to electric charge, as expressed in Eq. (S1.5). This leads us to posit the matter-charge hypothesis:

- Matter-charges exist in two varieties: positive matter-charges (Y_+) and negative matter-charges (Y_-). Positive charges emanate their properties from Y_+ , while negative charges stem from Y_- . The electricity quantity, q , reflects the amount of Y_+ or Y_- , with $|q|$ denoting the quantity of either matter-charge.
- In structures where Y_+ and Y_- coexist in equal measures, the term $Y_{\pm}$ is applied. Their electrical influences negate each other, and energy correlates directly with the $Y_{\pm}$ quantity. The associated $Y_{\pm}$ for energy E is represented by $|E|$.
- Matter-charges, within space or any structure, traverse at the constant velocity of light, c .
- Y_+ and Y_- are the most elementary forms of matter, immutable and unable to transmute between each other.

It is crucial to distinguish Y_+ and Y_- from the conventional unit charge, e . The constant e symbolizes a specific aggregation of Y_+ or Y_- , denoted by $|e|$. It is integral to the particle structure, with another portion linked to the particle's innate rest energy.

Moreover, Equation (S1.5) suggests that the matter-charge corresponding to an electron's rest energy is quantitatively identical to the matter-charge associated with the unit charge, leading to the inference that $|E_e| = |e|$. Thus, E_e is tied fundamentally to e , and within the purview of the matter-charge hypothesis, E_e is deemed the rudimentary unit of energy.

a. Presence of matter-charges in space

Energy’s ubiquity in space is a universally recognized truth. If Y_+ and Y_- , in balanced quantities, form the material basis for particles’ rest energy, then it stands to reason that all energy forms should mirror this composition. The transformation of gravitational potential energy into kinetic energy entails a reciprocal exchange of $Y_{\pm}$ between space and the particle’s orbit. Similarly, zero-point energy, as manifested in the Casimir effect, is a tangible representation of $Y_{\pm}$ within the spatial fabric.

The matter-charge hypothesis proposes that particles are dynamic aggregates of self-contained matter-charges, and space itself is suffused with these same charges. This shared matter foundation underpins the interactions between particles and those between particles and space.

b. Filling-toroidal-orbits and empty-toroidal-orbits

The Casimir effect, by revealing energy fluctuations at every point in space, implies that matter-charges in the spatial medium exhibit dynamic structures. Given that a particle’s matter-charge can manifest as a dynamic structure akin to a toroidal-orbit, it is plausible that matter-charge in space is similarly structured.

We refer to the structure formed by the matter-charge of particles’ rest energy as a “filling-toroidal-orbit,” and the structure formed by spatial matter-charge as an “empty-toroidal-orbit.” According to the particle toroidal-orbit model, all particles consist of these two orbit types.

The particle’s rest energy, radius, and magnetic moment are all determined by what we term the ‘filling-toroidal-orbit.’ Notably, in particles such as protons, filling-toroidal-orbits typically occur in pairs. Each pair consists of both positive (Y_+) and negative (Y_-) matter-charges—stemming from the particle’s inherent rest energy—which occupy toroidal-orbits of

different radii.

However, detecting an empty-toroidal-orbit poses a challenge because the matter-charge it contains originates from space, and equal amounts of Y_+ and Y_- within the orbit revolve in the same direction. This concurrent rotation neither emits detectable energy nor generates observable electric or magnetic fields. Yet, given that the unit charge in a particle’s structure is a constant, an empty-toroidal-orbit within the particle’s structure can maintain only defined energy capacities and spatial scales. These series of empty-toroidal-orbits fulfill a pivotal role in the particle’s structural framework.

4. Foundations for calculations in the particle toroidal-orbit model

The quark model has significantly aided in the discovery and categorization of numerous particles. Nonetheless, when viewed through the prism of the particle toroidal-orbit model, particles emerge as composed of two fundamental toroidal-orbits. These elementary structures have capacities of $\frac{1}{\alpha}$ and $\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}$ times the electron’s rest energy E_e , and are referred to as the “basic-toroidal-orbits” r_{-137} and r_{-861} . They possess energies of $E_{-137} = E_e \times \frac{1}{\alpha}$ and $E_{-861} = E_{-137} \times 2\pi = E_e \times \frac{2\pi}{\alpha}$ respectively.

For a more intuitive introduction, let’s preview some conclusions: the muon consists of one filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} and two empty-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} ; the π meson consists of one empty-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} and two filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} ; the proton comprises two filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-861} and one filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-137} ; tau leptons are made up of four filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-861} and one filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-137} , and so forth. Notably, quarks are also closely associated with these two basic-toroidal-orbits, with the new model identifying quarks as a special toroidal-orbit structure and providing an extremely direct formula for calculating quark masses, exemplified by $E_s = E_{-137} \times \sqrt{2} = E_e \times \frac{1}{\alpha} \times \sqrt{2} =$

99.03MeV, aligning closely with the latest strange quark mass value $m_s = 98.7_{-3.2}^{+4.0}\text{MeV}/c^2$ [10].

Acknowledging the centrality of the basic-toroidal-orbits is therefore indispensable. Furthermore, this section explores the stability mechanisms of particles, necessitating the introduction of the toroidal-orbit width formula —the diameter of the cross-sectional circle within the toroidal-orbit. We also discuss the orbit radius formula for the matter-charge of the particle’s unit charge, a vital component for precisely calculating particle magnetic moments.

It is important to note, however, that the last two formulae are presently introduced as empirical formulae. Despite their apparent simplicity, the underlying physical mechanisms remain elusive, potentially reliant on a more profound understanding of matter-charge. Nevertheless, all calculations pertaining to particle properties suggest that these formulae are consistent and reliable.

a. Basic-toroidal-orbit r_{-1} , r_{-137} , r_{-861}

Besides r_{-137} and r_{-861} , the orbit corresponding to the rest energy of the electron E_e is categorized as a basic-toroidal-orbit, labeled as r_{-1} . Its radius is $r_{-1} = r_e = \frac{c\hbar}{E_e} = 3.8615 \times 10^{-13}\text{m}$, and its circumference is $C_{-1} = r_{-1} \times 2\pi = 2.4263 \times 10^{-12}\text{m}$, which is instrumental in the computation of particle structures.

In essence, the energy of a toroidal-orbit dictates its radius and circumference. For instance, $r_{-137} = r_{-1} \times \alpha = 2.8179 \times 10^{-15}\text{m}$, and $r_{-861} = r_{-137} \times \frac{1}{2\pi} = r_{-1} \times \frac{\alpha}{2\pi}$. For alignment with existing physical models, r_{-1} can also be represented as $\frac{\hbar}{m_e c}$, correlating with the electron’s Compton wavelength $\lambda_e^{\text{Compton}}$, reflecting the electron’s quantum “size”. Further derivation for r_{-137} yields $r_{-137} = r_e \times \alpha = \frac{ch}{2\pi E_e} \times \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0\hbar c} = \frac{e^2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 m_e c^2} = r_e^{\text{classical}}$, equating to the electron’s classical radius. It is important to recognize that identical formulae can have disparate interpretations and applications in different models.

While a foundational comprehension of these toroidal-orbits is adequate for ensuing calculations, the underlying reason why all particles exhibit these orbits is still a subject for future research.

Matter-charge corresponding to the unit charge e interacts with spatial matter-charge to form a series of stable toroidal-orbits. These are initially empty-toroidal-orbits, but under high-energy conditions or when a particle accrues sufficient matter-charge, they have a propensity to fill, forming discernible filling-toroidal-orbits. These standardized constituents are therefore crucial in particle assembly; once a particle’s toroidal-orbit structure is determined, its properties can be conclusively inferred.

At the outset of this paper, by converting E_e and $E_p \times \frac{1}{4}$ into photons, we obtained r_{-1} and the rough radii of proton, but this is just one calculable method. In the later section, we will discuss the toroidal-orbit structure of photons, which will supplement the missing physical logic here.

As introduced previously, Y_+ and Y_- corresponding to the electron’s rest energy E_e enter different orbits. Given that the electron has a unit negative charge, envisioning this scenario becomes straightforward: Y_- , corresponding to the electron’s unit negative charge, rotates in the smallest orbit at the electron’s core. The Y_+ from the electron’s rest energy circulates within the outer r_{-861} orbit, while the outermost r_{-1} accommodates the Y_- from the rest energy. If we consider the Y_+ and Y_- corresponding to the rest energy as a coupled entity through spatial matter-charge, then the quantity of $|E_e|$ of Y_+ and Y_- would orbit around the centrally situated $|e|$ of Y_- , forming the orbit r_{-137} .

A more thorough derivation is provided in later. Owing to a similar mechanism, in other particle structures, Y_+ and Y_- corresponding to rest energy enter different toroidal-orbits, typically diverging by a factor of $\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}$. Nonetheless, the quantities and velocities of Y_+ and Y_- within these orbits are equal. Thus, if the outermost toroidal-orbit contributes a magnetic

moment of $1\mu_B$, the internal toroidal-orbit would contribute $\frac{\alpha}{2\pi} = 0.0011614\mu_B$. In the context of QED, this term is known as the Schwinger correction, describing the slight deviation of the actual magnetic moment of electrons from the Dirac theory's prediction, predominantly applied to the magnetic moment calculations of electrons and muons. This underscores how identical formulae can carry differing interpretations and applications across various models. As we shall see later, this concept is similarly applied to protons and neutrons, yielding magnetic moment predictions that are more accurate than those offered by the Standard Model.

b. Stable structure of particles and formula for toroidal-orbit width

A toroidal-orbit is a classical structure that can be fully characterized when its energy capacity is known. The major radius, perimeter, and width of the toroidal-orbit—the cross-sectional diameter or the “inner diameter” of the ring when vertically cut—can all be calculated using corresponding formulae.

If two toroidal-orbits are arranged perpendicularly, as in protons, part of the length of one orbit obstructs the other. The energy corresponding to the unobstructed portion of the toroidal-orbit contributes to the particle's rest energy. In other words, when the matter-charge associated with the rest energy of a particle does not suffice to fill its entire toroidal-orbit, an energy deficit arises. If the length of this deficit matches the width of a certain or a related basic-toroidal-orbit, the tightly interwoven orbit structure signifies a stable particle. With the exception of the electron, nearly all particles discussed in this text conform to stable structures established by this mechanism.

For all calculations related to particle structures that follow, the formula for the width of the toroidal-

orbit is indispensable:

$$W_{-X} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{X}} \times C_{-1}. \quad (\text{S1.6})$$

For a select few particle structures, the toroidal-orbit “unfolds,” incorporating an additional factor of 2π and altering the formula to $W_{-X} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{X}} \times C_{-1}$. The physical significance of this alteration is elaborated upon later in the text. Here, X signifies the energy of the target orbit relative to E_e , and $C_{-1} = r_{-1} \times 2\pi = 2.4263 \times 10^{-12}\text{m}$ corresponds to the circumference of r_{-1} .

For the first basic-toroidal-orbit r_{-1} with $X = 1$, it is recognized that as the energy within the orbit is amplified, the major radius of the orbit correspondingly diminishes, and the inner diameter of the orbit contracts as well. Hence, all toroidal-orbits can be perceived as derivatives of the r_{-1} orbit. Notably, for the r_{-1} orbit, its inner radius is proportionally $\frac{1}{4}\alpha$ of its major radius, and the major radius itself is α times larger than the radius of the Bohr orbit, indicating a definitive quantitative connection. It must, however, be acknowledged that despite subsequent calculations validating the precision of this formula, the exact mechanism underlying this relationship has yet to be discerned. Consequently, the formula must currently be regarded as empirical.

c. Radius formula for a particle's unit charge

The new model segregates the matter-charge within particles into three components, with their rotation within designated toroidal-orbits constituting the principal element of the particle's spin magnetic moment. In an electron's structure, the sum of Y_+ and Y_- equals $|E_e|$, revolving on r_{-1} and r_{-861} , and contributing to the magnetic moments μ_{part1} and μ_{part2} respectively. However, the Y_- signifying the unit charge also rotates on a diminutive orbit at the electron's center, contributing to μ_{part3} .

The radius for the matter-charge corresponding to the unit charge of a particle can be defined by a

clear formula, closely related to the width of the inner diameter of the toroidal-orbit.

$$r_{unit\ charge} = \frac{\frac{\alpha^2}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{X}} \times r_{-1}. \quad (S1.7)$$

In this instance, X denotes the energy of the toroidal-orbit most adjacent to the unit charge as a multiple of E_e . Analogous to Eq. (S1.6), under specific conditions, the miniature toroidal-orbit must “unfold,” integrating an additional 2π factor and modifying the formula to $r_{unit\ charge} = \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{X}} \times r_{-1}$. Introducing the unit charge into this tiny orbit gives rise to the μ_{part3} segment of the magnetic moment.

Summating these three components of the magnetic moment yields the total magnetic moment of the particle. For protons and neutrons, the computed magnetic moments nearly mirror the measured values; for electrons and muons, a slight variance persists. Notwithstanding, considering there is also relative motion between the toroidal-orbit tied to the unit charge and the toroidal-orbits associated with the rest energy, contributing a trivial μ_{part4} , adding a coefficient of $\frac{1}{(2\pi) \times (4\pi+1)}$ along with factors that account for the shape of the toroidal-orbit based on $r_{unit\ charge}$ can achieve results that closely match measured values.

Regrettably, although these additions bear clear correlations and convey definite physical meaning, the mechanism determining the specific orbit of matter-charge is not comprehended. As such, they must be approached as empirical formulae. We anticipate that with the acquisition of more measured magnetic moments of particles and further developments in the dynamics of matter-charge, a more comprehensive understanding will emerge.

5. The structures and attributes of several major particles

In the particle toroidal-orbit model, the structure of the particle determines its attribute values, and vice versa.

In this section, we will focus on four pivotal particles: electrons, muons, protons, and neutrons, showcasing the application of the new model. Not only do we have accurate data on their masses, but we also possess precise measurements of each particle’s magnetic moment and the radii for protons and neutrons. This critical information will significantly aid in identifying their toroidal-orbit structures. Moreover, this group, comprising two leptons and two baryons, will reveal crucial insights, setting the stage for the forthcoming discussion on strong and weak interactions.

a. Electrons

As has been elucidated earlier, the electron’s rest energy is posited as the fundamental unit of energy, positing $|E_e| = |e|$. The most external toroidal-orbit is designated as r_{-1} , distinctive in that it does not intersect with any other toroidal-orbits. When considering the magnetic moment contributions from the Y_- and Y_+ elements, which correspond to E_e at orbits r_{-1} and r_{-861} respectively, we obtain $\mu_{Part1} + \mu_{Part2} = -1\mu_B - \frac{\alpha}{2\pi}\mu_B = -1.0011614097\mu_B$. This computed value approximates very closely to the empirically measured spin magnetic moment of the electron, a quantity typically refined through Quantum Electrodynamics (QED) as a correction relative to the Bohr magneton.

In QED, the further exploration of the electron’s magnetic moment involves intricate higher-order loop corrections, computable through the use of Feynman diagrams. These amendments are intrinsically electromagnetic, reflecting the complexity inherent in quantum loop diagrams and requiring sophisticated computational techniques for their resolution [11]. Contrastingly, within the particle toroidal-orbit model, the ensuing task is to ascertain the specific toroidal-orbits corresponding to the matter-charge associated with the electron’s unit charge.

Protons are constituted of interwoven filling-toroidal-orbits, while the majority of particles consist

of a mix of filling-toroidal-orbits and empty-toroidal-orbits. This suggests that all particles, electrons included, should exhibit a three-dimensional structure. In addition to the peripheral filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-1} , electrons harbor a set of interlocked empty-toroidal-orbits, which together form the most stable configuration. Remarkably, this structure is akin to that of protons, accommodating a total energy equivalent to the proton's rest energy E_p , including four toroidal-orbits denoted as r_p . These intersect with r_{-1} and r_{-861} at an angle of 45° , as depicted in Fig. S1.1. While these toroidal-orbits are not directly observable, they exert an influence on the matter-charge associated with the electron's unit charge positioned at their nucleus.

By substituting $X = \frac{E_p \times \frac{1}{4}}{E_e}$, representative of the proton's actual toroidal-orbit energy, into Eq. (S1.7), we derive the radius of the toroidal-orbit linked to the unit charge. Subsequently, integrating the electric charge e and the velocity c , and acknowledging the 45° angular relationship between these orbits and the r_{-1} orbit, we calculate $\mu_{Part3} = \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{E_p \times \frac{1}{4}}{E_e}}} \times \sin(45^\circ) \times 1\mu_B$.

Thus, following the sign correction for the three components, the total magnetic moment is deduced as:

$$\frac{\mu_{e(3)}}{\mu_B} = (-1) + \left(-\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}\right) + \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{E_p \times \frac{1}{4}}{E_e}}} \times \sin(45^\circ), \quad (\text{S1.8})$$

wherein $\mu_{e(3)}$ is $-1.00115965224833\mu_B$, aligning well with the latest empirical measurement of $-1.00115965218059(13)\mu_B$.

If we introduce a further term $\mu_{Part4} = \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{E_p \times \frac{1}{4}}{E_e}}} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{(4\pi+1) \times (2\pi)}}{1\mu_B}$, which signifies a correction with a definable spatial structure, its underlying physical mechanism remains to be fully elucidated. Nevertheless, the value is remarkably close to the measured

magnetic moment:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mu_{e(4)}}{\mu_B} &= (-1) + \left(-\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}\right) + \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{E_p \times \frac{1}{4}}{E_e}}} \times \sin(45^\circ) \\ &+ \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{E_p \times \frac{1}{4}}{E_e}}} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{\pi}}{(4\pi+1) \times (2\pi)} = -1.00115965218060. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S1.9})$$

b. Muons

The fundamental toroidal-orbit for electrons is denoted as r_{-1} , whereas for muons, it is identified as r_{-861} . The muon structure is characterized by the intersecting orbit r_{-861} and a pair of perpendicular empty-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , converging at an angle of 45° . This configuration is illustrated in Fig. S1.2. As delineated earlier, the matter-charge in the un-

Figure S1.2. The toroidal-orbit structure of a muon.

covered part of the filling-toroidal-orbit corresponds to E_μ , while the matter-charge in the empty-toroidal-orbit is borrowed from space. Considering the inclination angle 45° and there are two intersections, the length of the energy gap on the filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} should be twice the width of the empty-toroidal-orbit r_{-137} multiply by $\sqrt{2}$. The following calculation confirms this:

The circumference of the filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} is $C_{-861} = \frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \times C_{-1}$, and the full-load energy is $E_{-861} = \frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times E_e$, and $E_\mu = \frac{105.6583755(23)\text{MeV}/c^2}{0.51099895000(15)\text{MeV}/c^2} \times E_e = 206.76828299 \times E_e$ [2], the length of the energy gap is $L = \frac{E_{-861} - E_\mu}{E_{-861}} \times C_{-861}$. Then, add coefficient 2π using Eq. (S1.6), we obtain the width: $W_{-137} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} \times C_{-1}$. Therefore, the length covered by the tilted-empty toroidal-orbits is $W = W_{-137} \times 2 \times \sqrt{2}$.

The results are: $L = 0.00088251 \times C_{-1}$, $W = 0.00088158 \times C_{-1}$, and the difference is $0.00000093 \times$

$C_{-1} = 2.256425 \times 10^{-19}$ m, which is very small, and it is a remarkably stable muon structure.

By correlating the gap length with the formula for the toroidal-orbit width, we can calculate the mass of the muon.

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} - \frac{E_\mu}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}\right)^2} \times C_{-1} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} \times \sqrt{2} \times C_{-1}. \quad (\text{S1.10})$$

The result obtained is $E_\mu = 106.008079$ MeV. Although this value is close to its measured value, there is a significant deviation of about 0.35 MeV.

To calculate the magnetic moment, consider:

r_{-861} is the outermost orbit of muons, filled with matter-charge sourced from E_μ and borrowed from space. The Y_- corresponding to $q_\mu = \frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times e$ rotates at c on r_{-861} , obtaining $\mu_{Part1} = \frac{1}{2} \times q_\mu \times c \times r_{-861} = 1\mu_B$.

The Y_+ in E_e will move towards the unit negative charge at the center of the electron, and the same is true for the Y_+ in E_μ , $\mu_{Part2} = \frac{1}{2} \times q_\mu \times c \times (r_{-861} \times \frac{\alpha}{2\pi}) = \frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \mu_B$.

The first two terms of the muon magnetic moment are the same as those of the electron, but the empty-toroidal-orbit in the muon structure is r_{-137} , which gives $X = \frac{1}{\alpha}$. Also, add a coefficient 2π , substituting Eq. (S1.7) to obtain the orbit $\frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} \times r_{-1}$, and this part contributes $\mu_{Part3} = \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} \mu_B$. Summing the corrected components leads us to the total magnetic moment:

$$\frac{\mu_{\mu(3)}}{\mu_B} = (-1) + \left(-\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}\right) + \left(-\frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}}\right) = -1.00116595870. \quad (\text{S1.11})$$

By incorporating $\mu_{Part4} = \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} \times \frac{\sin(45^\circ)}{(4\pi+1) \times (2\pi)} \times 1\mu_B$, we adjust $\mu_{\mu(4)}$ to $-1.00116592097\mu_B$, comfortably within the bounds of the latest measured value $-1.00116592061(41)\mu_B$ [5]. A further term $\frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} \times$

$\frac{\alpha}{(4\pi+1) \times (2\pi)} \times 1\mu_B$ yields:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mu_{\mu(4)}}{\mu_B} &= (-1) + \left(-\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}\right) + \left(-\frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}}\right) \\ &+ \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} \times \frac{\sin(45^\circ) + \alpha}{(4\pi+1) \times (2\pi)} = -1.00116592058, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S1.12})$$

which aligns remarkably close to the measured value. At present, precise magnetic moment measurements exist for only four particles, and additional corrections with μ_{Part4} are necessitated solely for electrons and muons. This does not suffice to establish a comprehensive pattern, particularly as the dynamics of matter-charge remain underexplored. Hence, despite the fact that coefficients like $\sin(45^\circ)$, 2π , α , and $4\pi+1$ recur with frequency in toroidal-orbit relationships and that we can provide an exceedingly detailed account of the internal structure of electrons and muons, we cannot definitively affirm whether this depiction mirrors the true internal state of these particles—this remains a significant limitation.

c. Protons

Protons manifest complex structures, constructed from an amalgamation of toroidal-orbits rather than from a singular basic-toroidal-orbit.

Imagine a scenario where one filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-137} combines with two r_{-861} orbits to form a proto-particle. The energy sum of these components would yield $E_{p0} = E_{-137} + 2 \times E_{-861} = \frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times E_e = 1859.0811 \times E_e$.

Distributing these matter-charges evenly across four toroidal-orbits tentatively postulates each orbit's energy capacity as $\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{4} \times E_e$. This allocation results in a circumferential length $C_p = C_{-1} \times \frac{4\alpha}{4\pi+1}$. Consequently, we deduce a radius $r_p = r_{-1} \times \frac{4\alpha}{4\pi+1} = 0.8308444 \times 10^{-15}$ m, i.e., Eq. (S1.2). Remarkably, this radius closely aligns with the proton radius measurements acquired via laser spectroscopy in 2019 [4].

Further partitioning the proton's energy E_p into

four equivalent segments and assigning them to these orbits, we compute the energy gap length as $L = \frac{E_{p0} \times \frac{1}{4} - E_p \times \frac{1}{4}}{E_{p0} \times \frac{1}{4}} \times C_p = 0.00002654 \times C_{-1}$. Utilizing Eq. (S1.6), we ascertain the orbit's width: $W = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\alpha}{2\pi \sqrt{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{4}}} \times C_{-1} = 0.00002694 \times C_{-1}$. The narrow discrepancy of $0.0000004 \times C_{-1}$ signifies a highly compact configuration.

This suggests that when two filling-toroidal-orbits superpose, the matter-charge at the intersection is extricated, thus reducing the proton's rest energy from the initial E_{p0} to the measured E_p value.

The center of the proton must be Y_+ corresponding to the unit positive charge, suggesting that the matter-charge rotating on r_p comes from Y_+ of E_p , and the orbit of Y_- part will move closer to the center. However, on the outermost toroidal-orbit of the proton, E_p is insufficient to fill the orbit, and there is no empty-toroidal-orbit available to borrow matter-charge like in the muon structure. Therefore, the magnetic moment contributed by each toroidal-orbit is no longer equal to $1\mu_B$, thereby: $\mu_{Part1} = \frac{E_p}{E_{p0}} \times \sin(45^\circ) \times 4 = \frac{E_p}{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times E_e} \times \sin(45^\circ) \times 4 \approx 2.79354377\mu_B$.

In the structure of the proton, two filling-toroidal-orbits are intersecting perpendicularly. Thus, unlike the orbit radii of the μ_{Part2} of the electron and muon, which are both $\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}$ of the outermost orbit, in the proton, a charge $q = \frac{E_{p0}}{E_e} \times e = \frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times e$ forms a toroidal-orbit at $\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}$ of the $r_{-137 \times 16} = r_{-137} \times \frac{1}{16}$ orbit. The direction of this toroidal-orbit is aligned with r_p . The final contribution to the magnetic moment is: $\mu_{Part2} = \frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \times \frac{4\pi+1}{16} \times \sin(45^\circ)\mu_B$.

There is no empty-toroidal-orbit in protons, hence, we obtain $X = \frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha}$ from the total energy E_{p0} of the three initial toroidal-orbits. Substituting this value into Eq. (S1.7) allows us to derive the orbit of unit charge $\frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{4\pi+1}} \times r_{-1}$ and $\mu_{Part3} = \frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{4\pi+1}}\mu_B$.

Summating the corrected segments, we obtain: $\frac{E_p}{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times E_e} \times \sin(45^\circ) \times 4 + \left(-\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}\right) \times \frac{4\pi+1}{16} \times \sin(45^\circ) + \frac{\alpha^2}{2\pi \sqrt{4\pi+1}} = 2.79284734468\mu_B$. As can be seen, if its unit is not a Bohr magneton (μ_B) but a nuclear magneton (μ_N) as Eq. (S1.1), this is nearly equivalent to

the latest measurement of proton magnetic moment, $2.79284734463(82)\mu_N$ [2].

A conundrum presents itself: should this concordance be dismissed as serendipitous, or does it hint at an intrinsic mechanism dictating the proton's magnetic moment via its toroidal-orbit configuration—a value slightly diminished relative to those of the electron and muon by the ratio of $\frac{E_p}{E_e}$?

Delving deeper into this matter might unveil novel domains. Following our discourse on neutron structures, we will provisionally explore themes relevant to the strong and weak interactions, quarks, and neutrinos.

d. Neutrons

The neutron exhibits a toroidal-orbit structure that is distinct from that of protons and electrons. Among all the particle structures examined, the neutron is the most unique. To elucidate this structure, we derive insights from the neutron's magnetic moment measurement and substantiate our findings with the neutron radius measurement. Here, we present our analytical approach:

The neutron's magnetic moment is empirically determined to be $-1.91304273(45)\mu_N$ [2]. By applying the patterns discerned from the toroidal-orbit framework, we contemplate multiple structural possibilities for the neutron. One plausible arrangement involves segmenting the magnetic moment into three components: $\mu_{Part1} = -\sqrt{2} - \frac{1}{2}$, $\mu_{Part2} = \frac{\alpha}{2\pi}$, and a minute value, $\mu_{Part3} = 0.00000942(45)$. Analogous to the μ_{Part2} value in electron and muon magnetic moments, which is $\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}$, we infer that neutrons also possess a structure characterized by alternating filling and empty-toroidal-orbits.

Delving into the μ_{Part1} component, we postulate its division into three distinct parts. Specifically, two overlapping segments together span a portion of the toroidal-orbit, amounting to $\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$ of its total circumference, collectively contributing a magnetic moment

of $\sqrt{2}$. The remaining part occupies half a filling-toroidal-orbit, contributing a magnetic moment of $\frac{1}{2}$. If neutron's filling-toroidal-orbit r_N has a capacity of $E_N = N \times E_e$, then the energy gap of this orbit should align with $1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}$ of C_N . The existence of a suitable empty-toroidal-orbit, likely r_{-137} or r_{-861} , that matches this gap—and an energy portion on the filling-toroidal-orbit equal to $E_N \times (\sqrt{2} + \frac{1}{2})$ that aligns with the neutron's measured mass—would strongly indicate the neutron's toroidal-orbit structure.

A straightforward calculation suggests that the empty-toroidal-orbit perpendicular to C_N corresponds to the fundamental toroidal-orbit r_{-861} . To determine its width, we modify Eq. (S1.6) by including a 2π coefficient, and we propose a novel hypothesis: the neutron borrows half of the energy from empty-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} , i.e., $E_e \times \frac{\pi}{\alpha}$, to enable movement within the main-toroidal-orbit and form a magnetic moment. Although this assumption is peculiar, it seems to describe a toroid composed of half r_{-861} and half r_n —providing a possible destination for the portion of the matter-charge contributing $\frac{1}{2}$.

While these ideas remain speculative, let us proceed to calculate the capacity of the neutron's filling-toroidal-orbit:

$$N \times E_e \times \left(\sqrt{2} + \frac{1}{2} \right) = E_n + \frac{\pi}{\alpha} \times E_e. \quad (\text{S1.13})$$

Substituting the rest energy $E_n = 939.56542052$ (54) MeV = $1838.683662 \times E_e$ [2], we deduce $N = 1185.445$. This calculation defines the outermost toroidal-orbit of neutrons as orbit r_{-1185} , with a radius:

$$r_{-1185} = \frac{C_{-1}}{2\pi} \times \frac{1}{N} = 0.32574418 \times 10^{-15} \text{m}, \quad (\text{S1.14})$$

in striking concordance with the measured neutron radius of $\sqrt{0.1060_{-0.005}^{+0.007}} \text{fm}$, where $\sqrt{0.1061} = 0.32572995$ [12]. This congruence lends credence to the proposed neutron structure.

In later, we will explore the deuteron's structure and properties. The deuteron, a composite particle of a proton and a neutron, exhibits a magnetic moment

that, when analyzed using the width of r_{-1185} , closely matches empirical values, serving as corroborative evidence.

The neutron structure entails a circumference $C_{-1185} = \frac{C_{-1}}{N}$, with the energy gap length on the ring being $L = C_{-1185} \times \left(1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} \right) = 0.00024707449 \times C_{-1}$. Employing Eq. (S1.6) to ascertain the width of r_{-861} , and factoring in the intersections between filling and empty-toroidal-orbits, yields a width of $W = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}}} \times C_{-1} \times 2 = 0.0002486898 \times C_{-1}$. The negligible discrepancy of $0.0000016 \times C_{-1}$ implies structural stability.

Because the structure of the neutron is unique relative to all other particles, we place the mass formula for the neutron at the end of S1.

Lastly, we scrutinize the μ_{part3} component in the neutron's magnetic moment equation, targeting a value of $\mu_{part3} = 0.00000942$ (45). Unlike the previously examined particles, the neutron hosts both unit positive and negative charges, potentially yielding different outcomes. We seek a formula that matches the numeric target, then explore plausible physical mechanisms consistent with the formula. Among several numeric estimates, we favor the expression $\frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{1}} + \left(\frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \right)^2 \times \sin(45^\circ) = 0.000009429$. Here, the first term is derived by inserting E_e into Eq. (S1.7), representing the electron's unit negative charge contribution within the neutron, while the second term arises from the proton's unit positive charge at the neutron's core, with the $\sin(45^\circ)$ factor reflecting the proton's toroidal-orbit inclination. This yields a four-layered structure.

Ignoring unit charge contributions, the two-term magnetic moment formula $\mu_{(2)}$ is straightforward: $(-\sqrt{2} - \frac{1}{2}) + \frac{\alpha}{2\pi} = -1.91305215$. However, summing the three components yields:

$$\frac{\mu_{n(3)}}{\mu_N} = \left(-\sqrt{2} - \frac{1}{2} \right) + \frac{\alpha}{2\pi} + \left(\frac{\alpha^2}{2\pi} + \left(\frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \right)^2 \times \sin(45^\circ) \right), \quad (\text{S1.15})$$

resulting in a value of -1.9130427236 that is close to the measured value. Nonetheless, only future, more

precise measurements of the neutron's magnetic moment can confirm the physical validity of this formula.

6. Strong and weak interactions

While Equations (S1.1) and (S1.15) successfully deliver numerical approximations for the magnetic moments of protons and neutrons, it raises the intriguing question of why the nuclear magneton μ_N is the chosen unit for their representation, as opposed to the Bohr magneton μ_B . Engaging with this query propels us into the underlying physical phenomena encapsulated within the toroidal-orbit model of particles, catalyzing a progression towards a deeper understanding of the strong and weak nuclear interactions, and potentially shedding light on the elusive nature of quarks, gluons, and neutrinos.

a. Dynamics within hadronic toroidal-orbits

The translation from Bohr magnetons to nuclear magnetons embeds a factor of $\frac{E_e}{E_p}$ into the magnetic moment expressions for protons and neutrons. The normal model for the magnetic moment of a toroidal-orbit, as posited in Eq. (S1.4), intimates that the magnetic moment m is directly proportional to the product of charge q , the speed of light c , and the radius r , giving us $m = \frac{1}{2}qcr = 1\mu_B$. A deviation from our earlier calculation by a factor of $\frac{E_e}{E_p}$ for the proton's magnetic moment implies a modification of one of these variables by the ratio.

Given the measured congruency of Equations (2) and (13) with empirical data regarding proton and neutron radii, we can dismiss alterations in radii. Equally unaltered is the quantity of charge in rotation, as the conversion between energy and charge is a foundational postulate of the matter-charge framework, a principle reinforced through derivations of electromagnetic interactions found in S3. Therefore, we are led to conjecture that the rotation velocity of matter-charge within the proton's toroidal-orbits decreases from c to

$$c \times \frac{E_e}{E_p}.$$

The viable explanations are limited; the most persuasive is predicated upon the constancy of matter-charge velocity at c , if the matter-charge's tangential velocity along the toroidal-orbit is reduced to $c \times \frac{E_e}{E_p}$, then an additional velocity component must exist within the inner diameter of the orbit, orthogonal to the orbital plane. This implies a compound rotational motion for charges on the proton's toroidal-orbit: a primary rotation at velocity $c \times \frac{E_e}{E_p}$ along the principal toroidal-orbit r_p , and a higher velocity secondary rotation— $\sqrt{c^2 - (c \times \frac{E_e}{E_p})^2}$ —perpendicular to the orbital plane, with a diameter determined by Eq. (S1.6).

While this secondary rotation is capable of engendering a notable magnetic moment, the toroidal geometry results in the mutual cancellation of opposing magnetic moments across the orbit. Consequently, although the proton's toroidal-orbits harbor this bi-directional vortex structure, we apprehend only the magnetic moment produced by the primary rotation. The upshot is that the genuine toroidal-orbits of protons and neutrons, if indeed constituted by these dual-rotational vortex structures, necessitate an adjustment of the rotational velocity from c to $c \times \frac{E_e}{E_p}$ in their magnetic moment calculations, effectively translating the computational units from μ_B to μ_N .

In physics, every action prompts a reaction. The inquiry then becomes: what could be the broader physical ramifications of these dual-rotational vortices within hadrons?

b. On strong interactions

The distinct magnetic moment formulations derived earlier point to a fundamental difference in the dynamical behavior of matter-charges within protons, neutrons, electrons, and muons. The dual-rotational vortices hypothesized for the toroidal-orbits of protons and neutrons, in contrast to the singular rotational motion posited for electrons and muons, hint at

disparate underlying physical processes.

Building on the matter-charge hypothesis—which posits the ubiquity of matter-charges in space that can engage with matter-charges within particle toroidal structures—the dual-rotational motion within a toroidal-orbit is theorized to exert an influence on ambient matter-charges. The primary rotation is conjectured to govern the dynamics of these spatial charges, culminating in what is defined as the magnetic field in S3. The secondary rotation, however, is envisioned to drive these charges through the toroid’s center at increased velocities, orthogonal to the toroidal plane, giving rise to a vortex-like configuration encasing the toroid.

When two such toroidal structures with dual-rotational dynamics approach proximity, their surrounding vortex-like formations are likely to interact prior to any physical contact between the toroids themselves. Given the substantial disparity in velocities between the two types of rotation, a novel form of interaction is anticipated to emerge, one that is distinct from electromagnetic interactions yet fundamentally similar in mechanism, influenced by the spatial extent of the vortex-like structures. We propose that these vortex-like formations, engendered by the dual-rotational movement of toroidal-orbits, underlie the physical essence of strong interactions.

Further contemplation on the dual-rotational dynamics suggests more nuanced implications, particularly in relation to particle radii. Electrons and muons, typically regarded as point particles due to the absence of experimentally discernible solid-like structure, are nonetheless modeled with outermost toroidal-orbits in magnetic moment computations. The elusive nature of these charge orbits, despite their role in magnetic moment generation, may stem from the fact that only toroidal-orbits with dual-rotational structure are amenable to size measurements via collisions, with the dual-rotational architecture also conferring enhanced stability.

Within the framework of particle physics, the ra-

tio $\frac{m_e}{m_p}$, representing the electron-to-proton mass, is a constant equating to $\frac{E_e}{E_p}$. The toroidal model posits that the proton’s structure is the epitome of stability, to the extent that even the electron’s structure is thought to incorporate a proton-like entity composed of empty toroidal-orbits. Current understanding fails to elucidate the mechanisms driving the second type of rotation within proton and neutron toroids, and why the velocity of the primary rotation reduces to $c \times \frac{E_e}{E_p}$. Nevertheless, if we consider these phenomena as empirical, several hypotheses emerge:

- Particles engaged in strong interactions are characterized by toroidal structures with dual-rotational dynamics. The calculation of magnetic moments for such particles necessitates the inclusion of the factor $\frac{E_e}{E_p}$.
- The dual-rotational dynamics introduce dual axes of rotation. Perpendicular intersections of two such toroidal-orbits result in each dimension of one toroid corresponding to the alternate dimension of the intersecting toroid, thereby reinforcing structural stability and elucidating the necessity for perpendicular interlocking in many toroidal configurations.
- Within the structures of protons and neutrons, it is plausible for two toroidal-orbits to coexist in the same spatial domain. Analogous to atomic orbital electrons, which can accommodate pairs with opposite spins, a toroidal-orbit with dual-rotational dynamics can house two similar dual toroids, whether of identical matter-charge, such as protons, or differing types, such as π mesons—the latter not contributing to a magnetic moment.

c. On quarks

The discourse on strong interactions necessitates a contemplation of quarks, the fundamental constituents as per the Standard Model. Within this

model, a proton is described as an ensemble of two up quarks and one down quark. Conversely, the particle toroidal-orbit model conceives the proton as a complex of toroidal-orbits locked in perpendicular interlock. Should quarks be an intrinsic component of protons with the potential to repel electrons, their most enigmatic positions would correspond to the loci where toroidal-orbits intertwine perpendicularly.

Prior calculations have yielded the energy associated with the gap length of the toroidal-orbits within the proton: $E_{p0} \times \frac{1}{4} - E_p \times \frac{1}{4}$. Envisioning each toroidal-orbit as a hollow conduit, we deduce that perpendicular interlocking occludes a diminutive section. When such interlocking occurs, the matter-charges traverse this region in tandem, with the primary rotation of one toroid aligning with the secondary rotation of the other. Presuming vector superposition occurs by introducing a $\sqrt{2}$ factor, the sealed segment's corresponding energy is expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(E_{p0} \times \frac{1}{4} - E_p \times \frac{1}{4} \right) \times \sqrt{2} &= 4.1424\text{MeV} \\ &= 2.0712\text{MeV} \times 2, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S1.16})$$

which intriguingly mirrors the estimated mass of a pair of up quarks, with an up quark mass assumed to be $m_u = 2.130 \pm 0.041\text{MeV}/c^2$ [13].

A primary distinction between down and up quarks is a single charge unit. Introducing the matter-charge $|e|$, or energy E_e , into this gap modifies the energy to:

$$\begin{aligned} \left(E_{p0} \times \frac{1}{4} - E_p \times \frac{1}{4} \right) \times \sqrt{2} + 1 \times E_e \\ = E_u \times 2 + 1 \times E_e = 4.65538\text{MeV}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S1.17})$$

corresponding to the down quark value $m_d = 4.675 \pm 0.056\text{MeV}/c^2$ [13].

Apart from conceptual divergence concerning charge, these special locations within the proton architecture resonate with other quintessential properties attributed to quarks, facilitating the direct computation of quark masses—a representation of physical manifestation rather than actual mass. More-

over, this modeling elucidates experimental phenomena pertinent to quarks. The specialized positions brought forth by intersecting toroidal-orbits are not discrete, independent entities, thus eluding direct observation, which aligns with the concept of quark confinement. Structures endowed with dual-rotational attributes are discernible in collisional experiments, consistent with observations from deep inelastic scattering experiments involving protons and electrons, where the deflected electrons imply interaction with a “quark” entity.

Within this innovative framework, up quarks are conceptualized as isolated regions emergent from low-energy environments where toroidal-orbits intersect perpendicularly. Under high-energy conditions, such intersections between foundational toroidal-orbits would result in an entirely isolated domain, encapsulating the toroidal-orbit's entire energy content. The Standard Model acknowledges four additional quarks of higher mass, with these masses interwoven with the basic-toroidal-orbits in the particle toroidal-orbit model as follows:

$$E_s = E_{-137} \times \sqrt{2} = 99.03\text{MeV}, \quad (\text{S1.18a})$$

$$E_c = E_{-861} \times 2 \times \sqrt{2} = 1244.459\text{MeV}, \quad (\text{S1.18b})$$

$$E_t = E_{-861} \times \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 2 \times \sqrt{2} = 170535\text{MeV}, \quad (\text{S1.18c})$$

$$E_b = \frac{E_{p0}}{4} \times 2\pi \times 2 \times \sqrt{2} = 4220.696\text{MeV}. \quad (\text{S1.18d})$$

$\frac{E_{p0}}{4}$, representing the complete energy of a proton's toroidal-orbit, is analogous to a basic-toroidal-orbit. The interrelation among these equations is notable, with computed rest energies reflecting the recognized quark mass values: $m_s = 98.7_{-3.2}^{+4.0}\text{MeV}/c^2$ [12], $m_c = 1.246 \pm 0.023\text{GeV}/c^2$ [14], $m_t = 172.6 \pm 2.5\text{GeV}/c^2$ [15], and $m_b = 4.197_{-0.008}^{+0.008}\text{GeV}/c^2$ [16], underscoring the model's accuracy. Although these quark-like structures cannot be empirically measured, the particle toroidal-orbit model theoretically provides their energetic or mass equivalents.

While quarks are the focus here, gluons may be

associated with the energies characterizing toroidal-orbits and the ensuing vortex-like structures, a topic beyond the scope of this discussion. Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD) stands as a mature theory; our nascent model, despite its simplicity, has exhibited methodological validity and reliability. Both models, despite divergent assumptions and viewpoints, are scientific endeavors targeting the same subject matter. The ensuing challenge lies in seeking avenues for reconciling these frameworks. The matter-charge hypothesis and particle toroidal-orbit model have profoundly influenced core physics concepts, encompassing the nature of fundamental particles, the very essence of energy, charge, mass, and the comprehension of special relativity, quantum mechanics, and the four fundamental interactions. As the toroidal model garners empirical support, especially within verifiable domains, its amalgamation with QCD seems an inevitable progression of scientific inquiry.

d. On weak interactions and neutrinos

Within the context of the particle toroidal-orbit model, weak interactions are intricately linked to the dual dynamics of toroidal-orbits. A prototypical weak interaction is epitomized by β decay, wherein a neutron transmutes into a proton and concurrently emits an electron and an anti-electron neutrino. This process is rigorously explored within the electroweak unification theory's purview. However, from the perspective of the particle toroidal-orbit model, β decay can be interpreted as a transition from a dual-rotational toroidal-orbit to a single-rotational one.

Drawing upon the Standard Model's interpretation of weak interactions, the crux of β decay is the transmutation of a neutron's down quark into an up quark [17]. In our framework, the up quark is conceived as a closed structure arising from the interlocking of dual-rotational toroidal-orbits, while the down quark is envisaged as this structure supplemented by a quantum of charge matter-equivalent

to $|e|$. Consequently, the down-to-up quark metamorphosis would entail the dismantling of the down quark's dual-rotational structure, engendering an electron characterized by a singular rotational modality and the up quark.

The electron stemming from the down quark's decay cannot conserve both rotational directions; hence, one such rotational sense must be preserved while the other dissipates. Nonetheless, in a closed system, angular momentum conservation precludes such rotation from vanishing into the void. It follows that a structure must exist, entailing a minimal quantum of matter-charge, which is ejected perpendicular to the neutron's main-toroidal-orbit and antipodal to the electron's trajectory. This departing structure is postulated as a neutrino in the new particle model.

Thus, while electroweak unification theory postulates quark flavor change as indicative of weak interactions, our particle toroidal-orbit model construes it as a transition involving either the change from a dual-rotational toroidal-orbit structure to a single-rotational one or vice versa, encompassing the gamut of weak interactions.

In our model, mass does not pertain to the Higgs mechanism but is addressed in the subsequent section on the Higgs particle, with a comprehensive elucidation in S2. This explication provides insights into the mass-bearing nature of neutrinos. The following hypotheses are posited based on the above narrative:

- During β decay, the dual-rotational dynamics of the down quark unravel, simultaneously birthing neutrinos and electrons. Momentum conservation dictates that these particles elicit movement in divergent directions from the originating neutron.
- The neutron's toroidal-orbit imposes a specific directional flow of matter-charge through its central axis. Thus, in β decay, the ejection path of negatively charged electrons is predetermined. The seminal Wu experiment [18], which ana-

lyzed the directional emission of electrons during β decay using cryogenically cooled, polarized cobalt-60 nuclei, elucidated that electrons preferentially emerge in a direction opposing the neutron's spin angular momentum, suggesting a definite ejection path for neutrinos as well. With these particles' spatial configurations at our disposal, we can endeavor to re-interpret the Wu experiments, including the parity anomalies and the observed violation of parity in weak interactions.

- Given that electrons and anti-electron neutrinos originate from the same structure during β decay, it is plausible that anti-electron neutrinos share the same toroidal-orbit structure as electrons. However, the electron orbit inherits a significant quantum of matter-charge, or specifically, the toroidal-orbit rotating in congruence with the neutron's orbit acquires a unit charge and the preponderance of matter-charge, culminating in an electron, while the counterpart transforms into an anti-electron neutrino. Similarly, anti-muon neutrinos and anti-tau neutrinos may possess toroidal-orbit configurations analogous to those of muons and tau particles, respectively, accounting for the trio of neutrino types.
- A cursory analysis of the magnetic moment formulae for these particles indicates that the type and rotational direction of matter-charge on each orbit tier are immutable and correlate to the sign of each term in the magnetic moment equations. Thus, not only are neutrinos inherently left-handed, but each fermion's orbital tier exhibits a defined chirality. However, the concept of a particle's spin angular momentum should not be conflated with the chirality of its orbits. The former derives from the matter-charge linked to the kinetic energy component of the corresponding particle, while the latter stems

from the matter-charge associated with the rest energy component. S4 delves into the origins of a particle's spin angular momentum, clarifying its relationship to the spin magnetic moment.

7. The structures and attributes of more particles

In this section, we intend to expand the application of the basic-toroidal-orbits framework and the toroidal-orbit width formula delineated in Eq. (S1.6). Our focus is to scrutinize the toroidal-orbit structures of an extended gamut of particles, endeavoring to unearth their governing universal principles and compute their respective attributes.

The first group of particles under consideration encompasses a trio of mesons: π , K , and η . Leveraging the experimentally ascertained radii and the established masses of the π and K mesons, we are poised to deduce their toroidal-orbit structures with a degree of simplicity. The structural configurations of the toroidal-orbits for π , K , and η mesons are observed to adhere to analogous patterns. Furthermore, given the diverse manifestations of the K meson, encompassing the antiparticle pairs K^+ and K^- , as well as the electrically neutral K^0 and $\bar{K}^0$, a succinct exposition on antiparticles within the confines of the matter-charge hypothesis and particle toroidal-orbit model is warranted, utilizing the K meson as an illustrative example.

The second group of particles we turn our attention to comprises η' , $\phi(1020)$, D , $\omega(782)$, ρ , B , J/ψ , and χ_{c0} . These particles, which are also mesonic by classification, exhibit higher energy levels than those encompassed in the initial group. While only the masses of these mesons are measured, the discernible uniformity in their toroidal-orbit structures enables us to postulate their configurations. Additionally, we shall take the opportunity to cast a cursory glance at the peculiarities of flavor-specific particles (e.g., B_S^0 , $B_C^\pm$) as well as particles in excited states (e.g., $J/\psi(2S)$), with the aim of delineating their distinc-

tive traits.

Our discourse extends to the third group of particles, the baryons, inclusive of Λ , Ξ , Ω , and Σ . The availability of both the measured masses and a preliminary understanding of their magnetic moments permits a more granular exploration of their structures. Consequently, we will articulate their particle structure formulae and endeavor to advance calculative formulae for their magnetic moments.

The fourth group of particles includes the tau leptons, Higgs boson, W bosons, and Z bosons. Their commonality lies in that these particles do not directly participate in the strong interaction. However, the products of their decay processes include particles that are involved in the strong interaction.

a. π mesons and the particle structure formula

Muons are composed of one filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} and two empty-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , while π mesons consist of one empty-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} and two filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} . Our thought process is as follows.

The first step is to conjecture the toroidal-orbit composition of the π meson, i.e., which filling and empty-toroidal-orbits make it up.

First, determine its filling-toroidal-orbits:

A particle's rest energy originates from its filling-toroidal-orbits, so the energy of the filling-toroidal-orbits making up π mesons should be greater than its rest energy but not by too much. From $E_{\pi^\pm} = 139.57021\text{MeV} = 273.13 \times E_e$ [19], it is hypothesized that the structure of $\pi^\pm$ mesons includes two filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , for $E_{-137} \times 2 = 274 \times E_e$.

Next, determine its empty-toroidal-orbits:

According to the characteristics of toroidal-orbit structures, the capacity of a toroidal-orbit is inversely proportional to its radius $r_{-1} = 386.15(4) \times 10^{-15}\text{m}$. By the multiple of the toroidal-orbit capacity to E_e , we can obtain the toroidal-orbit radius and vice versa.

The measured radius of $\pi^\pm$ is $r_{\pi^\pm} = 0.655(4) \times$

10^{-15}m [20], indicating that the main-toroidal-orbit of $\pi^\pm$ has a capacity around $\frac{386.15}{0.655} \times E_e = 589 \times E_e$. And for $\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} - \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 2 = 586.95$, indicating that the $\pi^\pm$ particle possibly has an empty-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} , which is recombined to create a stable structure after being filled with two filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , consistent with our judgment on its filling-toroidal-orbits.

Therefore, it is conjectured that π mesons are particles formed by the fusion of two filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} and one empty-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} .

Thus, the toroidal-orbit radius formula for π mesons is likely:

$$r_{\pi^\pm} = \frac{r_{-1}}{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} - \frac{E_{\pi^\pm}}{E_e}} = 0.65684 \times 10^{-15}\text{m}. \quad (\text{S1.19})$$

The second step is to determine the spatial structure of the π meson.

As previously introduced, when a proton reorganizes from three initial toroidal-orbits into the final interlocking toroidal structure, there is an energy loss at the points of interlocking. A similar situation should occur in the formation process of the π meson. The initial toroidal-orbits of the π meson are a filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} and two empty-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , its initial energy being $E_{-137} \times 2$, and the final energy being E_π . The energy difference $E_{-137} \times 2 - E_\pi$ corresponds to the energy at the interlocking positions on the main-toroidal-orbit of the π meson. Knowing the capacity, radius, and circumference of the π meson's main-toroidal-orbit, it's easy to find the length of the energy gap. If there is a basic-toroidal-orbit whose width perfectly relates to this energy gap length, we've found a toroidal-orbit structure consistent with the π meson's mass and circumference that also doesn't generate an observable spin magnetic moment—simply needing the main-toroidal-orbit to contain both Y_+ and Y_- . This is likely the toroidal-orbit structure of the π meson.

In the formulae below, we will place the length of the particle energy gap on the left side of the formula. The energy loss is $E_{-137} \times 2 - E_\pi$, the proportion of the gap on the toroidal-orbit is $\frac{E_{-137} \times 2 - E_\pi}{E_{-861} - E_{-137} \times 2}$, and the

total length of the gap part is: $\frac{E_{-137} \times 2 - E_\pi}{E_{-861} - E_{-137} \times 2} \times C_\pi$, which can be simplified to: $\frac{\frac{2}{\alpha} - \frac{E_\pi}{E_e}}{(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} - \frac{E_\pi}{E_e})^2} \times C_{-1}$.

After a simple search for a match, the following two formulae can be obtained:

$$\frac{\frac{2}{\alpha} - \frac{E_\pi}{E_e}}{(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} - \frac{E_\pi}{E_e})^2} \times C_{-1} = \left(\frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \times C_{-1} \right) \times \alpha \times \frac{1}{\pi}, \quad (\text{S1.20a})$$

$$\frac{\frac{2}{\alpha} - \frac{E_\pi}{E_e}}{(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} - \frac{E_\pi}{E_e})^2} \times C_{-1} = \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{E_{-861}}{E_e}}} \times C_{-1} \right) \times \sqrt{2}. \quad (\text{S1.20b})$$

In Eq. (S1.20a), $E_\pi = 139.57407\text{MeV}$. And the measured mass of $\pi^\pm$ is $139.57021(14)\text{MeV}/c^2$.

In Eq. (S1.20b), $E_\pi = 134.95462\text{MeV}$. And $m_{\pi^0} = 134.9768(5)\text{MeV}/c^2$ [8].

The E_π values in these two formulae are very close to the measured values of π mesons. However, a careful examination of the physical significance on the right side of the formulae is needed to determine whether we can trust they represent the structural formulae, or mass calculation formulae, for $\pi^\pm$ and π^0 mesons.

The third step is to interpret the physical meaning of the particle structural formula.

The right side of Eq. (S1.20b) (corresponding to π^0) is very clear; it corresponds to a basic-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} that intersects the energy gap of the main-toroidal-orbit at a 45° angle. This structure is very similar to that of a muon, but the main-toroidal-orbit intersects with the inclined toroidal-orbit only once.

However, the right side of Eq. (S1.20a) has some peculiarities; its structure is not about the width formula of a toroidal-orbit but rather involves embedding a basic-toroidal-orbit that could be denoted as $r_{-861 \times 137}$ into the gap of the $\pi^\pm$ main toroidal-orbit. The right side equals $\frac{C_{-861} \times \alpha}{\pi}$, which is also the diameter of the toroidal-orbit $E_{-861} \times \alpha$, a higher energy toroidal-orbit formed on the basic-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} . This too is a stable structure.

Unlike particles such as electrons and protons,

the Y_+ and Y_- corresponding to the main-toroidal-orbit of a π meson do not enter toroidal-orbits of different radii but share one, so its main-toroidal-orbit does not produce an observable spin magnetic moment as with electrons and protons. However, this doesn't mean that these Y_+ and Y_- overlap in space. Because mesons participate in the strong interaction, the main-toroidal-orbit possesses a dual-rotation structure, where the corresponding Y_+ and Y_- form symmetric, intertwined but non-intersecting helixes within the toroidal-orbit (comparable to the photon structure introduced in later), rather than the layered toroidal structure seen in electrons and protons.

b. *K mesons and antiparticles*

In addition to the π mesons, we also know the measured radius of K mesons, which helps to confirm their toroidal-orbit structures. However, unlike the π mesons, K mesons not only consist of the antiparticle pairs K^+ and K^- but also include the electrically neutral K^0 and its antiparticle $\bar{K}^0$. Therefore, after introducing the toroidal-orbit structures of K mesons, we will briefly discuss the concept of antiparticles in the new model.

Compared to muons, K mesons have an additional filling-toroidal-orbit, r_{-137} , meaning their initial toroidal-orbits include a filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} , a filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-137} , and two empty-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} . The analysis method for these particles is the same:

For K mesons, the heavier ones are $K^\pm$, with a measured mass of $493.677(16)\text{MeV}/c^2$ [8], or $E_e \times 966$. Since the energy of the particle's initial toroidal-orbits should be slightly higher than the particle's final energy, and $E_{-861} + E_{-137} = E_e \times 998$, we speculate that the initial filling-toroidal-orbits of K mesons include a filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} and a filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-137} .

Considering the radius of K mesons, with a mea-

sured value of $0.560(31) \times 10^{-15}\text{m}$ [8], and $\frac{386.15}{0.56} = 689$ as well as $\frac{E_{K^\pm}}{E_e} - \frac{2}{\alpha} = 692.03$, it is natural to assume that in the structure of K mesons, there are also two empty-toroidal-orbits, hence the main-toroidal-orbit's capacity is $E_{K^\pm} - 2 \times E_{-137}$. Its circumference is $C_{-1} \times \frac{1}{\frac{E_{K^\pm}}{E_e} - \frac{2}{\alpha}}$.

Thus, we initially assume K mesons to be composed of four toroidal-orbits, including two empty-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} .

Next, we determine the length of the energy gap. The energy lost by K mesons from the initial toroidal-orbits to form stable orbits is: $E_{-861} + E_{-137} - E_K$. The length of the energy gap on the toroidal-orbit is: $\frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\alpha} - \frac{E_K}{E_e}}{(\frac{E_K}{E_e} - \frac{2}{\alpha})^2} \times C_{-1}$.

Next, search for a suitable width of the basic-toroidal-orbit, and discard the C_{-1} that exist on both sides of the formula, we get the simplified particle structure formula:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\alpha} - \frac{E_K}{E_e}}{(\frac{E_K}{E_e} - \frac{2}{\alpha})^2} = \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{E_{-861}}{E_e}} \times \sqrt{2}} \right) \times 2, \quad (\text{S1.21a})$$

$$\frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\alpha} - \frac{E_K}{E_e}}{(\frac{E_K}{E_e} - \frac{2}{\alpha})^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{E_{-137}}{E_e}}}. \quad (\text{S1.21b})$$

In equation (S1.21a), $E_K = 493.713\text{MeV}$, while the measured mass of $K^\pm$ is $493.677(16)\text{MeV}/c^2$.

In equation (S1.21b), $E_K = 497.597\text{MeV}$, while the measured mass of K^0 is $497.611(13)\text{MeV}/c^2$ [8]. The calculated values match the measured values.

Therefore, if this is the calculation formula for the mass of K mesons, then the following formula represents the radius of $K^\pm$ mesons:

$$r_{K^\pm} = \frac{r_{-1}}{\frac{E_{K^\pm}}{E_e} - \frac{2}{\alpha}} = 0.5580 \times 10^{-15}\text{m}, \quad (\text{S1.22})$$

which is very consistent with the measured value.

Lastly, we need to check the details of these formulae and compare them with the characteristics of the particles.

Equation (S1.21b) has a clear physical meaning. The left side of the formula is still the length of the energy gap in the main-toroidal-orbit, while the right side corresponds to the width of the basic-toroidal-orbit r_{-137} , with a single intersection point. This represents the structure of the K^0 meson. However, it should be noted that both $K^\pm$ and K^0 initially contain two empty-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , which are considered when calculating the main-toroidal-orbit's capacity, thereby matching the measured toroidal-orbit radius. Thus, a corresponding $|E_{-137} \times 2|$ of Y_+ and Y_- are included in the vertical toroidal-orbits of K mesons, filling the vertical orbits of K^0 perfectly.

Reviewing the structure in Eq. (S1.21a) reveals additional insights. First, a coefficient of $\frac{1}{2}$ is added on the left side, indicating two intersection points on the main-toroidal-orbit. Second, the appearance of the coefficient $\sqrt{2}$ under the square root on the right side suggests the vertical intersection of the toroidal-orbit with two r_{-861} orbits, potentially indicating a strong tendency for $K^\pm$ mesons to participate in weak interactions, a notable characteristic of K mesons. The most important aspect is the special coefficient 2 on the right side of the formula.

If Eq. (S1.21a) indeed represents the structure of $K^\pm$ mesons, the coefficient 2 may correspond to another characteristic of K mesons, namely neutral K meson oscillations.

The Standard Model explains this phenomenon as a result of weak interactions allowing K^0 and $\bar{K}^0$ to convert into each other through two intermediate states, where the particles can exchange via virtual intermediate state W bosons. This mixing leads to two new quantum states—long-lived K_L^0 and short-lived K_S^0 , each with different lifespans and slightly different masses, closer to $K^\pm$ rather than K^0 .

However, according to the particle toroidal-orbit model, the reason might be the presence of two E_{-861} capacity toroidal-orbits running parallel through the main-toroidal-orbit of $K^\pm$ mesons, rather than one. While the stability mechanism is still unknown, this

configuration could form four different structures, matching the four K mesons with very similar masses: K^+ , K^- , K_L^0 , and K_S^0 . The components of K mesons are:

- K^+ and K^- : Both have symmetric spirals of Y_+ and Y_- in their horizontal main-toroidal-orbit and vertical orbits, with K^+ carrying an extra unit positive charge, and K^- carrying a unit negative charge, making them antiparticles of each other.
- K^0 and $\bar{K}^0$: In their horizontal main-toroidal-orbits, equal amounts of Y_+ and Y_- exist as symmetric spirals, but in their vertical orbits, the amount of $|E_{-137}|$ of Y_+ and Y_- form a layered structure. If K^0 's outer vertical orbit carries Y_+ , the corresponding Y_- will be in its inner orbit, and vice versa for $\bar{K}^0$, making them also a pair of antiparticles.
- K_L^0 and K_S^0 : With two vertical toroidal-orbits in $K^\pm$, oscillations between K^0 and $\bar{K}^0$ could result in Y_+ and Y_- from both entering the same orbit, a more stable configuration, or different orbits, a less stable configuration. Their rest masses are expected to be close to $K^\pm$, not K^0 and $\bar{K}^0$, explaining K_L^0 and K_S^0 .

This explains the distinctions among the six forms of K mesons in the new model.

Previously, we did not specifically discuss antiparticles because, under the matter-charge hypothesis, for particles with a hierarchical toroidal structure, simply swapping the constituting Y_+ and Y_- yields its antiparticle, including electrically neutral neutrons. For particles with both Y_+ and Y_- in the same orbit, like π^0 or photons discussed in later, swapping Y_+ and Y_- has no effect, making it its own antiparticle. However, particles like K^0 are special due to their vertical toroidal-orbits' layered structure, accommodating Y_+ and Y_- , thus K mesons contain two sets of antiparticles.

c. η mesons

According to the particle toroidal-orbit model, the properties of a particle are closely linked to its structure. Thus, the more attribute information we can obtain, the easier it is to determine the particle's toroidal-orbit structure. However, based on patterns summarized from analyzed particles, even if we only have the particle's measured mass, it's still possible to speculate on the particle's toroidal-orbit structure. Take η mesons, for example.

Its mass measurement value is $547.865 \pm 0.031 \pm 0.062 \text{MeV}/c^2$ [21], which can be converted to $E_e \times 1072$, slightly less than $E_{-861} + E_{-137} \times 2 = E_e \times 1135$. Therefore, it is speculated that its initial toroids include one filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} and two filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} . The energy loss during the formation of η mesons would then be $E_{-861} + E_{-137} \times 2 - E_\eta$.

Next, referencing the characteristics of the toroidal-orbits of π mesons and K mesons, and assuming that η mesons also contain two empty-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , the circumference of the main-toroidal-orbit of η mesons would be $\frac{1}{\frac{E_\eta}{E_e} - \frac{2}{\alpha}}$.

Based on this information, a particle structure formula is established and a matching structure is found:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} + \frac{2}{\alpha} - \frac{E_\eta}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{E_\eta}{E_e} - \frac{2}{\alpha}\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}}. \quad (\text{S1.23})$$

The right side of the formula has a very clear physical significance, corresponding exactly to the width of the basic-toroidal-orbit r_{-137} . Solving the formula yields $E_\eta = 547.759 \text{MeV}$, which is extremely close to its measured mass value. Therefore, η mesons are imagined as being formed by merging one filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} , two filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , and two empty-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} together, with the main-toroidal-orbit's capacity being $E_\eta - E_{-137} \times 2$, and a basic-toroidal-orbit r_{-137} intersecting perpendicularly for a

stable structure. Its radius should be:

$$r_\eta = \frac{r_{-1}}{\frac{E_\eta}{E_e} - \frac{2}{\alpha}} = 0.4840 \times 10^{-15} \text{m}. \quad (\text{S1.24})$$

d. η' mesons

Although we lack measured radii for η mesons to verify our model, the consistent patterns observed and the application of the basic-toroidal-orbit and toroidal-orbit width formula lend credence to the idea that η mesons, much like π and K mesons, contain two empty-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} . The capacity of their main-toroidal-orbit is their rest energy minus $2 \times E_{-137}$, leading to structural formulae on the left side that display nearly identical patterns. The calculated masses also align closely with the measured values. Interestingly, this pattern ceases to hold as particle energies increase, with more particles' main-toroidal-orbits showing a direct connection to the basic-toroidal-orbits, linking the gaps in the main-toroidal-orbits to the width of the basic-toroidal-orbits. This has led us to propose potential structural formulae for these particles based on their measured masses.

Additionally, as the rest energy of particles increases, some particle structures appear to exhibit a multiplicative relationship with the basic-toroidal-orbits, a mechanism we suspect to be similar to that found in electron sublayers (see S4). However, we have not delved into the details and corresponding physical meanings of this aspect.

Given the measured mass of η' mesons at $957.78 \pm 0.06 \text{MeV}/c^2$ [8] or $E_e \times 1874.33$, we speculate that their initial toroidal-orbits might consist of two filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-861} and two filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , totaling $E_e \times 1996.12$ —resulting in an energy loss of $E_e \times 121.79$ during particle formation. Another possibility might be one filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} and eight filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , totaling $E_e \times 1957.31$ —with an energy loss of $E_e \times 82.98$, slightly less than the first scenario.

Opting for the latter possibility and applying the basic-toroidal-orbit and toroidal-orbit width formula, we derive the following structural formula:

$$\frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 8 - \frac{E_{\eta'}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 2\right)^2} = \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}}}\right) \times \sqrt{2}. \quad (\text{S1.25})$$

This formula paints a clear picture—two perpendicular basic-toroidal-orbits r_{-861} intersecting obliquely with a main-toroidal-orbit of capacity $E_{-861} \times 2$, similar in spatial structure to that of muons. Solving for $E_{\eta'}$ yields 957.77326MeV , nearly identical to the measured value.

However, due to the following reasons, we cannot yet confirm this as the definitive structure for η' mesons:

- First, the structure of mathematical formula is mutable. For instance, the above formula could be adjusted to $\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} + \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 8 - \frac{E_{\eta'}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 2\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 2}}$, which represent two perpendicular toroidal-orbits of capacity $E_{-861} \times 2$, changing the depiction and potentially the properties described. Even if a particle's structural formula aligns with its measured mass and has a clear toroidal-orbit structure, further examination from multiple dimensions is needed to ensure the formula's structure matches all particle attributes.
- Second, we cannot fully trust structures inferred solely from particle mass measurements. The small discrepancies between the masses derived from structural formulas and the actual measured values indicate unacknowledged mechanisms at play.
- Most importantly, the toroidal-orbit width formula, Eq. (S1.6), remains empirical. The dynamical mechanisms underlying the entire particle toroidal-orbit model have yet to be elucidated, and integration with the Standard Model's existing findings is incomplete.

Hence, significant work remains to ascertain the detailed structures of η' mesons and other mesons. Although we provide structural formulae clearly related to corresponding particles and can calculate their mass and radius, using a unified method, these are, for now, merely possibilities.

e. $\phi(1020)$ mesons

For the $\phi(1020)$ mesons, with a measured mass of $1019.461 \pm 0.016 \text{MeV}/c^2$ [8] or $E_e \times 1995.035$, it's conjectured that their initial toroidal-orbit structure could consist of two filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-861} and two r_{-137} , amounting to $E_e \times 1996.18$ —resulting in a minimal energy loss of $E_e \times 1.08$.

Assuming that the main-toroidal-orbit capacity of $\phi(1020)$ mesons is also a multiple of the basic-toroidal-orbit, and similar to protons, they exhibit an overlapping structure, a structural formula can be deduced when the main-toroidal-orbit capacity is $E_{-137} \times 8$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{1}{2} \times \left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 2 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 2 - \frac{E_\phi}{E_e} \right)}{\left(\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 8 \right)^2} \\ = \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}}} \right) \times \sqrt{2} \times \frac{1}{8^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S1.26})$$

This results in an E_ϕ of 1019.47663MeV , matching the actual measured value precisely.

If this structural formula is considered accurate, there would be an overlay of toroidal-orbits at the position of the main-toroidal-orbit. It's also conceivable that the main-toroidal-orbit's capacity could be $E_{-137} \times 16$. Although it's currently challenging to choose between these two possibilities, it's suspected that at such energy levels, overlapping toroidal-orbits might be more feasible than halving the toroidal-orbit radius. Given the unclear mechanisms involved, the final factor of $\frac{1}{8^2}$ hasn't been analytically resolved, and this ambiguity extends to subsequent particle structural formulae as well.

f. D mesons

For the $D^\pm$ and D^0 mesons, their measured masses are respectively $1869.66 \pm 0.05 \text{MeV}/c^2$ for $D^\pm$ and $1864.84 \pm 0.05 \text{MeV}/c^2$ for D^0 [8], translating to $E_e \times 3658.83$ and $E_e \times 3649.4$. These values are slightly less than twice the initial toroidal-orbit of a proton: $E_{p0} \times 2 = E_e \times \frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times 2 = 3718.2 \times E_e$. It is speculated that their initial toroidal-orbits comprise four filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-861} and two filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , with the difference attributed to energy loss.

Assuming the main-toroidal-orbit capacity of D mesons is $E_{-861} \times 6$, the following structural formulae can be derived:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times 2 - \frac{E_{D^\pm}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 6 \right)^2} = \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}}} \right) \times 2 \times \frac{1}{6^2}, \quad (\text{S1.27a})$$

$$\frac{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times 2 - \frac{E_{D^0}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 6 \right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \times \frac{1}{2\pi} \times \frac{1}{6^2}. \quad (\text{S1.27b})$$

This results in $E_{D^\pm} = 1869.98836 \text{MeV}/c^2$ and $E_{D^0} = 1864.96441 \text{MeV}/c^2$, which align precisely with the actual measured values. The right side of Eq. (S1.27a) is notably neater but includes an additional coefficient of 2, suggesting a possible reason for the neutral D meson oscillations similar to those observed with K mesons.

g. $\omega(782)$ mesons

For the $\omega(782)$ mesons, their measured mass is $782.66 \pm 0.13 \text{MeV}/c^2$ [8], slightly less than $E_{137} \times 12$. Assuming their initial toroidal-orbit structure consists of 12 filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , with the main-toroidal-orbit's capacity also being $E_{-137} \times 12$, the fol-

lowing structural formula can be derived:

$$\frac{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 12 - \frac{E_\omega}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 12\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times \sqrt{2}}}. \quad (\text{S1.28})$$

This yields $E_\omega = 782.66189\text{MeV}/c^2$, aligning precisely with the actual measured value.

h. ρ mesons

For the $\rho^\pm$ and ρ^0 mesons, the Particle Data Group (PDG) reports their masses as $775.26 \pm 0.23\text{MeV}/c^2$ and $775.11 \pm 0.34\text{MeV}/c^2$ [8], respectively. If we also consider them as particles formed by 12 filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , we can derive the following two structural formulae:

$$\frac{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 12 - \frac{E_{\rho^\pm}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 12\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \times \frac{1}{4\pi}, \quad (\text{S1.29a})$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 12 - \frac{E_{\rho^0}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 12\right)^2} = \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \times \sqrt{2}}} \right) \times \sqrt{2}. \quad (\text{S1.29b})$$

These calculations yield $E_{\rho^\pm} = 776.44765\text{MeV}$ and $E_{\rho^0} = 775.26197\text{MeV}$.

The $\omega(782)$ mesons and ρ mesons have very close masses, and even their initial toroidal-orbit structures consist of twelve basic-toroidal-orbits r_{137} . Furthermore, the structure on the left side of their formulae is also the same—indicating they possess the same or similar main-toroidal-orbits. In contrast, the initial toroidal-orbit structure of π mesons is precisely two filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} and one empty-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} . Therefore, it's conceivable that the initial toroidal-orbit structure and the final toroidal-orbit configuration of the $\omega(782)$ mesons and ρ mesons determine their primary decay products to be π mesons. Observing their structure, one can find that on the right side of the $\omega(782)$ mesons' structural formula, there's a component $\frac{1}{\alpha} \times \sqrt{2}$, which may be the reason

why the number of π mesons in the decay products of $\omega(782)$ is one more than that of ρ mesons.

It can be seen that, whether in terms of the understanding of particle structure or other aspects, the new model and the traditional QCD approach have different ways of thinking.

i. B mesons

For the $B^\pm$ mesons, their measured mass is $5279.34 \pm 0.12\text{MeV}/c^2$ [8], equivalent to $E_e \times 10331.41 = E_{-861} \times 11.999$, compellingly suggesting an association of $B^\pm$ mesons with 12 r_{-861} toroidal-orbits. The B^0 mesons have a measured mass of $5279.66 \pm 0.12\text{MeV}/c^2$ [8], very close to that of $B^\pm$ mesons. This leads to the following structural formulae:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 12 - \frac{E_{B^\pm}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 12\right)^2} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} \right) \times \frac{1}{(4\pi + 1) \times (2\pi)} \times \frac{1}{12^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S1.30a})$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 12 - \frac{E_{B^0}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 12\right)^2} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha}}} \right) \times \frac{1}{(4\pi + 1) \times (2\pi)} \times \frac{1}{12^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S1.30b})$$

The results are $B^\pm = 5279.33866\text{MeV}$ and $B^0 = 5279.65988\text{MeV}$, nearly identical to their measured values. Although these formulae reintroduce a term previously seen in the magnetic moment formulae for μ_{Part4} of electrons and muons, $\frac{1}{(4\pi+1) \times (2\pi)}$, which is not yet well explained, the inclination is to accept these formulae as representing the structures of $B^\pm$ and B^0 mesons.

Moreover, B mesons possess two other flavors, B_S^0 with a measured mass of $5366.92 \pm 0.10\text{MeV}/c^2$ [8], slightly higher than $B^\pm$ but less than $E_{-137} \times 2$, and

$B_C^\pm$ with a measured mass of $6274.47 \pm 0.32 \text{MeV}/c^2$ [8], higher than $B^\pm$ but less than $E_{-861} \times 2$. Assuming B_S^0 and $B_C^\pm$ acquire additional filling-toroidal-orbits, two r_{-137} for B_S^0 and two r_{-861} plus two r_{-137} for $B_C^\pm$, yields the following formulae:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 12 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 2 - \frac{E_{B_S^0}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 12\right)^2} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha}}} \right) \times \sqrt{2} \times \frac{1}{12^2}, \quad (\text{S1.31a}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 12 + \frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 2 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 2 - \frac{E_{B_C^\pm}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 12\right)^2} \\ &= \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\alpha}{2\pi \sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times \sqrt{2}}} \right) \times 2 \times \frac{1}{12^2}. \quad (\text{S1.31b}) \end{aligned}$$

These calculations result in $E_{B_S^0} = 5366.67655 \text{MeV}$ and $E_{B_C^\pm} = 6274.57600 \text{MeV}$, which raises the question of whether these formulae accurately represent the structures of the two flavors of B mesons.

j. J/ψ mesons

The J/ψ meson's measured mass is $3096.900 \pm 0.006 \text{MeV}/c^2$ [8], which is slightly less than the sum of three E_{p0} and four E_{-137} . Therefore, it's hypothesized that the initial toroidal-orbit structure of J/ψ mesons consists of 6 filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-861} and 7 filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , with an initial energy of $E_e \times \left(\frac{12\pi+7}{\alpha}\right)$.

If the main-toroidal-orbit's capacity is $E_{p0} + E_{-861}$, that is, $E_e \times \left(\frac{6\pi+1}{\alpha}\right)$, the following structural formula can be derived:

$$\frac{\frac{12\pi+7}{\alpha} - \frac{E_{J/\psi}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{6\pi+1}{\alpha}\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 32}}. \quad (\text{S1.32})$$

This results in $E_{J/\psi} = 3096.9111 \text{MeV}$.

J/ψ is also known as $J/\psi(1S)$, representing the ground state of this particle. Its excited

state, $J/\psi(2S)$, has a measured mass of $3686.10 \pm 0.06 \text{MeV}/c^2$ [8], which is approximately $E_e \times 7213.5$, slightly less than the sum of three E_{p0} and two E_{-861} energies, equal to $E_{-861} \times 8 + E_{-137} \times 3 = E_e \times 7299.1$.

If the main-toroidal-orbit's capacity for $J/\psi(2S)$ is consistent with that of $J/\psi(1S)$, namely $E_e \times \left(\frac{6\pi+1}{\alpha}\right)$, the following structural formula can be derived:

$$\frac{\frac{16\pi+3}{\alpha} - \frac{E_{J/\psi(2S)}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{6\pi+1}{\alpha}\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \times \frac{1}{2\pi} \times \frac{1}{8}, \quad (\text{S1.33})$$

this yields $E_{J/\psi(2S)} = 3686.24943 \text{MeV}$.

k. χ_{c0} mesons

The χ_{c0} meson, within the context of the Standard Model, is considered an excited state of the J/ψ particle due to its placement in a different quantum state. Despite both originating from the same type of charm-anticharm quark pair, the χ_{c0} can be seen as a distinct particle from the J/ψ in certain contexts.

In the particle toroidal-orbit model, given the measured mass of the χ_{c0} as $3414.71 \pm 0.30 \text{MeV}/c^2$ [8] or $\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 7.76$, it is hypothesized that the initial toroidal-orbit structure of this particle consists of 8 r_{-861} . Assuming the main-toroidal-orbit capacity of the χ_{c0} particle is the same as that of the $J/\psi(1S)$ and $J/\psi(2S)$, which is $E_e \times \left(\frac{6\pi+1}{\alpha}\right)$, no feasible particle structure formula was found. However, by assuming its main-toroidal-orbit capacity to be $E_{-861} \times 4$, the following structural formula for the particle can be derived:

$$\frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 8 - \frac{E_{\chi_{c0}}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 4\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 8}}. \quad (\text{S1.34})$$

This results in $E_{\chi_{c0}} = 3413.54598 \text{MeV}$. Thus, the χ_{c0} and the J/ψ should possess different radii.

l. Λ baryons

Next, we will briefly discuss the Λ , Ξ , Ω , and Σ particles, which are also classified as hyperons. Com-

pared to the baryons protons and neutrons, their significant characteristic is their much shorter lifespans. This significantly increases the difficulty of directly measuring their properties, such as the electric charge radius. Furthermore, although we haven't reached the precision in measuring the magnetic moments of protons and neutrons, we have obtained approximate values for the magnetic moments of these hyperons. Therefore, based on their measured masses, we can attempt to construct particle structural formulae, explore possible configurations of their toroidal-orbit structures, and, using the approximate values of their magnetic moments, deduce the spatial configurations of these toroidal-orbits. In general, unless we encounter an exceptionally unique structure like that of the neutron (which borrows energy from empty-toroidal-orbits), we should be able to obtain a preliminary image of these particles.

In our examination of these hyperons, we have only discussed some key characteristics and have not been able to propose a clear and definitive structural model as we have for protons and neutrons. We are looking forward to future research that will delve deeper into the structural details of these particles.

Next, we will briefly delve into the Λ baryon. The measured mass of the Λ baryon is $1115.683 \pm 0.006 \text{ MeV}/c^2$ [8], or $E_e \times 2183.337$, or $E_{-137} \times 15.933$. Assuming the initial toroidal-orbit structure of the Λ particle consists of 16 basic-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} , we obtain the following structural formula:

$$\frac{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 16 - \frac{E_\Lambda}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 16}}, \quad (\text{S1.35})$$

resulting in $E_\Lambda = 1115.70587 \text{ MeV}$, which is very consistent with the measured value. (Other assumptions for the initial toroidal-orbit structure of the Λ particle, such as three basic-toroidal-orbits r_{-861} or two r_{-861} with four r_{-137} , do not yield formulae consistent with the consistency rules.)

When the formula is adjusted as described above,

the corresponding image is a vertical interlock between a toroidal-orbit with a capacity of $E_{-137} \times 16$ and the basic-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} . The capacity of the former is very close to E_Λ , suggesting that the left side of the formula, r_{-861} , might be empty-toroidal-orbits, while the right side, $r_{-137 \times 16}$, represents the toroidal-orbits containing all the rest mass energy of the Λ particle.

This formula may reflect the overall structure of the Λ particle, but it is not yet the final structural formula for the Λ particle, as the final formula should simultaneously reflect the particle's mass, radius, and magnetic moment. Although we do not have a measured radius for the Λ particle, we have obtained a rough estimate of its magnetic moment, which helps us refine the structural formula of the Λ particle and accurately understand its toroidal-orbit structure.

If we follow the initial assumption that the right side's $r_{-137 \times 16}$ contains all the rest mass energy of the Λ particle, the magnetic moment it provides should be $\frac{\frac{E_\Lambda}{E_e}}{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 16} \times \sin(45^\circ) = 0.706 \mu_N$, but the measured magnetic moment of the Λ particle is $-0.606 \pm 0.015 \mu_N$ [22], measured in 1981, which does not match.

If we consider a different approach, viewing the right side's $r_{-137 \times 16}$ as the initial energy source for the Λ particle, with this energy eventually operating in the left side's r_{-861} , we first adjust the structural formula to:

$$\frac{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 16 - \frac{E_\Lambda}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 3\right)^2} = \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 16}}\right) \times \frac{1}{3^2}. \quad (\text{S1.36})$$

Now, the capacity of the toroidal-orbits on the left side becomes $E_{-861} \times 3 = E_e \times 2583$, enough to accommodate E_Λ , while the right side's $r_{-137 \times 16}$ is considered empty-toroidal-orbits. The magnetic moment provided by the left side toroidal-orbits is: $\frac{E_\Lambda}{E_{-861} \times 3} \times \sin(45^\circ) = 0.597682 \mu_N$, which aligns with the measured value. If the magnetic moment's μ_{Part2} for the Λ particle is based on $\frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \mu_N$ with added $\sin(45^\circ)$ —to maintain consistency with the outer toroidal-orbits and the opposite sign to μ_{Part1} —since the μ_{Part1} and μ_{Part2} values for protons and neutrons are op-

posites, but without adding the term $\frac{4\pi+1}{16}$ from the proton's μ_{Part2} —suspected to be necessary only when two toroidal-orbits are same and perpendicular, the magnetic moment formula for the Λ particle is:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mu_{\Lambda(2)}}{\mu_N} &= -\frac{E_{\Lambda}}{E_{-861} \times 3} \times \sin(45^\circ) + \frac{\alpha}{2\pi} \times \sin(45^\circ) \\ &= -0.596520. \end{aligned} \quad (S1.37)$$

Lastly, if the Λ particle's actual toroidal-orbits are $r_{-861 \times 3}$, its electromagnetic radius should be:

$$r_{\Lambda} = r_{-1} \times \frac{1}{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 3} = 0.149 \times 10^{-15} \text{m}. \quad (S1.38)$$

m. Ξ baryons

Next up, let's dive into the Ξ baryons, which primarily exist in two charge states: the neutral Ξ^0 and the negatively charged Ξ^- . The measured mass of the Ξ^- particle is $1321.71 \pm 0.07 \text{MeV}/c^2$ [8], or $E_{-861} \times 3.004$. Considering the particle's actual energy shouldn't exceed the total energy of its initial toroidal-orbit structures, it's speculated that its initial toroidal-orbits consist of three filling-toroidal-orbits r_{-861} and one filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-137} , equating to $E_e \times \frac{6\pi+1}{\alpha}$. Following this assumption, a structure very similar to that of the Λ particle can be derived:

$$\frac{\frac{6\pi+1}{\alpha} - \frac{E_{\Xi^-}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 4\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{6\pi+1}{\alpha}}}. \quad (S1.39)$$

This results in $E_{\Xi^-} = 1322.48133 \text{MeV}$, aligning with the measured value. The corresponding image depicts an interlock between an empty toroidal-orbit with a capacity of $E_{-861} \times 4$ and a filling-toroidal-orbit with a capacity of $E_{-861} \times 3 + E_{-137}$.

While alternative formulations are possible, with the current structure, the magnetic moment provided by the filling-toroidal-orbits should be $\mu_{Part1} = \frac{E_{\Xi^-}}{\frac{6\pi+1}{\alpha}} \times \sin(45^\circ) = 0.672\mu_N$, which is close to the measured magnetic moments of $0.6507 \pm 0.0025\mu_N$ for Ξ^- [8] and $0.657 \pm 0.028 \pm 0.020\mu_N$ for Ξ^+ [8]. Although

the specific reasons are still unclear, it's speculated that, unlike the Λ particles, the matter-charge of Ξ^- particles still operates within the toroidal-orbits on the right side of the formula.

Under this assumption, the radius of the Ξ^- particle would be:

$$r_{\Lambda} = r_{-1} \times \frac{1}{\frac{6\pi+1}{\alpha}} = 0.142 \times 10^{-15} \text{m}. \quad (S1.40)$$

The Ξ^0 particle's measured mass is $1314.86 \pm 0.20 \text{MeV}/c^2$ [8], or $E_{-861} \times 2.988$, suggesting its initial toroidal-orbits consist of three basic-toroidal-orbits r_{-861} . However, no suitable structural formula was found with this assumption. Yet, if the initial toroidal-orbits of the Ξ^0 particle are the same as those of the Ξ^- particle, the following structure can be derived:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{6\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{2} - \frac{E_{\Xi^0}}{E_e} \times \frac{1}{2}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 2\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 16}}. \quad (S1.41)$$

This yields $E_{\Xi^0} = 1314.79969 \text{MeV}$, consistent with the measured value. This structure also clearly depicts the rest mass energy of the Ξ^0 particle split between two overlapping toroidal-orbits, each with a capacity of $E_{-137} \times 16$. This formula can be transformed into other forms, but as described, each toroidal-orbit contributes a magnetic moment of $\frac{\frac{1}{2} \times E_{\Xi^0}}{E_{-137} \times 16} = 0.5868\mu_N$. Assuming the spatial structure of the Ξ^0 particle's toroidal-orbits is consistent with that of the neutron's, with the main toroidal-orbit placed horizontally, the $\sin(45^\circ)$ factor isn't necessary. The total magnetic moment contributed by the two overlapping toroidal-orbits, $\mu_{Part1} = 1.1736\mu_N$, aligns with the measured value of $-1.20 \pm 0.06\mu_N$ [8].

However, these structural formulae for the Ξ particles are speculative and await a deeper understanding of the toroidal-orbits' internal mechanisms or further detailed data support.

n. Ω baryons

Moving forward to the Ω baryons, the measured mass of the Ω^- particle is $1672.45 \pm 0.29 \text{MeV}/c^2$ [8],

or $E_e \times 3272.9$, which is slightly less than the sum of 3 r_{-861} and 6 r_{-137} , totaling $E_e \times 3405.3$. Assuming the main-toroidal-orbit capacity of the Ω^- is 3 r_{-861} , we derive the following structure:

$$\frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 3 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 6 - \frac{E_{\Omega^-}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 3\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}}}. \quad (\text{S1.42})$$

The calculation results in $E_{\Omega^-} = 1672.62189\text{MeV}$, which is very close to the measured value.

Just like before, this is only a preliminary structure. It needs further adjustment to align with the measured radius and magnetic moment of the Ω^- particle.

Although we don't have a measured radius for the Ω^- , its measured magnetic moment is $-2.02 \pm 0.05\mu_N$ [8]. Targeting this, the adjusted particle structure formula becomes:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 3 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 6 - \frac{E_{\Omega^-}}{E_e}\right) \times \frac{1}{2}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times \frac{3}{2}\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}}}. \quad (\text{S1.43})$$

The formula's left side corresponds to a toroidal-orbit with a capacity of $E_{-861} \times \frac{3}{2}$, and the right side corresponds to a toroidal-orbit with a capacity of E_{-861} , both featuring overlapping structures with two intersections.

If we distribute the energy corresponding to 3 r_{-861} and 6 r_{-137} to the left and right side toroidal-orbits respectively, considering the energy loss during the formation of the Ω^- particle as $E_{loss} = E_e \times \frac{6\pi+6}{\alpha} - E_{\Omega^-} = E_e \times 132.38$, and if this energy loss is entirely within the left overlapping toroidal-orbits, then the magnetic moment provided by the left toroidal-orbits would be $\frac{E_{-861} \times \frac{3}{2} - E_{loss} \times \frac{1}{2}}{E_{-861} \times \frac{3}{2}} \times \sin(45^\circ) \times 2 = 1.3417359\mu_N$; and with each toroidal-orbit on the right containing the energy of 3 r_{-137} , their contributed magnetic moment would be $\frac{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 3}{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}} \times \sin(45^\circ) \times 2 = 0.6752372\mu_N$. Together, they sum up to be the mag-

netic moment μ_{Part1} of the Ω^- particle:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\mu_{\Omega^-(1)}}{\mu_N} &= -\frac{E_{-861} \times \frac{3}{2} - E_{loss} \times \frac{1}{2}}{E_{-861} \times \frac{3}{2}} \times \sin(45^\circ) \times 2 \\ &\quad - \frac{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 3}{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}} \times \sin(45^\circ) \times 2 = -2.0169731. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S1.44})$$

This result aligns with the measured value. Of course, further magnetic moment measurements are required to verify this structure.

o. Σ baryons

For the Σ baryons, which exist in three charge states: Σ^0 , Σ^+ , and Σ^- , their measured masses are respectively $1192.642 \pm 0.024\text{MeV}/c^2$, $1189.37 \pm 0.07\text{MeV}/c^2$, and $1197.449 \pm 0.030\text{MeV}/c^2$ [8]. These values are slightly less than the sum of $E_{-861} \times 4 + E_{-137} \times 5$, or the initial toroidal-orbit of the proton with four basic-toroidal-orbits r_{-137} .

Using the same method, the following structure equations can be found:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 2 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 5 - \frac{E_{\Sigma^0}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 2\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 16}}, \quad (\text{S1.45a})$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 2 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 5 - \frac{E_{\Sigma^+}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 2\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha}}}, \quad (\text{S1.45b})$$

$$\frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 2 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 5 - \frac{E_{\Sigma^-}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 16\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha}}}, \quad (\text{S1.45c})$$

yielding masses of $E_{\Sigma^0} = 1192.503\text{MeV}$, $E_{\Sigma^+} = 1189.272\text{MeV}$, and $E_{\Sigma^-} = 1197.000\text{MeV}$, which are close to their measured values. The next step is to refine these formulae based on other measured properties to determine the true particle structure.

For the Σ^+ particle, with a measured magnetic moment of $2.458 \pm 0.010\mu_N$ [8], its structure formula

is adjusted to:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 2 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 5 - \frac{E_{\Sigma^+}}{E_e}\right) \times \frac{1}{2}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{4}}}. \quad (\text{S1.46})$$

The left side of the formula corresponds to overlapping basic-toroidal-orbits r_{-861} , and the right side to overlapping proton orbits r_p . The energy loss during particle formation, $E_{loss} = E_{-137} \times \frac{4\pi+5}{\alpha} - E_{\Sigma^+} = E_e \times 79.686$, if all lost in the left orbit, then the left toroidal-orbit's magnetic moment contribution is $\frac{E_{-861} - E_{loss} \times \frac{1}{2}}{E_{-861}} \times \sin(45^\circ) \times 2$, and the total magnetic moment contributed by the energy rotating in the two overlapping r_p toroidal-orbits is $\frac{E_{-137} \times 5 \times \frac{1}{2}}{E_{-137} \times \frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{4}} \times \sin(45^\circ) \times 2$, summing up to $2.3912\mu_N$.

For Σ^- , with a measured magnetic moment of $-1.160 \pm 0.025\mu_N$, its structure formula is adjusted to:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 2 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \times 5 - \frac{E_{\Sigma^-}}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 8\right)^2} = \left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{4\pi+1}{\alpha}}}\right) \times 2. \quad (\text{S1.47})$$

If compared with the structure formulae of other baryons, the coefficient 2 on the right side of the formula seems a bit unusual, but the particle structure described by the current formula can achieve a magnetic moment consistent with that of Σ^- . The structure described by this formula, which accounts for the magnetic moment consistent with the Σ^- , has its left side corresponding to an orbit with a capacity of $E_{-137 \times 8}$ and the right side to an orbit with a capacity of $E_{-137} \times (4\pi + 1)$. The energy loss during particle formation, $E_{loss} = E_{-137} \times \frac{4\pi+5}{\alpha} - E_{\Sigma^-} = E_e \times 63.876$, contributes to a magnetic moment of $\mu_{part1} = -1.16453\mu_N$ if the loss is in the left orbit.

Although this structure formula accurately obtains the magnetic moment of Σ^- , it fails to correspond with its observed radius. The structure formula suggests extremely small radii for both orbits: the left toroidal-orbit's radius is calculated as $r_{-1} \times \frac{1}{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 8} = 0.352 \times 10^{-15}\text{m}$, and the right orbit's radius is even less, at merely a quarter of the proton's radius. Con-

trarily, measurements from a 2001 study put the radius of Σ^- at $0.780 \pm 0.010 \times 10^{-15}\text{m}$ [8]. Regrettably, among the variety of baryons discussed, only Σ^- has a documented radius measurement. Additional data could be instrumental in resolving these discrepancies.

And since we do not have the measured magnetic moment for Σ^0 , we will not make further adjustments to its structural formula.

p. Tau leptons

According to the conclusions drawn earlier, strong interactions arise from the dual-rotations present within a particle's toroidal-orbit. Therefore, if there's only a single rotation, it will not participate in strong interactions. We can use Eq. (S1.6) to check whether a particle's toroidal-orbit has a single or double rotation—if the width of the orbit that matches the energy gap of the primary toroidal-orbit follows the rule of $\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{X}}$, this indicates that the orbit embedded in the primary toroidal-orbit is more like a hollow tube, meaning it has a dual rotation. However, if, like the muon, a coefficient of 2π needs to be added to Eq. (S1.6), changing the formula to $\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{X}}$, it corresponds to a picture of the hollow tube-like orbit being unfolded into a planar ring. This means that there's only a single rotation within this orbit perpendicular to the primary orbit.

Tau particles are categorized as leptons, characterized by their non-participation in strong interactions. Based on this fact, let us search for the possible structure of tau leptons.

The measured mass of the tau particle is $1776.91 \pm 0.12_{-0.13}^{+0.10}\text{MeV}/c^2$ [23], or $E_e \times 3477$, slightly less than four r_{-861} and one r_{137} , i.e., $E_{-137} \times (8\pi + 1) = E_e \times 3581$. By following the exact same steps as before, we can derive the following expression:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{8\pi+1}{\alpha} - \frac{E_\tau}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{2\pi}{\alpha} \times 2\right)^2} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\alpha} \times 8}}. \quad (\text{S1.48})$$

The calculated result is $E_\tau = 1776.798\text{MeV}$. However, even though it's very consistent with the measured value of the tau particle's mass, the particle corresponding to this structural formula should be involved in strong interactions.

Interestingly, according to the measured value of the tau particle, there's another possible structure.

The proton is formed by two r_{-861} and one r_{-137} . The matter-charge in the initial toroidal-orbit evenly forms two groups of orbits perpendicular to each other, and each orbit is the same, forming a very symmetrical structure. If the tau particle is indeed composed of four r_{-861} and one r_{-137} , could a similar symmetrical structure be formed? After a little calculation, we find that if $E_{\tau 0} = E_{-137} \times \frac{8\pi+1}{2}$ is divided evenly into two orbits, the full-load energy of each filling-toroidal-orbit is $\frac{1}{2} \times E_{\tau 0} = \frac{8\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{2} \times E_e$. If these two identical toroidal-orbits are perpendicular to each other, we can obtain an equation:

$$\frac{\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{8\pi+1}{\alpha} - \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{E_\tau}{E_e}}{\left(\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{8\pi+1}{\alpha}\right)^2} \times \frac{4\pi+1}{16} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\frac{\alpha}{2\pi}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{8\pi+1}{\alpha}}}. \quad (\text{S1.49})$$

Solving for E_τ , we obtain $E_\tau = 3477.34330374 \times E_e = 1776.919\text{MeV}$, this number is also consistent with the measured mass of the tau particle.

The right side of this structural formula is still the common form of Eq. (S1.6), without the additional 2π . However, unlike all the structural formulae in the text, a coefficient of $\frac{4\pi+1}{16}$ was added to the left side of this formula. This coefficient has appeared in μ_{Part2} of the proton's magnetic moment. Although its physical meaning isn't as clear as 2π , if its corresponding physical meaning can help the above structural formula form a temporarily stable particle—where the energy corresponding to $E_{\tau 0}$ is split into two toroidal-orbits perpendicular to each other, and at the same time, the length of the energy gap on the

toroidal-orbit is greater than the width of the toroidal-orbit, allowing this toroidal-orbit structure to stabilize for a short time—then one can imagine that, as the toroidal-orbits are no longer tightly nested, if the matter-charge in the electric toroidal-orbit is imagined as a fluid, these matter-charge wouldn't need to maintain a dual rotation mode of motion, just a rotation along the toroidal-orbit would suffice.

If the above assumptions hold, this could be the reason why tau particles do not participate in strong interactions and are classified as leptons.

However, because this is not a tightly nested structure, the structure described by Eq. (S1.49), even if it existed, may only have a very short lifetime. Also, because there's no dual rotation in the tau particle's toroidal-orbit, or rather, the supposed dual rotation didn't form, the two orbits that were originally perpendicular to each other probably couldn't remain stable. The two originally perpendicular toroidal-orbits should merge into one, with all the matter-charge rotating in the same direction, and then proceed to the next step of disintegration. It might first decay into the structure described by Eq. (S1.48), then decay into different hadrons, such as π mesons or K mesons, which are the strong decays of the tau particle; it might also decay from this toroidal-orbit into an electron or a muon, which are the lepton decays of the tau particle.

Moreover, if tau particles are described by Eq. (S1.49), the magnetic moment provided by its initial structure should be close to $\sin(45^\circ) \times 2 = 1.414\mu_B$, but this is obviously beyond the range of the measured value [8]. Therefore, it is speculated that the tau particle measured in the experiment corresponds to the state where all the matter-charge merges into one toroidal-orbit, i.e., like the electron and muon, there's only one main-toroidal-orbit in the horizontal direction. If this hypothetical structure is assumed, μ_{Part1} and μ_{Part2} of the tau magnetic moment should be the same as those of the electron and muon, while μ_{Part3} is likely to be the same as the first part of μ_{Part3}

of the neutron magnetic moment, i.e., $\frac{\alpha^2}{\sqrt{1}}$. The total magnetic moment contributed by these three parts is:

$$\frac{\mu_{\tau(3)}}{\mu_B} = -1 - \frac{\alpha}{2\pi} - \frac{\alpha^2}{2\pi} = -1.00116988 \quad (\text{S1.50})$$

However, the current formula for the μ_{Part3} component of the particle's magnetic moment is based on the induction from limited magnetic moment measurements, rather than being a calculated formula derived from the dynamics of matter-charge. Deeper insights remain for further research.

q. Higgs particle and W&Z bosons

In the context of the Standard Model, the attribute of mass is provided by the Higgs mechanism, which also gives the Higgs particle its unique status. However, in new models, mass is a description of the quantity of matter-charge within the toroidal-orbit. It is generated by the self-balancing mechanism of the toroidal-orbit structure and is a metric directly related to the particle's rest energy (for more details, please refer to S2). All observable particles with specific mass indicators should be directly associated with specific toroidal-orbit structures. The Higgs particle is no exception.

We recently deliberated on the toroidal-orbit structure of tau leptons. The full-load energy of this structure can be expressed as $\frac{1}{2} \times E_{\tau 0} = \frac{8\pi+1}{\alpha} \times \frac{1}{2} \times E_e$. Mirroring the process from r_{-1} to r_{-137} , a coefficient of $\frac{1}{\alpha}$ is introduced. Consequently, the capacity of the subsequent toroidal-orbit maintained by the tau lepton's orbit can be described as follows:

$$\frac{1}{2} \times E_{\tau 0} \times \frac{1}{\alpha} = \frac{8\pi+1}{\alpha^2} \times \frac{1}{2} \times E_e = 125.385\text{GeV}, \quad (\text{S1.51})$$

this value is consistent with the Higgs boson, $125.25 \pm 0.17\text{GeV}/c^2$ [24].

Of course, compared to the leptons and hadrons discussed earlier, the Higgs particle has its distinct

characteristics. For instance, it does not directly participate in strong interactions and is considered a point particle - in our new model, this reflects that it lacks a dual-rotational toroidal structure. It decays into other particles, indicating that it too is formed by a toroidal-orbit structure of matter-charge; it also does not possess a magnetic moment, suggesting that the Y_+ and Y_- that compose it do not form a layered orbit. These peculiarities are likely because this represents a high-energy state of the toroidal-orbit that differs from the normal one. Like the relationship between r_{-137} and r_{-1} , or perhaps the relationship between the Higgs particle and the tau toroidal-orbit, the radius has been reduced by $\frac{1}{\alpha}$, and the capacity has also increased by $\frac{1}{\alpha}$.

In high-energy particles, this method of multiplying the toroidal-orbit capacity by $\frac{1}{\alpha}$ should be universally prevalent. For instance, if we adhere to this theory, could it be plausible that the mass formula for the W boson is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\alpha} \times (E_{-861} + E_{-137} \times 2) + E_{p0} \\ = 80435.271854\text{MeV?} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S1.52})$$

This formula describes a group of toroidal-orbits that have clear and spatially balanced structures. The energy it carries is just the latest measured value of the W bosons, $80433.5(9.4)\text{MeV}/c^2$ [6].

When we examine the capacity of toroidal-orbits in relation to their structure, it's evident that the capacity inversely relates to the orbit's radius, as given by $r_{-X} = \frac{C_{-1}}{2\pi} \times \frac{1}{X}$. Also, based on Eq. (S1.6), the orbit's width is defined by $W_{-X} = \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{X}} \times C_{-1}$. Linking r_{-X} with $\frac{1}{2} \times W_{-X}$, we see that at $X = \left(\frac{4}{\alpha}\right)^2$, the toroidal-orbit's inner radius surpasses its main radius, destabilizing the structure. This suggests a boundary to Eq. (S1.6)'s application. High-energy particles, like the W boson or those near the $E_e \times \left(\frac{4}{\alpha}\right)^2 = 153536$ MeV capacity, such as the Higgs particle, may have stability mechanisms distinct from lower-energy particles. This is likely tied to the coefficient $\frac{1}{\alpha}$, critical

for the stability of these particles.

For the Z boson, the measured mass is $91.1876 \pm 0.021 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ [8], which is very close to $\frac{E_p}{\alpha} \times \sin(45^\circ) = 90.9178$, with the difference being only $E_e \times 528$. Therefore, we are inclined to guess that the W boson is a stable toroidal-orbit structure, but the Z boson is not a real particle, but rather a physical characteristic exhibited by a double-spinning toroidal-orbit structure, similar to quarks. However, regarding the high-energy state toroidal-orbits of these high-energy particles, although we do have some preliminary ideas, we prefer to withhold them for the time being.

8. Equilibrium mechanism of basic-toroidal-orbits

As can be seen, three basic-toroidal-orbits are crucial for the specific application of the particle toroidal-orbit model. Here, I'm trying to discuss how r_{-137} and r_{-861} establish equilibrium based on r_{-1} .

It is easy to determine r_{-1} . And note that r_{-1} is α times the ground-state orbital radius r_{Bohr} in the Bohr model, in which electrons have quantised orbital angular momentum $\hbar = r_{\text{Bohr}} \times p = r_{\text{Bohr}} \times m_e v$, where v is the electron velocity in a ground-state orbital and $v = \alpha \times c$:

$$r_{\text{Bohr}} = \frac{\hbar}{m_e c \times \alpha} = \frac{c \hbar}{E_e} \times \frac{1}{\alpha} = r_{-1} \times \frac{1}{\alpha}, \quad (\text{S1.53})$$

r_{-137} is obtained from such assumptions and calculations:

Although Y_+ and Y_- from E_e rotate in distinct toroidal-orbits, they are entirely connected by matter-charges in space, and they should also have a centre of gravity or an equilibrium orbit.

According to the Bohr model, electrons orbit protons. Both particles have a charge e , and their Coulomb interaction creates a centripetal force that is equivalent to the centrifugal force.

$$k_e \frac{e^2}{r_{\text{Bohr}}^2} = m_e \frac{v^2}{r_{\text{Bohr}}}. \quad (\text{S1.54})$$

In the electronic self-structure, the matter-charges of E_e correspond to unit charge e and rotate around the unit negative charge. The radius of the equilibrium orbit of $Y_{\pm}$ of E_e is r_{-n} , if the Coulomb force between the two still holds and there still exists a classical equilibrium between the centripetal force and centrifugal force.

$$k_e \frac{e^2}{r_{-n}^2} = m_e \frac{c^2}{r_{-n}}. \quad (\text{S1.55})$$

On dividing Eq. (S1.55) by Eq. (S1.54), we obtain

$$\frac{r_{-n}^2}{r_{\text{Bohr}}^2} = \frac{v^2}{c^2} \times \frac{r_{-n}}{r_{\text{Bohr}}}, \quad (\text{S1.56})$$

which can be rewritten as

$$r_{-n} = \frac{v^2}{c^2} \times r_{\text{Bohr}} = r_{\text{Bohr}} \times \alpha^2. \quad (\text{S1.57})$$

On substituting (S1.53), we obtain

$$r_{-n} = r_{-1} \times \alpha = r_{-137}. \quad (\text{S1.58})$$

It is basic-toroidal-orbit r_{-137} , the second basic-toroidal-orbit determined by the unit charge.

And how is the radius of r_{-861} determined?

Matter-charges in the r_{-137} orbit from space not only rotate but also interact with the unit negative charge of the electron. This interaction takes time $T = \frac{r_{-137}}{c}$. The time taken for matter-charges in the r_{-861} orbit to complete a circle is $\frac{r_{-861} \times 2\pi}{c} = \frac{r_{-137}}{c}$, this represents the dynamic equilibrium between the structure of the toroidal-orbit and the matter-changes in space.

9. Photons

When new assumptions and models are adopted, some familiar things may take on a new appearance, which may seem strange at first sight. However, everything still remains logical and consistent with experiments and observations. Moreover, this may expand our previous understanding.

Wave-particle duality is the content in S4, while the following will only introduce the structure of photons. Photons can also be described by the particle toroidal-orbit model. Compared to electrons and protons, which not only have rest energy but also carry unit charges, photons only have energy and do not carry unit charges. and therefore, has a simpler structure.

Photons have energy and are electrically neutral, so a photon with energy E should also be split into Y_+ and Y_- with equal amounts of $|E|$. Photons can also exhibit dynamic electromagnetic waves, so the Y_+ and Y_- that make up photons should have non-coinciding orbits, which is necessary to form observable electromagnetic fields.

It is easy to conceive that as long as the Y_+ and Y_- rotate around the forward axis of the photon, an electrically neutral structure with periodic electromagnetic fields is formed.

Same as the typical characteristics of photons, however, this is simply a preliminary assumption, further information is required.

a. Spiralling radius of the photon

The greater the energy E , the greater is the frequency ν and the shorter are the period T and wavelength λ . The fluctuation period of photons during forward motion is

$$T = \frac{h}{E}. \quad (\text{S1.59})$$

In addition, the angular momentum of the photon is a constant $\hbar$. Photons are classical structures formed by matter-charges. Note that $\hbar$ results from the rotation of $Y_{\pm}$ around the axis, and an equal amount of Y_+ and Y_- will be combined into energy E . From $\hbar = r \times p = r \times \frac{E}{c} = \frac{h}{2\pi}$, we obtain

$$\frac{h}{E} = \frac{2\pi r}{c}, \quad (\text{S1.60})$$

and the rotation radius

$$r = \frac{hc}{2\pi E} = \frac{\hbar c}{E}. \quad (\text{S1.61})$$

Combining Eq. (S1.59) and Eq. (S1.60), we obtain

$$T = \frac{h}{E} = \frac{2\pi r}{c}, \quad (\text{S1.62})$$

indicating that the electromagnetic period, which is the time taken for a photon to move forward ($T = \frac{h}{E}$) and matter-charges to rotate ($T = \frac{2\pi r}{c}$) is same, furthermore, the circumference travelled by matter-charges ($2\pi r$) is equal to the wavelength of the photon, $\lambda = c \times \frac{h}{E} = cT = 2\pi r$.

Therefore, the Y_+ and Y_- that generated the photons are not forward-centred; instead, they spiral forward with radius $r = \frac{\hbar c}{E}$.

b. Bidirectional screwing within photons

Polarisation of light confirms that Y_+ and Y_- have the same rotation radius but different rotation orientations. When both components rotate in the same direction, the directionality of the polarisation cannot be reflected. Thus, when Y_+ and Y_- are interconnected in space, the positive and negative charges are neutralised, and the electric vector is the smallest. Additionally, the directions of motion of the positive and negative matter-charges are opposite, leading to the superposition of magnetic vectors and thereby generating the largest magnetic vector. When Y_+ and Y_- are the farthest possible apart in space, the electric vector is the largest; then, the positive and negative charges are aligned, and the magnetic vector is neutralised and the smallest and corresponds to the polarisation direction of the photons, as shown in Figure S1.3.

c. Pseudorotation and line structure

Photons are currently believed to be inverse double helix structures composed of equal numbers of Y_+

Figure S1.3. Projection ring on the vertical plane of photon velocity.

and Y_- , and they have radius $r = \frac{\hbar c}{E}$.

Matter-charges should not travel at speed c while spinning at c , else, the instantaneous speed of Y_+ and Y_- will be greater than c . Therefore, after thorough consideration, it is proven that the spin of the photon is pseudo rotation and not true rotation. Both Y_+ and Y_- form a circle of spirals in space but in opposite directions, and their projections on the vertical plane of velocity are rings with overlapping radii $r = \frac{\hbar c}{E}$, $2\pi r$ corresponding to their wavelength in the direction of motion. After the formation of the structure, Y_+ and Y_- move forward with speed c without rotation.

When such a spiral structure passes through an observer in space, periodic changes in the electromagnetic vectors and polarisation of light can be observed.

Because of the structure of the photon as shown above, Y_+ and Y_- are not concentrated at a single place, and λ are their lengths in the velocity direction. The density of the matter-charges is the same for each of the two helices projected as a circle, and they are uniformly distributed. Compared with the typical point charge concept, matter-charges in particles are a form of linear charge.

d. From photons to electrons

The structures of photons and electrons exhibit similarities.

If the energy of a photon is $E = E_e$, its screw-in radius is $r = \frac{\hbar c}{E_e} = r_e$, which yields the same projection

on the vertical velocity plane as the toroidal-orbit of an electron.

Photons have no charge per particle, therefore, if the circular projection of photons is its initial circular orbit, and Y_+ and Y_- rotate in opposite directions with the same radius, then Y_+ and Y_- will eventually collide, thereby destroying the toroidal-orbit structure, and subsequently, photons will appear. However, electrons possess an extra negative charge, thus, $|e| = |E_e|$. The Y_- in e should have some relationship with Y_+ split in E_e , similar to the correlation between Y_- and Y_+ in E_e .

If Y_- in e is at the centre of the toroidal-orbit and moves Y_+ in E_e inward, then Y_- and Y_+ of E_e will have orbits of different radii that do not interfere and rotate.

The toroidal-orbit structure of photons is broken, and matter-charges only move forward without rotating; in contrast, the toroidal-orbit of electrons is not broken, and the matter-charges first perform an orbit revolution. Consequently, the unit charge plays an important role in constraining Y_+ and Y_- to form electrons and other particles instead of photons.

10. From protons and neutrons to atomic nuclei

We have already discussed the toroidal-orbit structure of protons and neutrons, and if everything is as described earlier, the atomic nucleus, primarily composed of protons and neutrons, should also follow the same principle.

Within the atomic nucleus, there must inevitably be interactions between protons and neutrons, and the simplest and most typical case should be the interlacing of toroidal-orbits between one proton and one neutron.

If the neutron's orbit r_{-1185} crosses the vertical intersection of the proton's orbit r_p , the energy loss E_{loss} on the proton's toroidal-orbit due to the shielding by the neutron's toroidal-orbit would be:

$$E_{loss} = E_{p0} \times \frac{1}{4} \times \frac{W_{-1185} \times \sqrt{2}}{C_p} \times \sqrt{2} \times 2 \quad (S1.63)$$

$$= 14.573084 \times E_e.$$

$E_{p0} \times \frac{1}{4}$ represents the energy of a single proton orbit. $\frac{W_{-1185} \times \sqrt{2}}{C_p}$ describes the proportion of the proton orbit that is shielded. Coefficient $\sqrt{2}$ reflects the vertical interlacing of the actual proton orbit. The final coefficient 2 describes the superposition of two proton orbits together.

Therefore, if a proton and a neutron can form a deuterium nucleus in such a configuration, they would have a binding point. The portion lost due to shielding will no longer contribute to the magnetic moment. Therefore, the magnetic moment of the deuterium nucleus should be:

$$\mu_p \times \frac{E_p - E_{loss}}{E_p} + \mu_n = 0.85764\mu B \quad (S1.64)$$

and the measured value is approximately $0.857438\mu B$.

For another example, when two protons and two neutrons combine to form an alpha particle, the four particles will have four binding points in their orbits. The total energy loss due to shielding would be $E_{loss} \times 4 = 29.787\text{MeV}$, and the measured value of the binding energy of alpha particle is approximately 28.3MeV .

Although the two calculations mentioned above do not reach the precision as the magnetic moment of a proton or neutron, there are also some questions that cannot be answered directly, such as the binding energy of a deuterium nucleus is not equal to the E_{loss} . However, perhaps the error here is the key to exploring the interaction between the toroidal-orbits of protons and neutrons inside the atomic nucleus. For example, according to the coincidence in the numerical values in

$$E_{loss} \times 4 - E_e \times 2 \times \sqrt{2} = 28.3419992\text{MeV}, \quad (S1.65)$$

this is nearly the binding energy of the alpha particle. If the small error here arises from an unclear

specific mechanism, it seems possible to assume that there is no independent neutron structure within the atomic nucleus. Such as in an alpha particle, it is not composed of 2 protons and 2 neutrons, but rather a symmetric structure formed by two parts, with each part is two protons bonding with one electron. The coefficient $\sqrt{2}$ appears due to the shared usage of electrons by the two protons. This hypothesis could explain why neutrons in the atomic nucleus do not decay like free neutrons, as they have a different structure. It could also explain the radius of an alpha particle, $1.67824(83)\text{fm}$ [25], which is nearly twice the radius of two protons, instead of the sum of the radii of protons and neutrons. In addition, with such specific structures, we have the opportunity to make new hypotheses to explain strong interactions.

Now returning to the neutron, in the previous sections, we calculated the masses of dozens of particles, with the calculated values almost exactly matching their measured values. However, we did not calculate the mass of the neutron. Among all particles formed by intersecting toroidal-orbits, the neutron is the most unique. The gap in the neutron's toroidal-orbit differs from all other particles; it is not caused by shielding but is determined by a coefficient $(1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2})$, and the neutron borrows energy from space. These two unique mechanisms have not been thoroughly understood by us. If we calculate the mass of the neutron by combining the length of the energy gap with the width of the embedded toroidal-orbit, the obtained value is $E_\mu = 932.034 \text{ MeV}$, significantly lower than the actual measured value. However, if we supplement it with E_{loss} , we get:

$$E_n = \frac{(1 - \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}) \times (\sqrt{2} + \frac{1}{2})}{\frac{\alpha}{\sqrt{\frac{2\pi}{\alpha}}}} - \frac{\pi}{\alpha} + E_{loss} = 939.48035\text{MeV}, \quad (S1.66)$$

for convenience, I did not list the common particle structures but directly provided the calculation formula for the neutron mass, which is significantly close to the measured value of $939.56542052(54) \text{ MeV}$. But this implies a more unique outcome, namely, that the

toroidal-orbit structure of the neutron itself only carries 932.033 MeV of energy. In fact, within atomic nuclei, the neutron does indeed have only this amount of energy, which is consistent with the binding energy of the helium atom. However, when it forms an independent neutron outside of atomic nuclei, it absorbs an additional amount of energy, thereby forming the neutron as we know it. Under such a hypothesis, the radius, magnetic moment, and mass of the neutron are consistent with measured values. However, all studied particles conform to a unified initial toroidal-orbit rule, yet the neutron exhibits uniqueness, whether supplementing the neutron's mass with E_{loss} is reasonable, and the mechanisms behind these unique situations in the neutron's structure, require further specialized research, which may be combined with further studies on atomic nuclei.

The new model is a framework, and as the accuracy of particle physics measurements improves, the details within the framework will inevitably become more refined. However, this also requires more effort, especially considering the striking differences between the new model and previous understandings.

11. Conclusions

In our work, we have ventured to present the particle toroidal-orbit model alongside the matter-charge hypothesis, examining their implications for particle physics. We trace the journey from a single unit charge to the inception of a basic-toroidal-orbit and its proliferation to a multitude of particle species. Our approach to determining the toroidal-orbit structure of particles has been elucidated, with the calculation of their fundamental attributes undertaken individually. The extrapolation of these structures and the associated computational formulae for particles beyond those explicated within this paper is feasible applying the same methodology. This confirms the applicability, resilience, and precision of the model, facilitating a nuanced understanding of particle structures and

attributes. Admittedly, the model is yet to reach perfection; for example, the toroidal-orbit width formula is still empirical, and the significance of several mathematical factors remains to be elucidated. Nevertheless, it offers innovative insights and methodologies that enhance our grasp of particle physics.

In contrast to the Standard Model, which we are more accustomed to and which places a greater emphasis on mathematical formalisms, our model provides an exceptionally intuitive alternative. Although founded on completely different fundamental assumptions and perspectives, both models offer the potential for synergistic advancements in practical applications. For example, our new model adopts the Standard Model's particle classification, grouping baryons and mesons as hadrons, while maintaining leptons as a distinct category. Furthermore, it enriches this framework with insights into quarks—these are associated with the vertically staggered closed areas within toroidal-orbits. Such contributions serve as a constructive augmentation to the Standard Model.

Our framework enables novel approaches for quantifying mass, radius, and magnetic moments, which are intrinsically linked to toroidal-orbit structures and may offer advantages over the Standard Model. However, it has yet to find an effective method for estimating particle lifetimes, a field in which the Standard Model has been very successful. For example, according to the Standard Model, the range of the weak interaction is very short, on the order of 10^{-18}m , which in the new model corresponds to the internal diameter scale provided by the toroidal-orbit width formula. Hence, the two models should not only be seen as capable of complementing each other but it is also imperative that they do so.

More importantly, this model extends its reach beyond particle physics, grounded in fundamental principles that span the entirety of the physical realm, thereby forging connections between diverse fields.

The narrative woven through the main body of the text and the SI offers a holistic vision that en-

compasses particle physics, relativistic physics, quantum physics, and the four fundamental forces, substantiated by comprehensive calculations and theoretical proofs. Consequently, although the most crucial aspect—the dynamics mechanism of matter-charge—remains incomplete, it assembles into a coherent, convincing, and utilitarian worldview. We look forward with eagerness to future discussions aimed not just at refining this model but also at deepening our collective comprehension of the material universe.

S2: Deduction of Special Relativity, and the Explanation of Mass and Energy

1. Introduction

In this section, we discussed the physics phenomena related to special relativity, including time dilation, length contraction, relativistic mass effects, and the relationship among mass, energy and the quantity of matter-charge is discussed.

Einstein introduced the concept of a four-dimensional space-time structure that varies with relative velocity. He then utilized the principles of the invariance of the speed of light and relativity to describe the three effects of special relativity.

Although his explanation has already deeply penetrated people's minds, if particles do indeed possess toroidal-orbit structures by the matter-charge, which move at the speed of light through space, three relativistic effects will be manifested inevitably. Special relativity can be derived from the particle toroidal-orbit model and the matter-charge theory.

Moreover, because of the toroidal-orbit structure, mass and inertia are no longer complicated notions.

2. Time dilation effect with the toroidal-orbit structure

Consider the scenario in classical physics: Alice is relatively stationary in space, observing all details

of a spacecraft moving with a velocity v_1 , and she has discovered four time-related phenomena:

- Phenomenon 1: The timing of clocks on the spacecraft slows down.
- Phenomenon 2: Particles on the spaceship disintegrate at a slower rate.
- Phenomenon 3: The movement speed of all objects aboard the spacecraft decreases.
- Phenomenon 4: The physical actions of the spaceship become less efficient.

According to special relativity, it will be assumed that because of the speed of the spaceship relative to space, the time dimension of the inertial system of the spacecraft expands relative to Alice and the passage of time is accelerated or slowed down, causing many effects being observed simultaneously. However, by using the proposed model, we can observe different physical details.

a. Photon clock on the spacecraft

To describe phenomenon 1, we require a basic timer: the photon clock shown in Fig. S2.1. This clock consists of two parallel reflectors separated by distance d and a vertically oscillating photon P. Each time the photon travels back and forth between the reflective surfaces, the timing is increased by one. A photon clock A is placed next to Alice. As it is stationary in space, the distance that the photon travels once is $2d$, and its velocity in space is c . Then, the cycle time is $t = \frac{2d}{c}$, and the number of reflections in 1s is $n = \frac{1}{t} = \frac{c}{2d}$. Therefore, Alice thinks that every time the count changes by n , time passes by 1s.

The spacecraft travels at velocity v_1 relative to space, which contains photon clock B and observer Bob. From Alice's viewpoint, the vibration velocity of the photons in clock B between the plates is $v_2 = \sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}$, and the time for one cycle is $t' = \frac{2d}{v_2}$.

Figure S2.1. A photon clock model.

Therefore, in 1s in Alice's frame, the recorded number of clock A changes $n = \frac{c}{2d}$ times, and the count of clock B only changes $n' = \frac{1}{t'} = \frac{v_2}{2d} = \frac{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}{2d}$ times, and the displayed time is $\frac{n'}{n} = \frac{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}{c} < 1$ s; this is phenomenon 1.

b. *Decay time of particles on the spacecraft will slow down*

As explained in S1, muons have a toroidal-orbit structure that is created by the filling-toroidal-orbit r_{-861} , and the matter-charges rotate in the toroidal-orbit to create the magnetic moment (see Fig. S2.2). Since the magnetic moment direction of muons is parallel to their velocity, the rotating surface of the matter-charges corresponding to the rest energy of the muons is perpendicular to the velocity direction of muons.

Figure S2.2. The rotation of matter-charge in muon's filling-toroidal-orbit.

The outermost toroidal-orbit of muons is $C_{-861} = r_{-861} \times 2\pi = \frac{c\hbar}{E_e} \times \alpha$, and their measured lifetime is

$$T_\mu = 2.2 \text{ ms.}$$

The number of turns of Y. in the outermost toroidal-orbit in the lifetime of a muon is $n_\mu = \frac{T_\mu \times c}{C_{-861}}$.

If a muon is stationary in space, the rotation speed of the matter-charges in the toroidal-orbit is c . When the muon moves forward with speed v_1 , the rotation speed decreases to $v_2 = \sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}$, and the time spent n_μ increases. The larger v_1 , the longer is the decay period. Thus, phenomenon 2 also appears.

c. *Everything onboard the spacecraft moves at a slower velocity*

According to the model, all particles are composed of matter-charged toroidal-orbit configurations.

Any matter-charge in a toroidal-orbit is always rotating, and its average position is the toroidal-orbit. The movement of a particle in space is viewed as the summation of all the reciprocating motions.

The speed of particles in space is exactly proportional to the rate at which the matter-charge oscillates within the orbit.

Therefore, if an inertial frame is relatively fixed in space, the rotational velocity of all the matter-charge within the toroidal-orbit is c .

If all the objects in the spacecraft, including the microscopic particles that make up the object and all the matter-charges in the orbit of the microscopic particles, move with velocity v_1 then the speed at which they rotate in the toroidal-orbit is no longer c , but v_2 , which can also be regarded the rotational speed of these matter-charges relative to the spacecraft.

The particle motion in the inertial frame is considered the accumulation of reciprocating motions of matter-charges within the toroidal-orbit. When the reciprocating speed decreases from c to v_2 , the speed of all particles relative to the spacecraft decreases to $\frac{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}{c}$. The same is true of the speed of an object made up of particles, this is phenomenon 3.

d. Slowdown of efficiency of all physical actions on the spacecraft

The speed of the electromagnetic wave is the speed of matter-charges in space. Therefore, in the spacecraft with speed v_1 , the transmission efficiency of electromagnetic waves is reduced by $\frac{\sqrt{c^2-v_1^2}}{c}$. All physical actions, such as electromagnetic force and universal gravitation, transmitted at the speed of light will be slowed. Consequently, everything slowed down, this is phenomenon 4.

When all four phenomena occur concurrently, Alice perceives that everything on the spacecraft has slowed down as if the spacecraft has fallen into a time trap. Bob is ignorant of this as if the interior and exterior of the spacecraft are in different time and space.

Consequently, the particle toroidal-orbit model and the matter-charge theory unavoidably produce the time dilation effect, and the time dimension that varies dynamically with relative velocity has no physical relevance.

3. Length contraction effect and length contraction hypothesis

We assume that neither time nor space can shrink or expand. Experiments have demonstrated that at high speeds, the length of an object in the direction of motion will indeed decrease. Why is this so? At the end of the nineteenth century, the Irish physicist FitzGerald and the Dutch physicist Lorentz introduced the length contraction hypothesis [26]. According to this hypothesis, macroscopic objects are composed of a vast number of charged particles that form electromagnetically stable structures. Assume a large object is traveling through space at speed v_1 . Because of electromagnetic equilibrium in motion, the distance between the particles in the velocity direction of the object, is reduced; that is, the length becomes $\frac{\sqrt{c^2-v_1^2}}{c}$ times the length when it was stationary.

This calculation is easy to verify without the need

for additional assumptions, applying classical electromagnetic theory in classical spacetime. The macroscopic electromagnetic equilibrium is derived from the equilibrium between the matter-charges. Consequently, both macroscopic objects and microscopic particles experience the scale down effect.

4. Relativistic mass effect and matter-charge hypothesis

The relativistic mass effect states that when an object moves, its mass increases from m_0 to m and follows

$$m = m_0 \times \frac{c}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}. \quad (\text{S2.1})$$

Regardless of the difference between mass and energy, from the mass-energy formula, we have

$$E = E_0 \times \frac{c}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}, \quad (\text{S2.2})$$

where E_0 is the rest energy of the object, and $E = E_0 + E_k$ is the sum of the static and kinetic energy of the object.

Using the number of the matter-charges, we have

$$|E| = |E_0| \times \frac{c}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}, \quad (\text{S2.3})$$

which shows that when the number of matter-charges in a particle increases from $|E_0|$ to $|E| = |E_0| + |E_k|$, the speed of the particle changes from 0 to v_1 . The relationship between particle velocity and energy increment is deduced in the following text.

First, regardless of whether the particle is in motion, the radius of its toroidal-orbit does not change in the vertical plane of velocity; otherwise, as the speed of a particle' increases, we would observe not only the length contraction effect, but also expansion or contraction in the direction of vertical velocity.

Second, the density of the matter-charge in every toroidal-orbit is constant.

Therefore, when a particle with rest energy E_0 attains kinetic energy E_k , the matter-charge in the

toroidal-orbit increases by $|E_k|$. Since the radius of the toroidal-orbit remains constant, its density also increases, and hence, the equilibrium of the toroidal-orbit will be destroyed. Particles are self-balancing structures formed by $Y_{\pm}$ in the toroidal-orbit and space. Hence, to maintain their stability, the particles that have gained kinetic energy must move in space.

The velocity of the particle in space is v_1 , and the speed at which the matter-charge in the toroidal-orbit rotates on a plane perpendicular to the velocity decreases from c to $\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}$. Hence,

$$C = c \times t = c \times \frac{C_0}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}} = C_0 \times \frac{c}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}. \quad (\text{S2.4})$$

Considering the density of matter-charges in the toroidal-orbit remains constant, when the particle moves with speed v_1 , the amount of matter-charges in the toroidal-orbit is $\frac{c}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}$ times that at rest, which is also a multiple of the energy in the toroidal-orbit at rest.

Thus, when the stationary particle obtains additional energy E_k , it can only accept new matter-charges at a certain speed v_1 ; that is,

$$E = E_0 + E_k = E_0 \times \frac{c}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}. \quad (\text{S2.5})$$

If this velocity cannot be attained, equivalent matter-charges will move away with some form of energy.

This phenomenon is caused by the relativistic mass effect or the motion behavior of particles, but it is an inevitable consequence of the particle toroidal-orbit model and the matter-charge hypothesis, not the interaction between particles and four-dimensional space-time.

5. Derivation of the assumptions of special relativity

From the particle toroidal-orbit model and the matter-charge hypothesis, we can deduce the princi-

ple of invariance of light velocity and the principle of relativity, i.e., the two fundamental assumptions of special relativity.

a. Derivation of the principle of invariance of the speed of light

According to the principle of invariance of speed of light, the speed of light is constant in all inertial frames. Nevertheless, based on this paradigm, this principle is merely a mathematical result, and its physical significance is debatable.

Considering the time dilation effect and the length contraction effect and realizing that we must employ two-way light-speed measurements to measure the speed of light, we find that when an observer in an inertial frame measures the speed of light, the result is a constant c .

The derivation is simple:

Figure S2.3 shows a stationary inertial frame where O is the start and end point of light, A is a mirror, and d is the length of OA. We record the time when the light returns to O after traveling from O to A, and then get the speed of light c using the relation $v = \frac{2d}{t}$.

If the inertial frame is not stationary at a velocity v_1 , then there will be three cases.

In the first case, v_1 is perpendicular to OA. Bob measured the speed of light in the optical path of OA and AO.

Since the velocity of light in space is a constant, i.e., c and the speed of inertia in space is v_1 , the velocity of light in the optical path of OA and AO is

$$v_2 = \sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}. \quad (\text{S2.6})$$

Alice saw that the time spent was $t = \frac{2d}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}$, but because of the time dilation effect, Bob recorded the time as

$$t_2 = t \times \frac{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}{c} = \frac{2d}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}} \times \frac{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}{c} = \frac{2d}{c}. \quad (\text{S2.7})$$

So, Bob thinks that the distance traveled by light is $2d$, and the time is $\frac{2d}{c}$. Regardless of the velocity v_1 , Bob measured in the inertial frame that the speed of light remained constant as $\frac{2d}{\frac{2d}{c}} = c$.

Figure S2.3. Measuring the speed of light. The vibration direction of photons is perpendicular or parallel to the velocity direction of the photon clock.

In the second case, v_1 is parallel to OA, as Fig. S2.3(b). Bob measures the speed of light along the optical paths OA and AO.

Now, in addition to the time dilation effect, we should consider the length contraction effect. So, the distance between OA in motion is $d_2 = d \times \frac{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}{c}$.

The speed of points O and A in space is v_1 . Hence, the time for a photon to reach point A from O is $\frac{d_2}{c - v_1}$, and the time to return to point O is $\frac{d_2}{c + v_1}$. Therefore, in Alice's frame, the time taken for light to travel forth and back along OA is $t = \frac{d_2}{c - v_1} + \frac{d_2}{c + v_1} = \frac{2cd_2}{c^2 - v_1^2}$.

Considering the time dilation effect, Bob recorded the time taken as

$$\begin{aligned} t_2 &= t \times \frac{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}{c} = \frac{2cd_2}{c^2 - v_1^2} \times \frac{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}{c} \\ &= \frac{2d_2}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}} = \frac{2d \times \frac{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}{c}}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}} = \frac{2d}{c}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S2.8})$$

In this case, the speed of light that Bob measured was still c .

Regardless of whether the optical path is vertical or parallel, the angle of v_1 and v_2 , and the value of v_1 , Bob's measured result will not change, it remains constant at c , that is, the true speed of matter-charge traveling in space.

This is the first underlying assumption of special relativity.

b. Preliminary understanding of the principle of relativity

The second core principle of special relativity is the principle of relativity, which states that the physical laws are identical in all inertial frames. This principle, acknowledged as a widely applicable phenomenon, is not elaborated upon by the theory of relativity in terms of its underlying physical mechanisms. Instead, it is adopted as a fundamental physical principle and applied to various physical events. However, according to the particle toroidal-orbit model and the matter-charge hypothesis, although all physical behaviors in all inertial frames appear to conform to the principle of relativity from an observational standpoint, different physical behaviors have their own underlying mechanisms.

Because the time dilation effect and length contraction effect occur simultaneously, most scientific phenomena, particularly those related to electromagnetism and the renowned Michelson-Morley experiment, behave identically in different inertial frames.

In a few instances, certain particulars must be considered. For instance, when deducing the principle of invariance of speed of light, we examined both the relativistic effect and the two-way light velocity measurement.

Rarely does the principle of relativity fail. But in the second case just deduced, for instance, the time for light to travel from O to A is $\frac{d_2}{c - v_1}$ and the time to return is $\frac{d_2}{c + v_1}$, suggesting that the times for the two paths are distinct. However, according to the principle

of relativity, the times taken for these two paths should be considered equivalent.

Considering the notion of simultaneity of time and varying physical processes in different theories, there is no method to correctly quantify the time taken along each optical path, and it is impossible to compare them. The special theory of relativity and the theory in this paper are logically coherent.

In a few instances, the “principle of relativity” may not seem to apply; we shall describe a number of physical behaviors that reflect this principle.

6. Quantities free of relativistic effects

Most physical quantities, such as time, length in the velocity direction, and mass, are related to the speed within a defined reference system. However, there exist other attributes that are independent of speed. An example is the particle spin magnetic moment, which is discussed in S1 and can be easily understood from the description of the relativistic mass effect in this model.

When a particle is stationary in space, its orbital magnetic moment is $I \times S = (q \times \frac{v}{2\pi r}) \times (\pi r^2) = \frac{1}{2} \times q \times v \times r$, which is summed up as particle spin magnetic moments.

Because the matter-charges in the particle toroidal-orbit have the same velocity vector as the particle, the rotation speed of the matter-charges in the toroidal-orbit is no longer c ; it decreases to $v_2 = \sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}$. However, the amount of matter-charges in the particle increases as well, reaching the value of $\frac{c}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}$, and so, the two effects cancel out.

However, the aggregated particle spin magnetic moment does not change in the reference system, regardless of the velocity of the particle relative to the observer because the orbital magnetic moment is generated by the particle toroidal-orbit. The principle of relativity does not express this behavior: the magnetic moment remains the same regardless of the reference system.

This trait is likewise shared by the unit charge carried by particles. Although we will not go into details here, all physical phenomena will have a very specific rationale in this paradigm.

7. Energy, mass and inertia

Unlike electrons and protons, photons have no mass. Mass is associated with energy, particularly rest energy, but what exactly is mass?

If two objects gain the same energy E_k at the same time, then in the transition from a state of rest to motion, the less the change in speed, the higher is the mass according to the kinetic energy equation $E_k = \frac{1}{2}mv^2$. Thus, mass can be regarded as the difficulty with which the velocity of an object changes after gaining energy.

When particles with differing rest energies acquire the same amount of energy increments E_k from $E_0 + E_k = E_0 \times \frac{c}{\sqrt{c^2 - v_1^2}}$, the bigger E_0 , the lower v_1 .

The more matter-charges in the toroidal-orbit, the greater is E_0 regardless of whether we are dealing with a single particle or a macroscopic entity generated by a vast number of particles. The greater the difficulty in changing speed, the greater is the bulk displayed.

Therefore, mass is an unavoidable conclusion of the particle toroidal-orbit model and the matter-charge hypothesis, and it reflects the quantity of matter-charges within the particle. If the toroidal-orbit is destroyed, there is no mass, as in the case of photons.

Further, mass is related to inertia; however, inertia focuses on defining an object’s resistance as it changes its state of motion.

The model distinguishes between the change in the energy of the object after obtaining force and the change in speed of the object after acquiring energy.

We push an object in the first stage to generate kinetic energy and transmit the matter-charge between the hand and object.

In the second stage, as the energy of the object increases, too many matter-charges accumulate in the toroidal-orbits of the particles that comprise the object, and because self-equilibrium between the toroidal-orbit of the particle and the matter-charge in space, the speed of the particle in space is altered.

Although both phases follow the same trend, the physical processes are not synchronized; therefore, inertia with impedance characteristics is reflected. The larger the mass, the greater is the inertia, and they are consistent with each other.

The Standard Model considers mass as an intrinsic characteristic of particles, originating from the highly complex Higgs mechanism. Both models have fundamentally different concepts of mass.

8. Energy and the number of matter-charges

In S1, $|E_e|$ denotes the number of matter-charges included in the rest energy E_e of the electron.

The nuances here must be explained through a thought experiment and can also be considered the theory of relativity about “photon energy.”

a. New train thought experiment

The “train thought experiment” established by Einstein enabled the recognition that “simultaneity” has relativity. The new train thought experiment, which has a small variation from the original experiment, can help us understand the subtle relationship between the amount of matter-charges, relative velocity, and energy.

Consider two identical trains A and B, as well as two parallel train tracks that are spatially immobile. The two ends of each train are labeled (A1 and A2 and B1 and B2), and each end contains an identical light emitter that can emit photons of the same frequency, i.e., the same color and energy.

Alice and Bob are caught between these two trains.

Train A is parked on the track, while Train B is traveling quickly, and the spatial positions of the two trains will eventually coincide. Fig. S2.4 depicts this situation.

Figure S2.4. New train thought experiment.

When Alice and Bob see these four light emitters, the outcome is as follows.

When the viewers look at the train they are riding in, they notice that the light emitted at both ends of the train has the same hue, indicating that the same energy is being observed.

When they looked at each other, Alice notices that the B1 end was heading away, while the B2 end was approaching. The light emitted by B1 was red-shifted, while that emitted by B2 was blue shifted because of the Doppler effect.

Hence, Alice noticed that the two ends of train B emitted two beams of light with different colors, frequencies, and energies.

Similarly, Bob noticed that the two ends of train A released two beams of light of distinct colors, frequencies, and energies. The light released at A1 end was more energetic.

Thus, each observer believes that the two ends of the train they are riding in emit the same amount of light energy, while the photons generated by the two ends of the other vehicle have distinct “energy”; this is not a subjective belief and can be confirmed by experiments, as in the case of the photoelectric effect.

What is the difference among the photons emitted by the two trains?

Let us start with train A.

Because train A is generally spatially immobile, the photons released by A1 and A2 should be simi-

lar, yet Bob detects a difference in “energy.” Hence, we must distinguish between the two conceptions of “quantity of matter-charges” and “energy.” We reach the following conclusion.

The photons emitted by A1 and A2 have the same amount of matter-charges, but they reach Bob with different relative speeds, resulting in a distinct consequence. Photons that reach Bob have more “energy,” and the faster they go, the more energy they have.

Hence, the “energy” of a photon is not a set value; instead, it is related to at least two elements: the amount of matter-charges that comprise the photon and the velocity relative to the observer.

Next, consider Train B.

Because the photon energy from B1 is less than that from B2 and because both reach Alice at the speed of light, the photons from B1 carry less matter-charges.

However, because Bob moves in space, photons reaching from B1 to Bob have higher relative velocities.

The photons reaching from B2 to Bob are the inverse. Hence, for Bob, photons from B1 have the same energy as those from B2.

It can also be seen in this process that if the luminous body moves in space, the photons released in the direction of its motion will carry more matter-charges, and according to Alice, they will have more energy.

The radius of the photon is $r = \frac{\hbar c}{E}$; therefore, the photon in this direction will have a smaller radius according to Alice, though Bob in the other inertial frame will not concur at this point.

Hence, the photons emitted from train B will have varying radii depending on the velocity direction of the train and the direction of emission of the photon. In relativity, this is illogical. Will photons with the same energy but different radii produce different experimental phenomena? For example, when they pass through the same narrow slit? Or can these radii be measured or compared experimentally? This may demand an unrealistically high level of experimental

precision, but if such differences can be detected experimentally, it will prove to be another shortcoming in the principle of relativity.

b. Matter-charges and energy

The rest energy of an electron is E_e , however, for an electron relative to earth or any other frame of reference, which is stationary to the observer, must carry a greater number of matter-charges than $|E_e|$, because the speed of motion of our inertial system in space is unknown and it is not static.

We do not know if the number of matter-charges carried by a photon with energy E is larger or less than $|E|$ since we do not know the direction of motion of our inertial system in space. It seems that we also have no way to measure the specific quantity corresponding to $|E|$.

However, neither the idealized inertial frame relative to the space station nor the measurement of the amount of matter-charges is necessary. These two objectives are too challenging, and we should simplify them. In any case, most physical events adhere to the principle of relativity, and we can assume that every inertial frame is an ideal inertial frame. The principle of relativity is then used to calculate and characterize the physical phenomena through the application of energy.

Although matter-charges constitute the underlying essence of physical phenomena, energy is the physical quantity required to calculate and describe physical events in all inertial frames. Energy can be considered the effective value produced by the matter-charges.

9. Conclusions

Both the special theory of relativity and the explanations provided in this paper are logically self-consistent; however, they present fundamentally different frameworks. This model offers a more concise

and clear explanation for mass and energy relationships. In addition to the relativistic effects and particle models already discussed, subsequent sections will demonstrate the derivations related to quantum mechanics and interactions, and show how these concepts can be integrated into a unified theoretical framework. However, none of the existing theoretical frameworks has yet managed to achieve such integration effectively.

S3: Derivation of Coulomb- and Lorenz- Force Formula

1. Introduction

The physical properties of a positive charge are derived from the matter-charges Y_+ , while those of a negative charge are derived from the matter-charges Y_- , when the two are equal, the amount of Y corresponds to the energy and appears to be electrically neutral. However, we have not explained why matter-charge exhibits charge properties or why the interaction between matter-charges gives rise to electromagnetic interactions. This point is discussed in this section.

The matter-charge hypothesis incorporates two adjustments compared to previous physics models. First, a definite conversion connection between energy and the quantity of electric charge is established. Second, many matter-charges are considered to exist in space. Hence, it is possible to derive the basic formula of electromagnetic interaction.

Eventually, we see that the morphologies of the Coulomb force formula and the Lorentz force formula are virtually identical:

$$F_{\text{Coulomb}} = \frac{q_1 q_2 \times c^2}{r^2} \times 10^{-7}, \quad (\text{S3.1})$$

$$F_{\text{Lorentz}} = \frac{q_1 q_2 \times v_1 v_2}{r^2} \times 10^{-7}. \quad (\text{S3.2})$$

2. Preparation before deduction

In S1, we introduced the transition between energy and the amount of electricity charge, i.e., the amount of matter-charges in the electron rest energy is the same as that in unit charge:

$$|E_e| = |e|. \quad (\text{S3.3})$$

Accordingly, we can establish a relation among the amount of electric charge q , energy E , and the number of matter-charges $|E|$ or $|q|$:

$$q = \frac{E}{E_e} \times e, \quad (\text{S3.4})$$

$$|q| = \frac{q}{e} \times |e|, \quad (\text{S3.5})$$

$$|q| = \frac{E}{E_e} \times |e|. \quad (\text{S3.6})$$

Furthermore, the matter-charges in space must be incorporated into physical processes. Both the Coulomb and the Lorentz forces must be realized by means of the electromagnetic field in space, and the electromagnetic field is the specific distribution of the matter-charges in space under the matter-charge hypothesis.

Furthermore, two constants related to the matter-charges in space must be defined: the density M and the length s of the matter-charges in space. These two quantities, like $|e|$, are constants; nonetheless, their exact values cannot be defined. However, they play a substantial physical role in the matter-charge concept.

The number of pairs of matter-charges in space within a unit cube is M , i.e., the number of Y_+ in each cubic meter is M , as is the number of Y_- .

Let s (in meters) be the spatial scale of a monomer matter-charge. This distance is exceedingly small compared to the macroscopic scale, though it is nonzero. It is the smallest working distance in space between matter-charges, and it does not imply that only one matter-charge can exist inside the distance s .

The number of Y at the smallest spatial scale, i.e., the point position, or within s^3 cubic meters is as follows:

$$s^3 \times M. \quad (\text{S3.7})$$

3. Derivation of the Coulomb force formula using the matter-charge hypothesis

In adjacent spaces, a charged body creates an electric field, and another charged body in the electric field experiences a Coulomb force.

Coulomb force acts between two charged materials A and B in space if they have a positive charge q_1 and a negative charge q_2 , respectively, and the distance between them is r m.

The matter-charge theory is more concerned with the amount of matter-charges than with the amount of electric charge. Hence, we must first convert the quantities of electricity q_1 and q_2 carried by the two charged entities into the number of matter-charges using Eq. (S3.5).

$$|q_1| = q_1 \times \frac{|e|}{e}, \quad (\text{S3.8})$$

$$|q_2| = q_2 \times \frac{|e|}{e}, \quad (\text{S3.9})$$

which are the number of Y_+ carried by charged body A and the number of Y_- carried by charged body B, respectively.

The electric field inevitably comes from the interaction between some matter-charge carried by a charged body and the matter-charge in space, that is, charged body A carries Y_+ with certain q_1 , which will be neutralized by Y_- in the neighboring space with an equal amount; Y_+ will then be excited by an equal amount and spread outward. The electric field is the state in which $Y_{\pm}$ in space is excited from equilibrium to imbalance, and from equal to unequal.

While charged body A finally excites a specified amount of Y_+ at the position of charged body B after

many contacts with Y in space. The distance between the two charged bodies is r m, and the length of action between the matter-charges is s m.

$$n = \frac{r}{s}, \quad (\text{S3.10})$$

where s is extremely small and n is extremely large.

a. Excitation of Y_+ by charged body A

The excitation of charged body A in space is a spherical wave. The degree of matter-charge excitation should be inversely proportional to the spherical area ($4\pi r^2$). According to the Huygens-Fresnel principle, however, every point on the secondary wave front can regarded a source, and new spherical waves can originate in all directions. When all activities are superimposed at every point in space, the degree of excitation of the matter-charges is no longer inversely proportional to the square of the distance; rather, it follows Fresnel's hypothesis: the wave disturbance is inversely proportional to the distance.

As the Y_+ carried by charged body A is excited in all directions, the number of Y_+ excitations at the position of charged body B can be calculated as follows:

$$\frac{|q_1|}{\frac{4\pi r}{s}}. \quad (\text{S3.11})$$

b. Excitation of Y_- by charged body B

The number of Y_- carried by charged body B is $|q_2|$, and when it acts with matter-charges at its own point in space, the excitation number is $|q_2|$. The number of matter-charges at a space point is $s^3 \times M$; therefore, of all the $Y_{\pm}$ at the spatial point where charged body B is located, the proportion of Y_- excitation is given by

$$\frac{|q_2|}{M \times s^3}. \quad (\text{S3.12})$$

c. *Energy emitted from space at the location of charged body B*

Therefore, in the $Y_{\pm}$ at the point in space where charged body B is located, the number of simultaneous excitations of Y_+ and Y_- is given by

$$\frac{|q_1|}{\frac{4\pi r}{s}} \times \frac{|q_2|}{M \times s^3}. \quad (\text{S3.13})$$

Then, from Eq. (S3.6), the number of pairs of matter-charges is converted into energy, where E_1 is the energy excited by charged bodies A and B at the position of B.

$$E_1 = \frac{|q_1|}{\frac{4\pi r}{s}} \times \frac{|q_2|}{M \times s^3} \times \frac{E_e}{|E_e|}. \quad (\text{S3.14})$$

For convenience of the subsequent calculations, the formula is organized as follows:

$$E_1 = \left(\frac{|q_1| \times |q_2|}{M \times s^3} \times \frac{s}{4\pi} \times \frac{E_e}{|e|} \right) \times \frac{1}{r}. \quad (\text{S3.15})$$

d. *Coulomb force formula*

Charged body B carrying Y_- will move closer in the direction where Y_+ is active. When there is a slight displacement Δd , the gap between A and B changes, and the excited energy also changes:

$$E_2 = \left(\frac{|q_1| \times |q_2|}{M \times s^3} \times \frac{s}{4\pi} \times \frac{E_e}{|e|} \right) \times \frac{1}{r - \Delta d}. \quad (\text{S3.16})$$

E_1 and E_2 are the energies that can be excited in space; however, only $\Delta E = E_1 - E_2$ is the energy obtained by charged body B before and after moving. In this process, the energy changes to ΔE , the position changes to Δd , and the force can be calculated according to the formula $F = \frac{\Delta E}{\Delta d}$:

$$\begin{aligned} F &= \frac{\Delta E}{\Delta d} = \frac{E_1 - E_2}{\Delta d} \\ &= \frac{\left(\frac{|q_1| \times |q_2|}{M \times s^3} \times \frac{s}{4\pi} \times \frac{E_e}{|e|} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{r - \Delta d} \right)}{\Delta d} \\ &= \left(\frac{|q_1| \times |q_2|}{M \times s^3} \times \frac{s}{4\pi} \times \frac{E_e}{|e|} \right) \times \frac{\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{r - \Delta d}}{\Delta d} \\ &= \left(\frac{|q_1| \times |q_2|}{M \times s^3} \times \frac{s}{4\pi} \times \frac{E_e}{|e|} \right) \times \frac{\frac{r - (r - \Delta d)}{r \times (r - \Delta d)}}{\Delta d} \\ &= \left(\frac{|q_1| \times |q_2|}{M \times s^3} \times \frac{s}{4\pi} \times \frac{E_e}{|e|} \right) \times \frac{\frac{\Delta d}{r^2 - r \times \Delta d}}{\Delta d} \\ &= \frac{|q_1| \times |q_2|}{M \times s^3} \times \frac{s}{4\pi} \times \frac{E_e}{|e|} \times \frac{1}{r^2 - r \times \Delta d}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S3.17})$$

As Δd is extremely small, the aforementioned equation can be simplified into

$$F = \frac{|q_1| \times |q_2|}{M \times s^2} \times \frac{1}{4\pi} \times \frac{E_e}{|e|} \times \frac{1}{r^2}. \quad (\text{S3.18})$$

Using the form of the Coulomb force formula, it can be rewritten as

$$F = \left(\frac{1}{4\pi \times M s^2} \times \frac{E_e}{|e|} \right) \times \frac{|q_1| \times |q_2|}{r^2}. \quad (\text{S3.19})$$

Substituting Eqs. (S3.8) and (S3.9) into the above equation, i.e., by converting the number of matter-charges into the amount of electric charge, we get

$$F = \left(\frac{|e|}{e} \right)^2 \times \left(\frac{1}{4\pi \times M s^2} \times \frac{E_e}{|e|} \right) \times \frac{q_1 \times q_2}{r^2}. \quad (\text{S3.20})$$

A comparison with the Coulomb force formula,

$$F = k_e \times \frac{q_1 \times q_2}{r^2}, \quad (\text{S3.21})$$

shows that the two forms are similar. The preceding discussion on the case that charged materials A and B have heterogeneous charges; if they have identical electrical properties, they will repel each other and exhibit Coulomb repulsion; nonetheless, the basic form of Eq. (S3.20) remains unaltered.

4. Simplified form of the Coulomb force formula

The vacuum permeability μ_0 is constant:

$$\mu_0 = 4\pi \times \frac{10^{-7}\text{N}}{\text{A}^2}. \quad (\text{S3.22})$$

The relationship between μ_0 and the vacuum capacitance ε_0 is given by

$$\varepsilon_0 = \frac{1}{\mu_0 \times c^2}. \quad (\text{S3.23})$$

The Coulomb constant is, in turn, related to ε_0 as follows:

$$k_e = \frac{1}{4\pi \times \varepsilon_0}. \quad (\text{S3.24})$$

Substituting Eqs. (S3.22) and (S3.23) into Eq. (S3.24), regardless of the dimensions, the numerical part is given by:

$$k_e = \frac{1}{4\pi \times \varepsilon_0} = \frac{\mu_0 \times c^2}{4\pi} = \frac{4\pi \times 10^{-7} \times c^2}{4\pi} = c^2 \times 10^{-7}, \quad (\text{S3.25})$$

where 10^{-7} originates from the definition of the unit of amperes, and the numerical core of k_e is c^2 .

From Eqs. (S3.21) and (S3.25), regardless of the dimensions, a concise form of the Coulomb force is obtained as follows:

$$F = \frac{q_1 q_2 \times c^2}{r^2} \times 10^{-7}. \quad (\text{S3.26})$$

5. Derivation of the Lorentz force formula using the matter-charge hypothesis

A magnetic field is created by a moving charged body. Lorentz forces are applied to another charged entity traveling in a magnetic field.

Current generates a magnetic field. The most basic current is a linear forward movement of a charged particle (charged body A), and it also generates the most basic magnetic field. The Lorentz force is formed if another charged particle (charged body B) moves

within the magnetic field generated by the aforementioned current. This is the Lorentz force obtained by using the fewest elements.

Consider charged body A with a positive charge q_1 and moving along the paper surface with velocity v_1 from bottom to top. It will produce a magnetic field.

When the path distance from charged body A is r , it skims through charged body B carrying negative charge q_2 with velocity v_2 , and the direction is within the plane of the paper, as illustrated in Fig. S3.1.

Figure S3.1. Lorentz force formed by two moving point charges.

The Lorentz force is formed by the magnetic field generated by the motion of charged body A and the motion of charged body B in this magnetic field.

As in the case of the Coulomb force, we must determine the number of Y_+ and Y_- excited by the two charged entities, combine them as $Y_{\pm}$, convert it to energy, and finally calculate the force.

However, unlike the Coulomb force, we must consider not only the excitation induced by the matter-charges carried by these two charged bodies, but also the consequences of their motion.

a. Excitation of Y_+ by the motion of charged body A

First, as with Eqs (S3.8) and (S3.11), charged body A excites a specific amount of matter-charge in space. The positive charge carried by charged body A is q_1 , and the corresponding number of matter-charge is given by

$$|q_1| = q_1 \times \frac{|e|}{e}. \quad (\text{S3.27})$$

When the distance from the path of charged body A is r , the number of positive matter-charges that will be excited by charged body A is given by

$$\frac{|q_1|}{\frac{4\pi r}{s}} = \frac{q_1}{4\pi \times \frac{r}{s}} \times \frac{|e|}{e}. \quad (\text{S3.28})$$

The excitation as per Eq. (S3.28), from Y_+ of $|q_1|$, is the excitation caused by the interaction of $Y_{\pm}$ in space at the speed of light c .

The velocity v_1 of charged body A relative to space will lead to additional interactions and excitations:

$$\frac{q_1}{4\pi \times \frac{r}{s}} \times \frac{|e|}{e} \times \frac{v_1}{c}. \quad (\text{S3.29})$$

As at the end of S2, we described energy, which is the effect of the amount of matter-charges versus the relative velocity.

b. Excitation of Y. by the motion of charged body B

The negative charge carried by charged body B is q_2 , and the corresponding quantity of matter-charge is given by

$$|q_2| = q_2 \times \frac{|e|}{e}. \quad (\text{S3.30})$$

Furthermore, owing to velocity v_2 of charged body B, an additional quantity of excitation is introduced as follows:

$$q_2 \times \frac{|e|}{e} \times \frac{v_2}{c}. \quad (\text{S3.31})$$

At the point location, within s^3 cubic meters, the number of pairs of positive and negative matter-charges present is $M \times s^3$. Thus, at the location of charged body B, the proportion of Y. excited by the motion behavior of charged body B is given by

$$\frac{q_2 \times \frac{|e|}{e} \times \frac{v_2}{c}}{M \times s^3}. \quad (\text{S3.32})$$

c. Energy excited from space owing to the motion of two charged bodies

Eventually, owing to the motion of the two charged bodies, the number of $Y_{\pm}$ that are simultaneously excited at the position of charged body B is given by

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{q_1}{4\pi \times \frac{r}{s}} \times \frac{|e|}{e} \times \frac{v_1}{c} \times \frac{q_2 \times \frac{|e|}{e} \times \frac{v_2}{c}}{M \times s^3} \\ &= \frac{q_1 \times q_2}{4\pi r} \times \left(\frac{|e|}{e}\right)^2 \times \frac{v_1 \times v_2}{M \times s^2 \times c^2}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S3.33})$$

Converting the number of $Y_{\pm}$ into energy, we get

$$\begin{aligned} E_1 &= \frac{q_1 \times q_2}{4\pi r} \times \left(\frac{|e|}{e}\right)^2 \times \frac{v_1 \times v_2}{M \times s^2 \times c^2} \times \frac{E_e}{|e|} \\ &= \left(\frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi \times M s^2} \times \frac{v_1 v_2}{c^2} \times \left(\frac{|e|}{e}\right)^2 \times \frac{E_e}{|e|}\right) \times \frac{1}{r}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S3.34})$$

d. Obtaining the Lorentz force formula

As B is subjected to Lorentz forces, by causing it to undergo a slight displacement Δd , we can obtain the free energy at this time as follows:

$$E_2 = \left(\frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi \times M s^2} \times \frac{v_1 v_2}{c^2} \times \left(\frac{|e|}{e}\right)^2 \times \frac{E_e}{|e|}\right) \times \frac{1}{r - \Delta d}. \quad (\text{S3.35})$$

The force at this time can be calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} F &= \frac{E_1 - E_2}{\Delta d} \\ &= \frac{\left(\frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi \times M s^2} \times \frac{v_1 v_2}{c^2} \times \left(\frac{|e|}{e}\right)^2 \times \frac{E_e}{|e|}\right) \times \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{r - \Delta d}\right)}{\Delta d} \\ &= \left(\frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi \times M s^2} \times \frac{v_1 v_2}{c^2} \times \left(\frac{|e|}{e}\right)^2 \times \frac{E_e}{|e|}\right) \times \frac{1}{r^2 - r \times \Delta d}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S3.36})$$

When Δd is extremely small, the formula is given by

$$F = \frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi \times Ms^2} \times \frac{v_1 v_2}{c^2} \times \left(\frac{|e|}{e}\right)^2 \times \frac{E_e}{|e|} \times \frac{1}{r^2}. \quad (\text{S3.37})$$

This formula needs to be rearranged further.

e. Existing Lorentz force formula

If the existing electromagnetism formula is used, according to the Biot-Savart law, the magnetic field generated by point charge A at distance r is given by

$$B = \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \times \frac{q_1 v_1}{r^2}. \quad (\text{S3.38})$$

According to the Lorentz force formula, the force of charged body B in the magnetic field is given by

$$\begin{aligned} F = qvB &= q_2 \times v_2 \times \frac{\mu_0}{4\pi r^2} \times q_1 v_1 \\ &= \frac{q_1 q_2 \times v_1 v_2}{4\pi r^2} \times \mu_0. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S3.39})$$

From Eq. (S3.22), regardless of the dimensions, we get

$$F = \frac{q_1 q_2 \times v_1 v_2}{r^2} \times 10^{-7}. \quad (\text{S3.40})$$

6. Simplified form of the Lorentz force formula

Next, we proceed to rearrange the Lorentz force formula derived from the matter-charge hypothesis given by Eq. (S3.37). From Eqs. (S3.20) and (S3.21), we get

$$k_e = \left(\frac{|e|}{e}\right)^2 \times \frac{1}{4\pi \times Ms^2} \times \frac{E_e}{|e|}. \quad (\text{S3.41})$$

Reconsidering Eq. (S3.25), we get

$$\left(\frac{|e|}{e}\right)^2 \times \frac{1}{4\pi \times Ms^2} \times \frac{E_e}{|e|} = c^2 \times 10^{-7}, \quad (\text{S3.42})$$

where M , s , and $|e|$ are all nonmeasurable constants, and we adjust them to the left-hand side of the equation as follows:

$$\frac{Ms^2}{|e|} = \frac{E_e}{e^2} \times \frac{1}{4\pi} \times \frac{10^7}{c^2}. \quad (\text{S3.43})$$

It can be further rewritten as follows:

$$E_e = \frac{Ms^2}{|e|} \times 4\pi \times c^2 \times e^2 \times 10^{-7}. \quad (\text{S3.44})$$

Substituting the above into Eq. (S3.37), we get

$$\begin{aligned} F &= \frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi \times Ms^2} \times \frac{v_1 v_2}{c^2} \times \left(\frac{|e|}{e}\right)^2 \times \frac{1}{|e|} \\ &\quad \times \frac{1}{r^2} \times \frac{Ms^2}{|e|} \times 4\pi \times c^2 \times e^2 \times 10^{-7} \\ &= \frac{q_1 q_2 \times v_1 v_2}{r^2} \times 10^{-7}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{S3.45})$$

Thus, the Lorentz force formula derived from the matter-charge theory is identical to that derived from the existing formulas in electromagnetism.

Furthermore, the Coulomb force formula given by Eq. (S3.26) can be rewritten similar to the Lorentz force formula given in Eq (S3.45). The former emphasizes that charged body carrying matter-charge interact with the surrounding matter-charge in space at the speed of light. The latter emphasizes that the velocity of charged body in space affects their interaction with the surrounding matter-charge.

7. Magnetic field in the matter-charge hypothesis

Positive and negative electric fields can be distinguished in electric fields; however, magnetic fields cannot. We can see more details based on the matter-charge concept.

At each point in space, Y_+ and Y_- are equal. When an external positive charge neutralizes Y_- , it excites Y_+ . The positive electric field corresponds to the corresponding space. The number of excited Y_+ fluctuates with distance in this space near the positive charge, generating a constant spatial distribution. Negative electric fields are analogous.

However, if a foreign positive charge moves in space at a uniform velocity v , the intensity of Y_+ at

each location in nearby space increases by $\frac{v}{c}$, which corresponds to the same value of Y_- intensity. Furthermore, the positive electric field that it generates appears to travel together with a positive charge.

The intensity of Y_- increases by $\frac{v}{c}$ when the positive charge is replaced by a negative charge, and the intensity of action of Y_+ reduces by the same value. However, in the opposite direction opposite to v , the intensity of activity of Y_+ increases by $\frac{v}{c}$, while that of the action of Y_- decreases.

Hence, the magnetic field generated by the positive charge in motion is comparable to that generated by the negative charge in motion in the opposite direction, resulting in an increase in Y_+ and a decrease in Y_- .

Hence, for the sake of simplicity, the magnetic field can be considered the convection of Y_+ and Y_- in space. The magnetic field generated by the annular current can also be visualized as eddy currents formed by Y_+ and Y_- in space.

8. Conclusions

Using the most fundamental assumptions of the matter-charge hypothesis, we obtained the Coulomb and Lorentz force formulas, characterized their underlying physical processes, and structured them into consistent forms.

We demonstrated the active nature of the electric field and the passive nature of the magnetic field using this method, and they correspond to the Gaussian law and the Gaussian law of magnetism in Maxwell's equations, respectively.

Furthermore, although in this work, only the constant electromagnetic field was examined, the law underlying the time-varying electromagnetic field can be equally easily understood. This is because, according to the matter-charge hypothesis, two factors affect the degree of excitation of matter-charges in space: the amount of matter-charges excited by the charged body and the speed of the charged body. Regardless of

whether the former factor (corresponding to changes in the electric field) or the latter factor is changed (corresponding to changes in the magnetic field), they all effects the matter-charges in space; hence, electricity and magnetism can certainly transform each other. These results can be linked to Faraday's induction law and the direction indicated by the Maxwell-Ampere law in Maxwell's equation.

The electromagnetic model under the matter-charge hypothesis not only describes situations consistent with Maxwell's equations but also combines Maxwell's equations with the Lorentz force formula. Hence, from the viewpoints of electromagnetism and electromagnetic interactions, this section supports the matter-charge hypothesis. However, there are some differences here.

The first is the difference in energy cognition. According to the matter-charge hypothesis, an electric or magnetic field only changes the excited state of the matter-charges in space, and the Y in space is extracted as energy only when certain circumstances are met. However, energy is a feature of electric and magnetic fields according to the known theories of electromagnetism.

The second difference is related to photons. According to S1, photons are the most fundamental particles, classical structures defined by the particle toroidal-orbit model. Details of photon fluctuations will be provided in S4. According to the current electromagnetism theory, photons are principally dynamically overlapping electric and magnetic fields, and photon energy is electromagnetic field energy.

Furthermore, this part solely considered the stationary ideal inertial frame of relative space. However, it can be easily derived that electromagnetic interactions will obey the principle of relativity in any inertial frame, as previously described.

Finally, we did not cover the direction of the Lorentz force, which will be discussed in the following section.

S4: Basic Content of Quantum Mechanics

1. Introduction

Special relativity investigates the rules of physics at high speeds, and quantum mechanics investigates the microscopic world, but within the framework of the particle toroidal-orbit model and the matter-charge hypothesis, both theories revert to classical physics and form an understandable and describable unified whole. The fact that microscopic particles exhibit wave-particle duality is an essential reason that quantum mechanics believes the microscopic world has different physical rules. Let us consider an electron in motion: is it a particle or a wave?

2. Wave-particle duality

Electrons are viewed as particles in classical physics and move as per classical motion. Electrons exhibit wave-particle duality and follow wave functions according to quantum mechanics. However, the matter-charge theory states that an electron is a classical structure generated by matter-charges that may be characterized by the particle toroidal-orbit model. The kinetic energy of the particle gives the precise quantity of matter-charges, which will interact with the matter-charges in space and trigger periodic orbits and fluctuations outside the electron, depending on the kinetic energy of the electron.

Hence, in a narrow sense, electrons are the toroidal-orbit structure discussed in S1, while in a broad sense, electrons are the toroidal-orbit structure formed by their own matter-charge, combined with the range-dependent fluctuations formed by matter-charge in space excited by the kinetic energy of electrons, which is also a toroidal-orbit structure but outside the electron. The two toroidal-orbit constructions are joined. Similarly, photons are, in a broad sense, composite structures generated by the matter-charges in photons and the excited fluctuations of the matter-

charges in space.

Wave-particle duality holds that particles have both particle and wave qualities: they exhibit particle properties at some times and wave properties at other times. According to the matter-charge theory, the particle property is derived from the matter-charges generated by the toroidal-orbit model, but the wave property is derived from the matter-charges aroused in space.

If we only discuss the properties of particles, it is sufficient to discuss the toroidal-orbit structure of particles. However, if we want to discuss the motion of particles in space, we also need to consider the fluctuations formed by excited matter-charge in space.

The new model describes complex phenomena such as single-photon double-slit interference experiments with ease. When a photon collides with a double slit, both the matter-charges of the photon and the excited wave in space collide with the double slit. The former will travel through a gap, while the later will generate an interference wave because of the double slit; subsequently, the two will recombine. The wave and particle aspects of the photon are exhibited during this phase, and the quantized single photon can interfere with itself.

The particle and wave properties are both classical and describable according to the matter-charge hypothesis. We can analyze the two independently or describe the total, which is the wave function in quantum mechanics. Both methodologies are reasonable, but the details and perspective of the study differ.

3. Kinetic energies of particles and matter waves

Particle energy is divided into two types: rest energy and kinetic energy. The former gives rise to the toroidal-orbit structure explained in S1; the latter interacts with the matter-charges in space to produce matter waves that surround the particle.

The processes involving light waves and matter waves are identical, and the matter-charges of photons

combine to generate a light wave, which stimulates the matter-charges in space. It has a wave period

$$t_p = \frac{1}{\nu} = \frac{h}{E}, \quad (\text{S4.1})$$

where E represent the photon energy, and $Y_{\pm}$ corresponds to the number $|E|$. Since the speed of photons is c , the distance traveled throughout the period is the wavelength:

$$\lambda_p = c \times t_p = \frac{ch}{E}. \quad (\text{S4.2})$$

The period and wavelength of the waves excited by the kinetic energy of particles are similarly computed. Consider a moving electron with mass m_e , velocity v , and kinetic energy $E_k = \frac{1}{2}m_e v^2$. Regardless of the rest energy of the electron, $Y_{\pm}$ corresponds to $|E_k|$, which allows us to determine its wave-length.

From (S4.1), the period of the electron is

$$t_e = \frac{1}{\nu} = \frac{h}{E_k} = \frac{h}{\frac{1}{2}m_e v^2}. \quad (\text{S4.3})$$

The wave moves at the velocity of electrons, and the distance traveled at a time is

$$s = v \times t_e = 2 \times \frac{h}{m_e v} = 2 \times \frac{h}{p}. \quad (\text{S4.4})$$

The following questions remain unanswered: Why do matter waves result from the kinetic energy of electrons exciting matter-charges in space? Why does Eq. (S4.4) correspond to twice the wavelength of matter waves, i.e., $\lambda = \frac{h}{p}$? How do electrons interact with matter waves?

a. Excitation process of matter waves

In Eq. (S4.3), the matter-charges that are excited by E_k and originate are represented by $|E_k|$, which excites matter waves. Although we have already discussed the particle toroidal-orbit model in detail, we will review a few features here.

The number of matter-charges with $|E_e|$ forms the toroidal-orbit structure of the electron; when the

electron is stationary in space, Y_+ and Y_- are evenly distributed in their respective toroidal-orbits and interact with the same amount of matter-charges, and the number of matter-charges carried by electrons in their toroidal-orbits and that are excited in space have the same spatial distributions.

If the electron acquires extra matter-charges with $|E_k|$, the number of matter-charges in its toroidal-orbit will increase to $|E_e| + |E_k|$; however, the amount of matter-charges in the space containing the toroidal-orbit structure will remain the same at $|E_e|$. To achieve this, the electron must move in space and excite the matter-charges with $|E_k|$ from the space in front of the electron.

These matter-charges with $|E_k|$ excited by the kinetic energy of the electron from space generate the electron matter waves. They rotate around the electron for a specific time, with a forward speed v and a space speed c . They encompass the path of the electron and occupy a specific space.

b. Two spins of electrons

There are two types of electron spins, they correspond to the spin quantum number m_s . According to the particle toroidal-orbit model, the spin of electrons must exhibit a classical behavior, and matter-charges will exhibit two types of rotation when rotating in the electron orbit.

Matter-charges in the toroidal-orbit of electrons interact with those in matter waves beyond electrons. Consequently, there are two symmetrical waves of length $v \times t_e$ and wavelength $\lambda = \frac{1}{2} \times v \times t_e$, which equals the wavelength of matter waves $\frac{h}{p}$.

Consequently, an electron instantaneously stimulates a pair of matter waves traveling in opposite directions with wavelength λ , and each fluctuation can be matched to an electron in a specific spin direction.

Opposite waves can be overlaid to generate a stable standing wave, and a pair of electrons with opposite spins can coexist in matter waves; this structure

is known as an electron orbital.

c. Uncertainty principle

Quantum physics views an electron as a cloud of electrons, but the matter-charge theory considers an electron as a unit composed of the electron and matter waves that surround it. In matter waves, the electron still follows the classical motion, and there is no motion besides that in the direction of motion of the electron.

We reach this conclusion because of the precision of the spin magnetic moment of the electron. Using the particle toroidal-orbit model, in which each item has a distinct physical meaning and the electron is not required to rotate around the axis, one can derive the equation for the magnetic moment of the electron. If an electron does rotate around the speed axis, it contributes to a strong magnetic moment.

In quantum mechanics, however, the ' position and velocity of an electron are indeed unknown. This is because electrons are surrounded by matter waves, without which the direct observation of electrons is impossible. Before the means of observation reach the electron, they interact with the matter-charges in matter waves, which travel to the electrons with speed c . When the means of observation finally reach the electron, their position, direction, and speed have been altered. This is analogous to the observation that when you visit your neighbor, you will always find them at the front door. Therefore, electrons are always visible outside their traditional orbit, and the profile of the electron cloud is likewise dictated by electron-excited matter waves.

d. Pauli exclusion principle

According to the aforementioned structure, if two electrons are in close proximity, their matter waves should already be influencing and interfering with one another before they collide, unless they share the same

matter wave, with the same t_e and λ , and the physical quantities are identical except for spin.

The range of matter waves and the range of electron orbitals are given by the Pauli exclusion principle.

e. Spin angular momentum of electrons and the direction of Lorentz force

The classical radius of the photon is $r = \frac{\hbar c}{E}$. Y_+ and Y_- , which make up photon energy E , are described as two spiral precession lines.

The electron possesses a spin angular momentum, which does not indicate that it is rotating around the velocity axis, but similar to the photon, Y_+ and Y_- form the electron kinetic energy E_k and rotate around the velocity axis.

Consider that the electron has two spin directions and excites waves simultaneously in both directions. So, in each period $T = \frac{h}{E_k}$, $Y_{\pm}$ with $|E_k|$ will rotate about the axis twice, with the rotation radius $r = \frac{\hbar c}{E_k} \times \frac{1}{2}$. Then, the spin angular momentum of the electron is

$$r \times p = r \times \frac{E_k}{c} = \frac{\hbar c}{E_k} \times \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{E_k}{c} = \frac{\hbar}{2}. \quad (\text{S4.5})$$

We were unable to introduce the direction of the Lorentz force in S3, which dealt with electromagnetism; it is introduced here.

The magnetic field is seen as the convection of Y_+ and Y_- . Particles traveling ahead in space stimulate $Y_{\pm}$ there. If the environment in which the particle is located is in a magnetic field, the excited Y_+ and Y_- in space in front of the particle will follow the trend of the magnetic field and move in opposite directions, and their directions of motion will be perpendicular to the direction of motion of the particle.

If the particle has a positive charge, it will be deflected toward Y_- . If it carries a negative charge, it is deflected in the direction of Y_+ , following Fleming's left-handed rule.

4. Quantization and quantum number in electron orbits outside the nucleus

Quantization and wave-particle duality uphold quantum mechanics. Using the matter-charge theory, the electron cloud with wave-particle duality can be redescribed as a combination of electrons and electron-excited matter waves. The electron surrounded by matter waves remains a classical particle with classical motion, and the matter wave is also a classical fluctuation whose wave-length and period can be measured. Quantification can be similarly described.

The Bohr model and Sommerfeld's elliptical orbital theory are revisited herein to explain the quantization conditions, principal quantum number n , angular quantum number l , and magnetic quantum number m using these two models. Further, we describe the spatial distribution of electron clouds, as these are fundamental prerequisites for the application of quantum mechanics and uncover useful new details.

a. Bohr model, principal quantum number n , and energy quantization

According to Eq. (S4.4), when an electron excites a wave in space, the total length is twice the wavelength of the matter wave; hence, two opposed matter waves appear simultaneously. Therefore, when an electron orbits a proton, standing waves are generated. For a standing wave to exist, the wavelength of the matter wave must be equal to the circumference of the orbit:

$$\lambda = 2\pi r. \quad (\text{S4.6})$$

The Bohr model also considers the equivalence of centrifugal and centripetal forces, i.e.,

$$m_e \frac{v^2}{r} = k_e \frac{e^2}{r^2}. \quad (\text{S4.7})$$

From Eq. (S4.4), we see that the angular momentum $\hbar$ of electrons is

$$r \times m_e v = r \times p = \frac{\hbar}{2\pi} = \hbar, \quad (\text{S4.8})$$

and the orbital radius of the ground-state electron is

$$r = k_e \frac{e^2}{mv^2}. \quad (\text{S4.9})$$

In the presence of a standing wave, the next stable condition is

$$C_n = 2\pi r_n = \lambda \times n. \quad (\text{S4.10})$$

In classical models, the fundamental quantum number n represents the number of electron orbital levels. Other physical quantities are related to such orbits as follows:

$$r_n = r_1 \times n^2, \quad (\text{S4.11})$$

$$C_n = C_1 \times \frac{1}{n^2}, \quad (\text{S4.12})$$

$$\lambda_n = \lambda_1 \times n, \quad (\text{S4.13})$$

$$r_n = r_1 \times n^2, \quad (\text{S4.14})$$

$$C_n = \lambda_n \times n. \quad (\text{S4.15})$$

The kinetic energy of different layers of electrons is

$$E_n = E_1 \times \frac{1}{n^2}. \quad (\text{S4.16})$$

The kinetic energy of all atoms, except for hydrogen, in the electron orbit is constant. If there are k protons in an atom, the ground-state kinetic energy of the electron is $E_1 \times k^2$, which is also the ionization energy of the final electron of each atom.

In the electron orbital hierarchy outside the nucleus, regardless of the type of atom or the number of layers of electron orbitals, the orbital energy is related to E_1 . Further, from $\alpha = \frac{v}{c}$, we obtain

$$E_1 = \frac{1}{2}m_e v^2 = E_e \times \frac{1}{2}\alpha^2. \quad (\text{S4.17})$$

The orbital energy is related to E_e . In the matter-charge hypothesis, the quantization basis of energy E_e , E_e is related to the unit charge e as $|E_e| = |e|$, from which the entire physical world is constructed.

b. Quantization in the electronic sublayer

The electronic sublayer will now be discussed. Quantization associated with E_e is also applicable to the sublayer energy of electrons.

The following characteristics of electrons are defined by quantum mechanics:

- Based on their angular quantum number l , the electrons in the electron layer are divided into distinct sublayers.
- In these sublayers, the angular momentum of electrons is $\sqrt{l(l+1)}$.
- The electrons in different sublayers have distinct orientations and different types of electron clouds according to their magnetic quantum number m .

The underlying mechanics are then discussed.

1. Why do electronic sublayers exist

According to Eq. (S4.10), the electron orbit must be circular. $C_n = n \times \lambda_n$ indicates that starting from C_2 , an orbit should contain many pairs of electrons. The kinetic energy of these electrons in the orbit of C_2 should be distinct; otherwise, the Pauli incompatibility principle is violated.

The first pair of electrons in each electronic layer, that is, the electrons in the s sublayer, have rotational speed v_n , orbit perimeter C_n , and energy $E_{(n,s)} = E_n$. If the second pair of electrons continue rotating around C_n with speed v_n but with different speeds in the vertical direction, they will pass through the circular orbit of C_n and enter the elliptical orbit defined

by Sommerfeld. These electron pairs have both spin and vibration, as well as higher kinetic energy, shorter period for their matter waves, and a smaller range.

Different kinetic energies imply that the electron is in a sublayer other than the s sublayer, as indicated by the vertical motion of the electron. Electrons migrate ahead in C_n ring while simultaneously vibrating. The matter waves stimulated by their kinetic energy will envelop the electron orbit and form a range suitable for spatial equilibrium.

2. Mathematical relationship of angular momentum $\sqrt{l(l+1)}$

An orbit $E_{(n,p)}$ in the standing waves must be an integral multiple of $E_{(n,s)}$. In the same layer, the kinetic energy of the higher sublayer must be an integral multiple of that of the lower sublayer, with the multiplier being at least 2. Specifically, the ratio of the electron kinetic energy in each sublayer is given by:

$$E_s : E_p : E_d : E_f = 1 : 2 : 6 : 12. \quad (\text{S4.18})$$

Clearly, the extraordinarily high kinetic energy of electrons in the d and f sublayers is the primary cause of energy-level staggering. Regardless of the atom, electronic layer, or sublayer, all parameters are strongly related to the kinetic energy $|E_e|$ of the electrons. Hence, the relationship between angular momentum and kinetic energy is clear.

When the elliptical orbit of the electrons in the high sublayer intersects the circular orbit of the electrons in the s sublayer, their potential energy and radius r remain the same; their velocity is determined using Eq. (S4.19), and their angular momentum is $r \times p$. Their angular momentum satisfies the following relationship:

$$p_s : p_p : p_d : p_f = 1 : \sqrt{2} : \sqrt{6} : \sqrt{12}. \quad (\text{S4.19})$$

This is the same as $\sqrt{l(l+1)}$ in quantum mechanics.

Although the kinetic and potential energy of a system change continuously, its angular momentum remains constant. Hence, angular momentum is used as the basis for calculations in quantum mechanics. The matter-charge hypothesis focuses on the energy, and therefore on the amount of matter-charges underlying the energy. When the electrons of a high sublayer are far away from the electrons of the s sublayer, its kinetic energy is converted into potential energy, but the overall amount of matter-charge remains constant, i.e., $|E_k| + |E_p|$ remains constant.

The following points apply to kinetic energy:

Because the electron orbits of the p sublayer extend in three directions, thereby creating fluctuations with the same periods but with three distinct states, the kinetic energy of the d sublayer electrons is thrice that of the p sublayer electrons.

The kinetic energy of each sublayer was computed, but it could not be easily verified because of the interactions among the electrons in the system. The final electron of the atom has an ionization energy, which satisfies $13.6\text{eV} \times k^2$, and it can be measured directly and without interference. However, the kinetic energy of the electrons in the sublayer must obey the above equation as long as the angular momentum is characterized by $\sqrt{l(l+1)}$, and the matter wave possesses physical material. More importantly, the classical images we describe, including standing waves, periods, wavelengths, and other classical motion and motion features in the orbit, must exist.

c. Magnetic quantum number and the shape of the electron cloud

The magnetic quantum number m reveals not only the orientation of the electron orbital but also the number of electrons in the sublayer. When the magnetic quantum number of one sublayer is depleted, successive electrons must acquire greater kinetic energy to enter the next sublayer. The magnetic quantum number m takes the values 0, 1, 2, ...

Electrons in a conventional model rotate around the axis. According to the model proposed in this study, regardless of the sublayer, all orbits with $m = 0$ are symmetrical about the axis of rotation, whereas the directions of orbits with $\pm n$ are symmetrical in space. Matter waves produced by electrons will wrap around the classical orbit of the electron, generating three-dimensional (3D) structures in space.

To begin, a 3D coordinate system is created. The electrons in the $1s$ sublayer rotates classically in the toroidal-orbit, and the magnetic moment of the electron or-bit shows that the direction of the velocity of the atom is perpendicular to the orbital plane. The rotation axis of the ring rail can be designated as the z -axis, and the rotation surface of the $1s$ sublayer electrons can be designated as the xy -surface.

All s sublayer electron orbitals are within the xy -plane. Matter waves are shaped like doughnuts in space when they are activated by all the electrons in the s sublayer.

However, when they are not observed, this is simply a theoretical version. The xy -plane will flip when an observation is made, and the electron, as a little magnet created by a circular current, will easily change its orientation under external influence. The observation findings, thus, follow the uncertainty principle. Hence, the electron cloud of the s sublayer particle is represented as a sphere in quantum mechanics.

The classical orbit of the electron and the type of matter waves it excites will be symmetrical about the z -axis for layers other than the s sublayer for $m = 0$ electron pairs.

For each sublayer, we provide a brief description of the electron cloud (or the spatial shape of an excited matter-charge outside the orbit of an electron).

1. First and second layers

A pair of electrons in the $1s$ sublayer revolves around the z -axis on the xy -surface, and the initial form of matter waves is a ring. However, when observed, the shape is spherical.

The same holds true for electrons in the $2s$ sub-

layer, except that in this case, the radius is four times r_1 . The $2p$ sublayer contains three electron pairs, where $m = 0$ is an electron pair whose orbit is on the xy -plane and vibrates about the z -axis. The $m = 1$ electron pairs rotate on the yz -plane and the xz -plane, and their vibration directions are along the x -axis and y -axis, respectively. The matter waves created spindle perpendicular to each other on the perimeter of the three electron pairs, dividing the space into eight quadrants.

2. Third layer

The scenario of the $3s$ and $3p$ substrates is identical to the $2s$ and $2p$ substrates.

However, the $3d$ sublayer has several peculiarities. Because E_{3d} is six times E_{3s} , it rotates with speed v_3 and travels across the xy -plane with speed $v_3 \times \sqrt{6-1} = v_3 \times \sqrt{5}$. Hence, in the $3d$ sublayer, the $m = 0$ electron pair will form a ring between the two ring rails of $1s$ and $2s$ and will also extend in both directions along the z -axis, forming a matter-wave structure in which the toroidal-orbit and spindle coexist.

As matter waves, the two pairs of electrons $m = 1$, which rotate on the xz - and yz -planes and vibrate along the y - and x -axes, respectively, produce four spindles in their corresponding four quadrants.

The two $m = 2$ electron pairs form four spindles extending on the xy -plane and four spindles extending in the direction of the four quadrants in the xy -plane.

Because the toroidal-orbit of the third layer of electrons is very high, r_3 is nine times r_1 , and the matter waves of the $3d$ sublayer electrons disperse; as the primary quantum number increases, it becomes increasingly difficult to recreate a complete picture.

3. Layer 4

The scenarios for $4s$, $4p$, and $4d$ are similar to those for $3s$, $3p$, and $3d$, respectively.

The electrons in the $4f$ sublayer have high kinetic energy, $E_{4f} = E_{4s} \times 12 = E_{1s} \times \frac{3}{4}$, which is higher than E_{3d} .

Because the scale of C_4 is larger, the $4f$ electrons

rotate more slowly in C_4 and the electrons move faster in the vertical vibration direction. So, matter waves excited by the $4f$ electrons resemble separated ring petals. The two $m = 3$ electron pairs should be symmetrical about the z -axis and in the xy -plane as well.

5. Conclusions

The matter-charge concept is similar to Einstein's hidden variable interpretation.

Some people classify quantum theory into three stages, with the aforementioned principles belonging to the first stage. Wave-particle duality, matter waves, four quantum numbers, quantization of energy, and angular momentum, however, eventually reduce to classical physics descriptions. Hence, quantum mechanics and quantum field theory created from the first stage should also reduce to classical physics.

Based on the matter-charge hypothesis and the particle toroidal-orbit model, our understanding of quantum mechanics, special relativity, electromagnetic interactions, and the microstructure of particles has changed. We have gained a new concept of particle integrity that continues the research ideas of classical physics. Moreover, if these two hypotheses constitute the underlying truth of the physical world, research is necessary in more than just the few areas mentioned in literature. All areas of physics should be reexamined and explored in depth. Thus, there remains an overwhelming amount of work to be completed.

S5: Gravitation, General Relativity, and the Density of Matter-Charge in space

1. Introduction

Building upon the matter-charge hypothesis, we recognize the pervasive presence of matter-charges with intrinsic density throughout space. In the context of electromagnetic interactions detailed in S3, we have quantified these entities as M , representing

the concentration of $Y_{\pm}$ per cubic meter. A pivotal inquiry that emerges is the variability of this density in the cosmic expanse. Such fluctuations, if present, would have profound implications for our understanding of gravitation and general relativity. In the forthcoming discussions, we aim to elucidate how the matter-charge hypothesis lends robust and consistent support across various disciplines of physics.

2. The constancy of density M

Wave theory suggests that the propagation speed of a wave through a medium is proportionate to the medium's density. If we posit that the propagation speed of matter-charges in space is similarly tied to their density, then the speed of light would be expected to decrease as density diminishes.

As detailed in S2 regarding special relativity, it was shown that an inertial frame moving through space experiences a reduction in the speed of light relative to its own frame, resulting in the simultaneity of four time-related phenomena. If the speed of light is indeed lower in regions of reduced density, these time-related phenomena would similarly occur, slowing down all motion within that area as if caught in a time trap. However, such a slow-down would go unnoticed by an observer within this low-density zone. Any local measurement of light's speed would still yield the invariant speed c , since the time effect must be considered. Consequently, the observed effects are consistent with those at the standard density M , due to the same reason. Thus, the principle of relativity is expected to hold consistently across various densities.

Therefore, although M is theoretically a variable quantity, for an observer it remains a constant in practical terms, serving as an effective and enduring measurement, analogous to the constant speed of light c .

3. Mechanisms of density change

Consider an ideal space characterized by a matter-charge density of M , which can be diminished through at least two mechanisms.

The first mechanism involves the conversion between kinetic and potential energy. A common example of this energy transformation is the descent of an object. Give a special example, the interaction between the Milky Way and the Andromeda galaxy illustrates this concept. Due to the gravitational attraction, gravitational potential energy is converted into the galaxies' kinetic energy, meaning Y in space is continually depleted. During this conversion, kinetic energy increases, which leads to a reduction in the actual density of matter-charges in space.

The second mechanism pertains to the interactions of Y , carried by particles, with the matter-charges in space. We delineate the division of particles into unit charge and energy. In S3, our focus was solely on the interaction between unit charges and matter-charges in space, in the context of electromagnetic interactions. Nonetheless, energy components, which is also composed of matter-charges, will behave in a manner akin. As a result, a particle's unit charge can neutralize one type of matter-charge and simultaneously excite another, inducing an electric field. In contrast, the energy component neutralizes both types of matter-charges at once, creating regions in space where Y_+ and Y_- are concurrently reduced. This dynamic depicts a gravitational field. At a distance r from a mass source, the density diminishes from $\rho_0 = M \times s^3$ to

$$\rho = M \times s^3 - \frac{|E|}{r}. \quad (\text{S5.1})$$

While the total density of matter-charges in space remains unchanged, the effective density of matter-charges available for interaction is reduced.

4. Distinguishing General Relativity from Gravitation

The rest energy of a particle or a planet, represented by E in Eq. (S5.1), brings about a decline in the effective matter-charge density. This decrease slows the propagation rate of the matter-charge, reduces the speed of light, which in turn precipitates time effects.

Embracing the core tenet of relativity—that the speed of light is invariant—we would infer that time dilation is accompanied by spatial expansion, as postulated by general relativity. In contrast, according to the matter-charge hypothesis, it is not space or time that alters, but rather the effective density of matter-charge in space that changes.

Additionally, Eq. (S5.1) intimates that the effective density of matter-charges in space is not uniform near massive celestial bodies. The total amount of matter-charges, or energy, or mass of the celestial bodies influences the density, which diminishes as distance decreases.

Regions where the effective density of matter-charges lessens with distance are commonly referred to as the universal gravitational fields surrounding massive celestial bodies.

Wave theory predicts that waves in a medium will tend towards regions of lower density or velocity. Consequently, light refracts towards celestial bodies upon entering such regions, akin to being attracted to them. Analogously, substances made of matter-charges exhibit similar behavior, with particles moving towards the celestial bodies, driven by their constituent moving matter-charges and their periodic rotation within toroidal-orbits.

In this context, the number of matter-charges in photons remains unchanged, but as the environmental density decreases, photons express increased energy, resulting in gravitational blue shift. Three parameters are correlated with energy: the quantity of matter-charge, the relative velocity, and the environmental

density.

Particles, dynamic structures of matter-charges, also undergo periodic rotations within their toroidal-orbits, gravitating towards areas of lower density, or towards the celestial bodies. As their altitude varies, so does their velocity, necessitating the acquisition of matter-charges from space that align with their kinetic energy and translate potential energy into kinetic energy.

The matter-charges within the particle's toroidal-orbit interact with the matter-charges in the corresponding region of space. If a particle is at different altitudes, where the available density of matter-charges in space varies, the quantity of matter-charges interacting with it will also differ. Therefore, when a particle falls a tiny distance downwards, the number of matter-charges interacting with it in space will decrease slightly. The additional matter-charges obtained at higher altitudes will not be released externally but will instead contribute to the particle's kinetic energy. Hence, similar to equation Eq. (S3.17), we can determine the force exhibited during this process based on the relationship $F = \frac{\Delta E}{\Delta d}$.

Eventually, a formula analogous to the Coulomb force emerges, proportional to mass and inversely proportional to the square of the distance. This mechanism elucidates how a mass source generates a universal gravitational field and how an object within this field experiences the universal gravitational force.

5. Same and different

The space-time effect in general relativity arises from the diminishing density of matter-charges, whereas universal gravitational attraction is due to the gradient in matter-charge density. Although these two phenomena typically manifest concurrently near celestial bodies, their underlying physical mechanisms differ, necessitating independent investigation.

Within the matter-charge hypothesis, the concept of curved space-time in general relativity is supplanted

by a flat space, described using Descartes' 3D coordinate system. However, an additional coordinate for density (x, y, z, ρ) must be incorporated. While this concept requires further exploration, mathematical expressions of the two theories could be interconvertible.

6. Conclusions

At a seminar in April 1961, C.N. Yang relayed a metaphor, saying that if a marine biologist uses a fishing net with a six-inch mesh, after a long period of careful study, he might observe a pattern that all fish are longer than six inches [27]. Yang then commented that this hypothetical example is quite absurd, however, such instances are easily found in modern physics. Due to the complexity and indirect nature of experiments, people often fail to recognize the selective characteristics of the experiments they conduct. The selection is based on preconceived concepts, which may themselves be unsuitable. [28]

The prevailing view operates on different selections compared to the matter-charge hypothesis. If we adopt the new selection, where space is filled with matter-charges, particles are dynamic structures formed by matter-charges, every entity in the universe is a different structure formed by matter-charges, and all physical actions are interactions between different structures of matter-charges based on the interactions of matter-charges itself, we are presented with an entirely new picture as proposed by the matter-charge hypothesis and the particle toroidal-orbit model.

In fact, this is a remarkably concise model. One can imagine that when two adjacent matter-charges in space interact, the interaction necessarily involve a concept akin to "efficiency," corresponding to the velocity at which the interaction between the matter-charges propagates through space. This efficiency is an intrinsic attribute of the material. When considering human-defined units of time and space, we obtain the constant speed of light (c). Correspondingly,

Planck's constant (h), the fine-structure constant (α), and even the unit charge (e), or in the new model, the fundamental unit of energy (E_e), all stem from the intrinsic attributes of matter-charges, coupled with constants related to geometric structures (π). These constants are the ones used in the derivations earlier in the text.

With such an approach, we not only reinterpret existing knowledge but also have the potential to break through established understanding. For instance, if the mechanism of gravitation proposed in this model is correct, could we effectively harness it? If there are endless matter-charges in space, might there be a way to extract them continuously? The interaction speed between matter-charges is invariably c , yet as the transmission speed of water waves is significantly lower than the velocity of water molecules moving through space and the speed of their mutual interactions, we must question whether the movement speed of matter-charges in space is really just c ? If photons are structures formed by matter-charges, as they traverse vast spaces measured in billions of light-years, they may interact with the matter-charges in that space. Suppose this interaction leads to a reduction in the number of matter-charges within the photon's structure, effectively decreasing its energy, which is the essence of the tired light theory. In that case, photons emanating from more distant galaxies would exhibit a stronger redshift in our observations, giving the impression of an ever-expanding universe. Therefore, as light travels long distances in the universe, the matter-charges in photons might be transferred to the background space, potentially increasing the number of matter-charges in the background space; or could manifest as the cosmic microwave background radiation. Therefore, this would negate the need for the hypothesis of dark energy. If space is abundant with matter-charges, and a portion forms observable particles, through methods described by the particle toroidal-orbit model, constructing our known universe, might it be possible that another portion of the

matter-charges, through an alternative process, forms another universe that overlaps with ours yet is difficult to observe?

Thus, more than 50 years after the feast of new discoveries in fundamental particle physics has ended,

research into matter-charges has not yet formally begun. Much work remains to be explored. Nevertheless, I am convinced that a model that not only fosters deep discussion but also maintains logical consistency and achieves a unified understanding across various domains of physics is what we collectively strive for.

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